

GLOBAL RESEARCH JOURNAL OF BUSINESS MANAGEMENT

VOL. 4, NO. 2: DECEMBER 2024

**ISSN PRINT: 2811-1710
ISSN ONLINE: 2811-1729**

**ASSOCIATION OF MANAGEMENT & SOCIAL
SCIENCES RESEARCHERS OF NIGERIA
(AMSSRN)**

**GLOBAL RESEARCH
JOURNAL OF
BUSINESS
MANAGEMENT
(GRJBM)**

Volume 4, No. 2: December 2024

A Publication of the
**Association of Management and Social
Sciences Researchers of Nigeria (AMSSRN)**

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15657039

Print ISSN: 2 8 1 1 - 1 7 1 0
Online ISSN: 2 8 1 1 - 1 7 2 9

Online Access:

<https://journals.amssr.org/grjbm/category/grjbm/volume-4/vol-4-issue-2/>

ABOUT THE JOURNAL

The *Global Research Journal of Business Management (GRJBM)* is a publication of the Association of Management and Social Sciences Researchers of Nigeria (AMSSRN). It is a peer-reviewed journal published real-time online and two times annually in hardcopy, focusing on cutting-edge research and practical solutions in business management and related disciplines.

Scope

GRJBM invites research articles from a broad spectrum of topics, including but not limited to organizational behavior, strategic management, financial management, human resource management, entrepreneurship, and the impact of technology on business processes.

Vision

To be a global leader in fostering scholarly debates and disseminating high-quality, timely, and impactful research on contemporary business management issues.

Mission

To continuously provide an intellectually stimulating platform for academics, practitioners, and policymakers to share insights, drive innovation, and contribute to the advancement of business management practices worldwide.

EDITORIAL PREFACE

We are pleased to present Volume 4, Issue 2 of the *Global Research Journal of Business Management (GRJBM)*, a publication of the Association of Management and Social Sciences Researchers of Nigeria (AMSSRN). As a trusted platform for the dissemination of impactful research, GRJBM continues to deliver high-quality, peer-reviewed articles that address contemporary challenges and opportunities in the realm of business management.

This issue features an engaging collection of articles that examine critical themes such as financial deepening, employee soft skills, artificial intelligence in entrepreneurship, ownership structures, and the role of insurance premiums in economic growth. Together, these studies reflect the journal's commitment to advancing knowledge and informing practice within Nigeria and beyond.

We are deeply grateful to our contributors for their insightful work and to our reviewers and editorial team for their dedication to maintaining the high standards of GRJBM. The unwavering support of AMSSRN has also been instrumental in the continued success of this journal.

We trust that the articles in this issue will stimulate meaningful discussions and provide actionable insights for researchers, practitioners, and policymakers.

Dr. N. H. Akpanabia

Editor

Prof. Yusuf Zaoka

Editor-in-Chief

ADVISORY BOARD

1. **Prof. Vincent A. Onodugo:** Faculty of Business Administration, University of Nigeria, Nsukka.
2. **Prof. Prince Famous Izedomie:** Department of Accounting, University of Benin, Edo State.
3. **Prof. Tankiso Moloi:** University of Johannesburg, South Africa.
4. **Prof. Godwin Emmanuel Oyedokun:** Department of Management and Accounting, Lead City University, Ibadan.
5. **Prof. Ile Nobert:** Department of Business Administration, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Nigeria.
6. **Prof. Austin U. Nweze:** Rector, Institute of Management & Technology, Enugu State.
7. **Prof. Ezeabasili Vincent:** Department of, Chukwu Emeka Odumegwu University, Igbariam.
8. **Prof. Ado Ahmed:** Department of Management and Accounting, Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University, Bauchi.
9. **Prof. Uche Uwaleke:** Department of Management and Accounting, Nasarawa State University, Keffi,
10. **Prof. T. O. Enudu:** Department of Business Administration, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Nigeria.
11. **Prof. Francis Emeni:** Department of Accounting, University of Benin, Edo State.
12. **Prof. Chike Nwoha:** Department of Accountancy, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Enugu.
13. **Prof. Uche Ugwuanyi:** Department of Accountancy, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Enugu.
14. **Prof. Adanma Eyisi:** Micheal Okpara University, Umudike, Abia State.
15. **Prof. Emmanuel Akpan:** Department of Management and Accounting, Federal University, Otuoke, Bayelsa State.
16. **Associate Prof. Adonai Okonkwo:** Department of Business Administration, Enugu State University of Science and Technology.
17. **Associate Prof. Njogo Bibian:** Bells University, Abeokuta.
18. **Prof. Uche Lucy Onyekwelu:** Department of Accountancy, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, ESUT.
19. **Prof. Aderemi Kabiru Adeyemo:** Lead City University, Ibadan.
20. **Prof. Muhammad Liman Muhammad:** Bayero University, Kano State.
21. **Prof. Ifeoma Mary Okwo:** Enugu State University of Science and Technology.
22. **Prof. Enudu Titus:** Enugu State University of Science and Technology.
23. **Prof. Vitalis Chukwuma Onah:** Charisma University, British West Indies.
24. **Associate Prof. Joseph Achua:** Central Bank of Nigeria, Abuja.
25. **Associate Prof. Israel Omesi:** Ignatius Ajuru University Port-Harcourt.
26. **Dr. Blaize Igiebor:** Central Bank of Nigeria.
27. **Dr. Kennedy Modugu:** HCT Business School, Dubai, United Arab Emirates.
28. **Dr. Nobert Osemeka:** Liverpool Business School, England, United Kingdom.
29. **Dr. Domnic Erah:** Central Bank of Nigeria.
30. **Dr. Ebere Emmanuel Ozioko:** C4 Consulting Nigeria.
31. **Dr. Isokari Francis Ololo:** Questman's Synergistics Limited Abuja.
32. **Dr. Godwin Ogurube:** Nigerian Deposit Insurance Corporation, Abuja.
33. **Dr. Mary Kehinde Salawu:** University of Johannesburg, South Africa.
34. **Dr. Ada Mac-Ozigbo:** National Open University of Nigeria, Abuja.

EDITORIAL BOARD

Editor –in – Chief	Prof. Yusuf Zaoka
Editor	N. H. Akpanabia, PhD
Associate Editors	
Orga Josephine, PhD	Department of Business Administration, ESUT
Onuoha Charity, PhD	Department of Business Administration, ESUT
Ezuh, Gideon, PhD	Department of Business Administration, ESUT
Ajide Folarunshun, PhD, FAMSSRN	Department of Economics, UNILORIN
Leonard Amaefule, PhD, FAMSSRN	Department of Accountancy, IMSU
Ijeoma Orjiakor, PhD, FAMSSRN	Ijeoma Orjiakor, PhD, FAMSSRN
Elias Agbo, PhD, FAMSSRN	Department of Accounting & Finance, GO-UNI
Chukwuebuka Innocent Nnubia, PhD, FAMSSRN	Department of Accountancy, UNIZIK
Eunice Okpalajiego, PhD, FAMSSRN	Department of Economics, GO-UNI
Rachael Iliemena, PhD, FAMSSRN	Department of Accountancy, IMSU
Tony Onotja, PhD, FAMSSRN	Department of Accountancy, BSU
Ann Nwakaego Duru, PhD, FAMSSRN	Department of Accountancy, ESUT
Bertram Agu, PhD, FAMSSRN	Department of Banking & Finance, ESUT
Chinelo Obiekwe, PhD, FAMSSRN	Department of Banking & Finance, MOU
Seini Odudu Abu, PhD	Department of Accounting, Federal University Dutsin-Ma
Uchenna Onyeamaechi, PhD	Department of Management, Abia State University

LIST OF CONTRIBUTORS

1. **Abada Uchechukwu Daniel, PhD:** Department of Accountancy, Madonna University Nigeria, Okija Campus, Nigeria
2. **Achilike I. Nicholas, PhD:** Alex Ekwueme Federal University, Ndufu-Alike, Ikwo, Ebonyi State, Nigeria
3. **Agbadua Oyakhromhe Bamidel:** Department of Banking & Finance, Federal Polytechnic, Auchi, Nigeria
4. **Ale Solomon Akintayo:** Bursary Department, National Open University of Nigeria, Abuja, Nigeria
5. **Allwell Azubuike Onunwor, PhD:** Department of Management, Faculty of Management Sciences, Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Rivers State, Nigeria
6. **Ama Udu:** Department of Business Administration, National Open University of Nigeria, Abuja, Nigeria
7. **Chike Ernest Nwoha:** Department of Accountancy, Faculty of Management Sciences, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Enugu State, Nigeria
8. **Chukwuto Nnamdi Ogochukwu:** Bursary Department, National Open University of Nigeria, Abuja, Nigeria
9. **Clementina Ngozi Onyeze:** Department of Co-operative Economics and Management, Faculty of Management Sciences, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Enugu State, Nigeria
10. **Echereobia Nkiruka Justina, PhD:** Department of Marketing, Federal Polytechnic Nekede, Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria
11. **Ejiofor Emmanuel Onyeka, PhD:** Department of Banking and Finance; Department of Accountancy, Madonna University Nigeria, Okija Campus, Nigeria
12. **Enujioke Isaac Emeka, PhD:** Coal City University, Enugu State, Nigeria
13. **Ezeaku Faith Onyedikachi:** Department of Insurance and Risk Management, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Enugu State, Nigeria
14. **Ese James Ighoroje, PhD:** Department of Banking and Finance, Delta State University of Science and Technology, Ozoro, Delta State, Nigeria
15. **Ibe Emmanuel C.:** Department of Marketing, Federal Polytechnic Nekede, Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria
16. **Nnamdi Nnabuihe Onyenandu:** Department of Business Administration, National Open University of Nigeria, Abuja, Nigeria
17. **Nwokeiwu Johnson, PhD:** Alex Ekwueme Federal University, Ndufu-Alike, Ikwo, Ebonyi State, Nigeria
18. **Okoh Johnson Ifeanyi:** Department of Financial Studies, National Open University of Nigeria, Abuja, Nigeria
19. **Ojeogwu Chike Ignatius:** Department of Banking and Finance, Delta State Polytechnic, Ogwuashi Uku, Delta State, Nigeria
20. **Onu Abara, PhD:** Department of Business Administration and Management, School of Management Sciences, Federal Polytechnic, Ekowe, Bayelsa State, Nigeria
21. **Onyemenonu Paulinus Chijjeze:** Department of Marketing, Federal Polytechnic Nekede, Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria
22. **Onuoha Ijeoma Perpetua, PhD:** Accountancy Department, Alex Ekwueme Federal University, Ndufu-Alike, Nigeria
23. **Okparaka Vincent Chukwuka, PhD:** Department of Insurance and Risk Management, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Enugu State, Nigeria
24. **Timothy Oladele Ishola:** Department of Business Administration, National Open University of Nigeria, Abuja, Nigeria
25. **Ugwa Tochukwu Nonyelum:** Public Administration Department, Akanu Ibiam Federal Polytechnic, Unwana, Ebonyi State, Nigeria

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. **Effect of Savings and Credit Co-Operative Societies (SACCOS) and other Financial Institutions on Financial Deepening, Financial Development and Economic Growth in Nigeria (1982-2021)** 1
Nwoha Chike Ernest; Onyeze Clementina Ngozi; Ugwa Tochukwu Nonyelum
2. **Employee Soft Skills and Competitiveness of Commercial Banks in Rivers State** 17
Onunwor Allwell Azubuike, PhD
3. **Artificial Intelligence and Entrepreneurship: Implications for Sustainable Venture Creation in Nigeria** 41
Onyenandu Nnamdi Nnabuihe; Ishola Timothy Oladele; Udu Ama
4. **Analysing the Effects of Ownership Structure on Financial Performance of Oil Firms in Nigeria** 55
Ejiofor Emmanuel Onyeka, PhD; Abada Uchechukwu Daniel, PhD
5. **Impact of Insurance Premium on Economic Growth in Nigeria; Long Run Approach (1996-2023)** 69
Ezeaku Faith Onyedikachi; Okparaka Vincent Chukwuka, PhD
6. **Outsourcing as a Strategic Tool for Organizational Sustainability: A Study of Manufacturing Firms in Enugu Metropolis** 85
Achilike I. Nicholas, PhD; Nwokeiwu Johnson, PhD; Enujioke Isaac Emeka, PhD
7. **Fuel Subsidy and the Nigerian Sustainable Development** 104
Ighoroje Ese James, PhD
8. **Business Strategy and Performance of Selected Consumer Goods Firms in Enugu State** 120
Onu Abara, PhD
9. **Reduce Strategy: A Tool for Sustainable Packaging in Nigerian Bottling Company, Imo State** 143
Echereobia Nkiruka Justina, PhD; Onyeike Iheanyichukwu Samuel, PhD; Onyemenonu Paulinus Chijieze; Ibe Emmanuel C.
10. **Unravelling Fiscal Policy Effects on Unemployment in Nigeria through ARDL Approach** 159
Agbadua Oyakhromhe Bamidel; Ale Solomon Akintayo; Chukwuto Nnamdi Ogochukwu; Ojeogwu Chike Ignatius; Okoh Johnson Ifeanyi

Effect of Savings and Credit Co-Operative Societies (SACCOS) and other Financial Institutions on Financial Deepening, Financial Development and Economic Growth on Nigeria (1982-2021)

NWOHA, Chike Ernest¹; ONYEZE, Clementina Ngozi²; UGWA, Tochukwu Nonyelum³

¹ Department of Accountancy, ² Department of Co-operative Economics and Management,

^{1 & 2} Faculty of Management Sciences,

Enugu State University of Science and Technology (ESUT),

Enugu State, Nigeria.

³ Public Administration Department,

Akanu Ibiam Federal Polytechnic, Unwana,

Ebonyi State, Nigeria.

toochis.ugwa@gmail.com

08037807847

Abstract

Research Purpose: The elusive nature of economic growth in Nigeria despite financial deepening efforts raises pertinent questions. In this study, we examine the impact of savings and credit co-operative societies (SACCOs) and other financial institutions on financial deepening, financial development, and economic growth in Nigeria from 1982 to 2021. We delve into the specific effects of financial deepening on growth, the influence of financial institutions and market deepening on growth, and the role of financial co-operatives in enhancing financial deepening.

Methodology: This research utilises secondary data from the IMF Findex database and the Federal Directorate of Co-operative Societies. The data analysis employs error correction modelling (ECM) to establish relationships between the variables.

Findings: Our analysis reveals that while the financial deepening index has a positive, albeit insignificant, effect on economic growth, the deepening of financial markets enhances growth, while deepening of financial institutions has a depressing effect. Notably, deepening of finance in co-operatives significantly enhances financial development in Nigeria through co-operative society investment channels.

Conclusion: We conclude that financial deepening does influence economic growth in Nigeria, and financial cooperatives play a crucial role in driving financial deepening.

Recommendations: To engender efficient financial deepening, we recommend institutional reforms in the banking sector. Additionally, we suggest leveraging savings and credit co-operatives as a potent tool for further financial deepening. The policy implication is clear: co-operatives should not be neglected in the pursuit of economic growth.

Key words: *Savings and Credit Co-operative societies (SACCOs), Financial Deepening, Financial Institutions, Financial Markets, Economic Growth.*

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The co-operatives in general and the financial co-operatives in particular constitute a suitable institutional framework for financial deepening as they support inclusive economy and prevent social exclusion. An important but indirect way in which the poor can be helped out of poverty is by accelerating the growth rates of the countries in which they live. A more direct way to achieve this end is by allowing them to convert flows of savings over time into lump sums that can be invested to generate income and reduce susceptibility to shocks, cover life-cycle needs and acquire useful consumer durables. Financial services are important in reducing poverty and in tackling the other dimensions of poverty.

Among the current socio-economic challenges confronting policymakers the world over is the challenge of financial inclusion, an effort geared towards financial deepening. Policymakers at the World Bank and at national levels are currently grappling with the challenge of bridging the financial inclusion gap. This is buoyed by the grim statistics on financial inclusion. As at 2014, two billion adults reported not having an account (Demirgüç-Kunt et al., 2014) and by 2017, about 1.7 billion adults remained unbanked (Demirgüç-Kunt et al., 2018). By 2021, the World Bank report bemoans that despite promising growth in account ownership, only half of adults in developing economies could access extra funds within 30 days if faced with an unexpected expense, and that about half of adults were concerned about one financial stress or the other (Demirgüç-Kunt, et al., 2022).

On the Nigerian front, economic growth has remained elusive, the efforts at financial deepening notwithstanding. This is because finance affects the real economy in several ways and understanding the possible mechanisms through which it may impact on economic growth is essential in order to derive sound policy recommendations. Perhaps, the thread or connection between financial deepening and improvements in a country reflected in economic development is either not existent or has broken down in Nigeria. A possibility is that variables that should have entered the model of economic growth were being left out. Organisations like savings and credit co-operatives (SACCOs) are treasured because of their reach and the role they play in banking the unbanked. The SACCOs help to deepen the economy and make for rural financial inclusion. Regrettably, the roles of the savings and credit co-operatives have remained largely untapped, under tapped, and underappreciated in the Nigerian economy. Unarguably, it is time to

gain a deeper appreciation and understanding of what and how financial co-operatives can contribute to the development of the country (Birchall, 2013). In doing so, there is the need to ascertain whether the savings and credit cooperatives matter in the finance-supply value chain. Consequently, the under-listed research questions guided this study.

- i. What is the effect of financial deepening on economic growth in Nigeria?
- ii. What is the impact of developments in financial institutions and financial markets in the Nigerian economy?
- iii. What is the effect of financial deepening of co-operatives on financial development in Nigeria?

And we hypothesised that:

- i. Financial deepening has no effect on economic growth in Nigeria.
- ii. Deepening of financial institutions and financial markets has no impact on economic growth in Nigeria.
- iii. Deepening of finance in co-operatives has no impact on financial development in Nigeria.

2.0 REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Conceptual Review

The concepts reviewed included financial deepening, economic growth/development, and savings and credit co-operatives (SACCOs).

Financial Deepening

Traditionally, finance has been linked primarily with the accumulation of input factors in the production process, regarding capital as an important input factor and its accumulation as a condition for sustainable economic growth (Jhingan, 2003). In this study, the term financial deepening is used interchangeably with financial development. Financial development has been comprehensively defined as a blend of penetration, access and efficiency of the financial system (Sahay et al. 2015). The penetration/depth component captures the magnitude and liquidity of markets. The access component refers to the capacity of persons to gain access of financial services. The efficiency component denotes the ability of institutions to render financial services to members of the population/the populace at low and affordable price and still maintain sustainable returns. It also captures how active the capital markets of an economy are.

A related concept to financial deepening is financial inclusion. Olatunde (2023) posits that financial inclusion is recognized globally for its potential to catalyse economic advancement, contributing to poverty reduction, employment generation, wealth creation and overall enhancement of welfare and living standards. Financial inclusion is but an aspect of financial development and both are measured differently. In the view of Olatunde (2023), financial inclusion eases entry to basic financial services for a larger segment of a country's populace and businesses, stimulating inclusive economic growth by incorporating the financially disadvantaged

into the economy. The easing of entry constitutes access. Financial inclusion is also concerned with the depth of the financial system because access is not just sufficient. However, the difference between financial deepening and financial inclusion is that financial deepening, beyond accounting for accessibility of financial services to the generality of the populace, is at the same time concerned with the efficiency of the financial system. That is, the ability of the financial system to render the required services at prices within the reach of the low income segments of the society without jeopardising the sustainability of the businesses.

Economic Development

The term economic development is often used interchangeably with economic growth. However, economic growth is just an aspect of economic development (Sen, 1983). GDP growth is identified as an early stage of growth (Terra, Filho & Fonseca, 2021). Economic growth in itself is a phenomenon of market productivity and increases in Gross Domestic Product (GDP).

The intricate relationship between financial development and economic development remains one of the most fervently contested issues in finance literature. Theoretical evidence suggests that financial development has the potential of accelerating economic growth through mobilisation and apportionment of resources to productive investments with higher returns. However, the influences of finance on growth likely hinges on a number of causes such as how mature the financial system of the country is, the stage of economic development, the quality of the relevant institutions, and other elements. While economic development is generally linked to advancements in various pointers such as educational attainment as measured using literacy rates, longevity of life as captured using life expectancy, and standard of living captured using poverty rates, this study specifically adopts GDP per capita because it reflects growing development population. If GDP per capita is improving, it reflects that on the average, the economy is getting better off. For, the progress of a nation, although intertwined with diverse concepts, typically involves advancing economic growth marked by increased productivity (Kuznets, 1966). Development requires a long-run growth. The latter necessitates innovation, bringing about shifts in how the income of a country is distributed and this has ramifications for the general welfare.

Savings and Credit Co-operatives (SACCOs)

Our inquiry into the concept of savings and credit cooperatives would begin with understanding of the concept of co-operatives in general. Consensus appears to exist regarding the concept “co-operative” among the practitioners. Co-operatives are understood as user-owned, user-controlled and user-benefited organisations (Otto & Ukpere, 2011; Karakas, 2019). The core rationale for cooperation stems from the presence of unmet needs among members, coupled with a degree of cohesion and/or homogeneity among these individuals (Groeneveld, 2016). Throughout history, the functioning of co-operatives was guided by a set of ideals (known as the Rochdale Principles) set out in 1884 by the Rochdale Society of Equitable Pioneers in Rochdale, England.

The SAACOs are financial cooperatives. Birchall (2013) posits that the vital rudiments of a financial co-operative are ownership of the organisation, control of the organisation and to whom benefits accrue. According to Birchall, each individual holds ownership in the cooperatives through a single member-share. However, the cooperative does not belong just to the existing group of members but is an intergenerational endowment maintained in the business for the benefit of present and future members. Shares in co-operatives cannot be transferred, eliminating the existence of a market for them. The customers also control the co-operatives. As members, they play an important role in governance, wielding voting power tied to their personal membership. Each member, regardless of their invested capital, holds an equal one-person, one-vote privilege. The customers are also the main beneficiaries. The main preoccupation of the business is to benefit the members rather than to maximise profit. They can expect some of the profits to be distributed to them as a dividend, but this is proportionate to the use they make of the business rather than to their investment.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 2.1 Links between Financial Development, SACCOs and Economic Growth

2.2 Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on both the central proposition of the social capital theory and the Schumpeterian theory of economic development. The Schumpeterian theory is germane for a study of financial deepening and economic growth. On the other hand, the social capital theory captures the human angle and participation that are the hallmarks of the co-operatives.

The Schumpeterian Theory of Economic Development

The most established connection between finance and economic growth could be traced to the work of Schumpeter (1911) in which he contended that investors require credit in order to enhance Investment. Joseph Alois Schumpeter first propounded the theory of economic growth in his work the *Theory of Economic Development* published in German in 1911 (its English version appeared in 1934) which was elaborated and refined but in no way altered (Jhingan, 2003) in any essential respect in his *Business Cycles* (1939) and *Capitalism, Socialism and Democracy* (1942).

The relevance of the Schumpeterian theory for this study is evident in the role that Schumpeter assigned to finance: bank credit is presumed to fund investments, leading to heightened money incomes and prices, fostering a cumulative expansion across the entire economy. His model commences with the disruption of the circular flow, sparked by an entrepreneurial innovation in the form of a new product aimed at profit generation. To disrupt the circular flow, entrepreneurs engaged in innovation receive funding through the expansion of bank credit. And where there are no banks or insufficient formal banking services, mutual organisations like cooperatives spring up to fill the void in providing the much needed intermediation.

The Social Capital Theory

Social capital finds its theoretical roots in a hybrid framework, drawing insights from economists, sociologists, and other social sciences. The early theoretical groundwork is attributed to trio of Pierre Bourdieu, James Coleman and Robert Putnam, each approaching it from distinct perspectives and yielding diverse theoretical and conceptual outcomes.

Bourdieu's (1986) conceptualisation of social capital hinges on acknowledging that capital extends beyond the economic realm and that social exchanges involve more than pure self-interest, necessitating the consideration of capital and profits in all their forms. Like Bourdieu (1986), Coleman (1988) perceived social capital as fundamentally embedded within the social fabric of relationships among individuals. Unlike Bourdieu, who focused on the uneven distribution of social capital in terms of power and status, Coleman was engrossed with social capital emerging as a product of the social structure. Putnam (1995) treated social capital as a public good, and as the amount of participatory potential, civic orientation, and trusts in others available to cities, states or nations. And argued that it is basically the quantity of trust present, serving as a key characteristic in defining the political culture of modern society.

Bourdieu's theory is relevant especially to the place of financial co-operatives in financial deepening and economic growth. The theory underscores that people, acting individually or in

groups, accrue social capital by having established and recognized institutionalised relationships based on mutual acquaintance and acknowledgment. Coleman’s theory is relevant to our study as it relates to the place of savings and credit co-operatives. The theory recognizes that social capital is both private and public good, bringing benefits to all in the group, and not just the organisers of the networks. Putnam’s perspective aligns with Coleman’s notion that social capital is a quality capable of facilitating interpersonal co-operation; while his treatment of social capital as public good is in disparity with Bourdieu’s theory. His notion of all-engaging potential and trust is germane for a study in co-operatives.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

The research design adopted for this study is the *ex-post facto* research design. The research is designed to determine the cause-and-effect relationship between a dependent variable (economic growth) and the independent variables (financial development, Co-operative society savings and co-operative society investment).

The area of study is the Nigerian economy. This work is based on secondary data. The secondary data on measures of financial deepening and economic growth were obtained from various sources, including, the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Statistical Database, the World Bank Global Financial Development Database, the World Bank FinStats, and IMF’s Financial Access Survey, and data obtained from the annual reports of the cooperative societies submitted to the Federal Directorate of cooperative societies.

Model Specification

The purpose of our study is testing the hypothesis that economic growth in Nigeria is related to financial deepening (FD) and that cooperatives contribute to financial deepening.

We specify a model of the form:

$$y_{it} = \alpha_0 + \beta_0 FD_{it} + \beta_1 \frac{Trade}{GDP}_{it} + \beta_2 \frac{FDI}{GDP}_{it} + \beta_3 Inflation_{it} + \epsilon_t \quad (1)$$

And, we propose that savings and credit cooperatives work for financial deepening.

$$\text{We specify a model of the form: } FD_t = \alpha + \beta_1 CSS_t + \beta_2 CSI_t + \beta_3 X_{it} + \mu_t \quad (2)$$

Where y_t represents our measure of economic development at time t , FD represents financial deepening variables, X represents the set of control variables, CSS = Co-operative Society Savings; CSI = Co-operative Society Investment; α = Intercept or Constant; β = Slope of the

regression line concerning the independent variables; μ is the error term. The two control variables included in our model are log of initial GDP and inflation.

Methods of Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics was used to explain the data, and a stationarity test was carried out to test for the presence of unit roots in the time series data. In the presence of unit root problem a vector error correction model was employed to estimate cointegration among the variables.

In order to analyse the effect of the improvement in financial development on economic growth the dynamic model employed in our study was the System GMM (generalised methods of moments) on annual data. The System GMM methodology was developed by Arellano and Bover (1995). To perform this analysis, as a first step, we modified our Equation (1) into the following dynamic panel regression equation:

$$y_{it} = \alpha_0 + \rho y_{i,t-1} + \beta_0 FD_{it} + \beta_3 X_i + u_{it} \quad (3)$$

where $y_{i,t-1}$ is the lagged growth variable with coefficient ρ . All other variables are as explained.

Blundell and Bond (1998) improved the system GMM estimation method and proved that the first difference is better than the GMM estimator. Taking the first difference of Equation (4) we have:

$$\Delta y_{it} = \alpha + \gamma_0 \Delta y_{i,t-1} + \gamma_1 \Delta FD_{it} + \gamma_2 \Delta X_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (4)$$

where Δ is the difference operator, α and γ are parameter estimates, and ε_{it} is the error term.

To model the error correction, we include the lagged error term from Eq.3 in Eq.4 and estimate the model:

$$\Delta y_{it} = \alpha + \gamma_0 \Delta y_{i,t-1} + \gamma_1 \Delta FD_{it} + \gamma_2 \Delta X_{it} + \sigma u_{i,t-1} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (5)$$

where σ is the coefficient of the error correction term. This is the **error correction model (ECM)**. A priori, we expect a negative σ if the error correction must hold.

4.0 DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS/DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

4.2 Data Analysis

The data analyses presented below were done using EViews statistical package (version 10).

	Per capita GDP growth	FD	FI	FM	CSS	CSI
Mean	1.56	0.19	0.19	0.17	12.44	10.61
Median	4.99	0.19	0.19	0.19	12.04	10.74
Maximum	32.13	0.27	0.24	0.32	13.46	11.28
Minimum	-43.4	0.12	0.15	0.09	11.5	9.83
Std. Dev.	18	0.03	0.03	0.05	0.7	0.4
Skewness	-0.44	0.11	0.08	0.27	0.25	-0.53
Kurtosis	2.6	2.58	1.63	3.02	1.42	2.34
Jarque-Bera	1.54	0.37	3.16	0.49	2.52	1.44
Probability	0.46	0.83	0.21	0.78	0.28	0.49
Sum	62.24	7.52	7.76	6.98	273.73	233.45
Sum Sq. Dev.	12630.46	0.05	0.03	0.1	10.21	3.31
Observations	40	40	40	40	22	22

Source: The Researcher from data presented in Table 4.1.1 above.

Hypothesis I: Financial deepening has no effect on economic growth in Nigeria

Preliminary analyses revealed that the variables of our model are integrated of order one, I(1) so we estimated both the long-run (ECM) and the short-run models.

Table 4.2.2. H₀: FD has no effect on economic growth in Nigeria: Long run

Controls: log of initial GDP, Trade/GDP, FDI/GDP, INF					Critical values			Decision
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-cal	Prob.	10%	5%	1%	
C	-36.37	22.18	-1.64	0.11	1.68 4	2.02 1	2.70 4	Accept H ₀
FD	63.84	91.09	0.70	0.49	1.68 4	2.02 1	2.70 4	Accept H ₀

Source: The researcher's computation

Table 4.2.3. H₀: FD has no effect on economic growth in Nigeria: Short run (ECM)

1st Difference Regression	Critical values
---------------------------	-----------------

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-cal	Prob.	10%	5%	1%	Decision
C	0.50	2.30	0.22	0.83	1.684	2.021	2.704	-
D(FD)	65.41	150.53	0.43	0.67	1.684	2.021	2.704	Accept
u_{t-1}	-0.90556	0.249	-3.64	0.001	1.684	2.021	2.704	significant

Source: The researcher’s computation

Table 4.2.2 and Table 4.2.3 above show that the parameter-estimate for financial deepening is positive, indicating a positive effect of FD on economic growth in Nigeria. However, the impact is not statistically significant as the t-cal is less than the critical value in absolute terms. The coefficient of the error correction term reveals about 90.56 per cent of the discrepancy between the long-term and short-term per capita GDP is corrected in the transition from the short run to the long run. We do not reject the null hypothesis that the composite index (FD) has no effect on economic growth in Nigeria.

Hypothesis II: Deepening of financial institutions and financial markets has no impact on economic growth in Nigeria

Table 4.2.4. H_0 : The Long run Model

Controls: log of initial GDP, Trade/GDP, FDI/GDP, INF					Critical values			Reject H_0 ?
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-cal	Prob.	10%	5%	1%	Yes, No
C	21.77	27.86	0.78	0.44	1.68 4	2.02 1	2.70 4	-
FI	-326.79	127.44	-2.56	0.02	1.68 4	2.02 1	2.70 4	Yes
FM	208.622	72.2611	2.887	0.006915	1.68 4	2.02 1	2.70 4	Yes

Source: The researcher’s computation

Table 4.2.5. The short run/ECM Model

Controls: log of initial GDP, Trade/GDP, FDI/GDP, INF					Critical values			Reject H_0 ?
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-cal	Prob.	10%	5%	1%	Yes, No
C	0.63	2.15	0.29	0.77	1.68 4	2.02 1	2.70 4	-
D(FI)	-403.90	156.18	-2.59	0.01	1.68 4	2.02 1	2.70 4	Yes

D(FM)	237.4739	112.3165	2.114328	0.0429	1.68 4	2.02 1	2.70 4	Yes
u_{t-1}	-0.93268	0.226736	-4.1135	0.0003	1.68 4	2.02 1	2.70 4	-

Source: The researcher’s computation

Tables 4.2.4 and 4.2.5 both reveal that while the impact of financial institutions on growth was negative, the impact of financial markets on growth was positive. The coefficient of the error correction term is negative and highly significant. It indicates that about 93.27 percent of the discrepancy between the long-term and the short term per capita GDP is corrected during the transition from the short run to the long run. We reject the null hypothesis that deepening of FI and FM has no impact on economic growth in Nigeria (short run).

Hypothesis IV: Deepening of finance in co-operatives has no impact on financial development in Nigeria

Table 4.2.6.

Dependent Variable: log(FD), Controls: per capita GDP growth, log of Inflation					Critical values			Reject H ₀ ?
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.	10 %	5 %	1 %	Yes, No
LOG(CSS)	-0.028	0.0435	-0.63721	0.5325	1.734	2.101	2.878	No
LOG(CSI)	0.212	0.0823	2.577849	0.0196	1.734	2.101	2.878	Yes

*** sig at 1% , ** sig at 5%, * sig. at 10%

Source: The researcher’s computation

Table 4.2.7.

Dependent Variable: log(FI), Controls: per capita GDP growth, log of Inflation					Critical values			Reject H ₀ ?
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.	10 %	5 %	1 %	Yes, No
LOG(CSS)	0.069	0.041	1.715	0.105	1.734	2.101	2.878	No

LOG(CSI)	0.176**	0.063	2.816	0.012	1.734	2.101	2.878	Yes
*** sig at 1% , ** sig at 5%, * sig. at 10%								

Source: The researcher’s computation

Table 4.2.8.

Dependent Variable: log(FM), Controls: per capita GDP growth, log of Inflation					Critical values			Reject H ₀ ?
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.	10%	5%	1%	Yes, No
LOG(CSS)	-0.123	0.083	-1.477	0.158	1.734	2.101	2.878	No
LOG(CSI)	0.243	0.150	1.618	0.124	1.734	2.101	2.878	No
*** sig at 1% , ** sig at 5%, * sig. at 10%								

Source: The researcher’s computation

Co-operative society savings have a negative effect on composite index of financial deepening and in the financial market (FM) sub-component in Nigeria but have positive impact on the sub-component of financial institution (FI). Co-operative society investments have a positive effect on financial deepening (using both the composite measure and the sub-components) in Nigeria. While the impact of co-operative society savings is not significant, co-operative society investments had a significant impact on financial deepening (measured using the financial institution sub-component).

5.0 FINDINGS

Firstly, our finding was that the composite index FD has a positive relationship with economic growth. A unit increase in FD tends to cause per capita GDP to grow by a factor of about 64 in the long run and 65 in the short run, other things being equal. However, with a probability of 0.49 and 0.67 respectively, this effect is not statistically different from zero.

Secondly, we found that deepening of financial institutions and financial markets exert significant impacts on per capita GDP growth in the short run and in the long run. However, while the effect of financial markets is positive in both the long run and short run, the effect of financial institutions is negative. A unit increase in the financial institution deepening index will, other things being equal, cause per capita GDP to contract by a factor of about 400 in the short run and a factor of about 326 in the long run. Contrarily, a unit increase in the financial market deepening index will, other things being equal, cause per capita GDP to grow by a factor of about 237 in the short run and 209 in the long run.

Thirdly, we found that co-operative society investment (CSI) has a positive and statistically significant impact on the composite index (FD) and on the financial institution index (FI). Its impact on the financial market is positive but insignificant. This indicates that the co-operatives invest more in financial institutions than in financial markets. The coefficient of determination, a measure of goodness of fit, indicates that about 85% variation in the financial institution index is explained by co-operative society savings and co-operative society investment. The co-operatives channel their members' investments through the financial institutions. A percentage increase in co-operative society investment will, other things being equal, cause the financial deepening index or its subcomponent (FI and FM) to increase by about 20 per cent. This can also be interpreted as the elasticity of financial deepening with respect to co-operative society investment. The impact of co-operative society saving (CSS) is positive on the financial institution index but negative on the composite index, FD and on the financial market index. Again, this suggests that co-operatives are more relevant in the financial institution channel. They effectively bank the unbanked but do not play as much in the financial markets. However, the effect of co-operative society savings on financial development is not statistically different from zero. We also observe that the parameter estimates are, in absolute terms, less in CSS than CSI. This suggests that co-operative societies' investment matters more than savings. The poor/unbanked may not just be interested in saving their money; they are savvy and pursue returns on investment. Further research can probe this. Overall, we rejected the null hypothesis that deepening of finance in co-operatives has no impact on financial development in Nigeria as the co-operative impact is felt through the investment channel.

6.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

We conclude that financial deepening matters for economic growth in Nigeria and that financial co-operatives (the SAACOs) matter for financial deepening. While the effect of financial deepening on growth felt via the financial market channel is positive and growth enhancing, the effect felt via the financial institutions channel is enervating. The savings and credit cooperatives

through their savings and investment activities enhance financial deepening via the financial institution channel and support the growth enhancing effect of the overall financial deepening.

Based on the findings of this study, we recommend as follows:

- a) Engender efficient financial deepening for the Nigerian economy through institutional reforms in our banking sector to ensure that the banks do not engage in unproductive financing.
- b) Leverage on the savings and credit cooperatives to deepen finance in Nigeria. This can be done by giving credit guarantees to financial institutions that advance loans to the cooperatives for on-ward lending to their members, and creating enabling environments for the co-operatives to thrive.
- c) Give more visibility to the co-operatives and the co-operative sector so as to boost their financial deepening efforts. This can be done by measuring and reporting their activities and establishing an online researchable database that will track the index of co-operative contribution to the Nigerian economy.
- d) Create an enabling environment for financial deepening. This can be done by avoiding over-regulation, putting institutions and infrastructure in place, curtaining fraud in the system and rebuilding trust in Nigerian banks and the financial system.

References

- Birchall, J. (2013). Resilience in a downturn: The power of financial cooperatives. *International Labour Office*. Geneva.
- Bourdieu, P. (1986). The forms of capital. In *Hand Book of Theory and Research for the Sociology of Education*. Ed. J G. Richardson. New York: Greenwood press.
- Coleman, J. S. (1988). Social capital in the creation of human capital. *The American Journal of Sociology* 94.
- Demirgüç-Kunt, A., Leora K., Dorothe S., & Saniya A. (2022). *The Global Findex Database 2021: Financial inclusion, digital payments, and resilience in the age of COVID-19*. The World Bank Group.
- Demirguc-Kunt, A., Leora K., Dorothe S., Saniya A., & Jake H. (2018). *Global Findex Database (Policy Research Working Paper 29510)*. The World Bank Group.

- Demircuc-Kunt, A., Leora K., Dorothe S., & Peter V. O. (2014). *The Global Findex Database: Measuring financial inclusion around the World* (Policy Research Working Paper 7255). The World Bank Group.
- Fiamohe, R., Dedehouanou, S., Araar, A., Bouraïma, N., & Djo, A. (2021). *Access to financing for productive employment opportunities for women in rural Benin* (Working Paper No. 07). Partnership for Economic Policy.
- Goldsmith, R. W. (1969). *Financial structure and development*. New Haven: Yale University Press.
- Greenwood, J. & Smith, B. (1997). Financial markets in development and the development of financial market. *Journal of Economic Dynamic and Control*, 21(1), 145-181.
- Groeneveld, H. (2016). Doing Co-operative Business Report: Methodology and exploratory application for 33 countries. *International Co-operative Alliance*.
- Hicks, J. (1969). *A Theory of economic history*. Oxford: Clarendon Press
- Itaman, R. E. (2022). The finance-growth nexus enigma: Bringing in institutional context and the productiveness debate. *Journal of Economic Surveys* 36, 504-527.
- Jhingan, M. L (2003). *The Economics of development and planning* (36th ed.) Vrinda Publications.
- Karakas, C. (2019). Cooperatives: Characteristics, activities, status, challenges. *European Parliamentary Research Service*.
- King, R. G. & Levine, R. (1993). Finance and growth: Schumpeter might be right. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*.
- Kuznets, S. (1966). *Modern Economic Growth: Rate, Structure and Spread*. Yale University Press.
- Lucas, R. E. (1988). On the mechanics of economic development. *Journal of Monetary Economics*, 12.
- Olatunde, I. (2023). (Advancing financial inclusion in Nigeria via digital financial services. *Zenith Economic Quarterly* 19(2) 26-32.

- Otto, G. & Ukpere, W. (2011). Credit and thrift co-operatives in Nigeria: A potential source of capital formation and employment. *African Journal of Business Management*, 5(14), 5675-5680
- Putnam, R. D. (1995). Bowling alone: America's declining social capital. *Journal of Democracy*, 6(1), 65-78.
- Robinson, J. (1952). The Generalization of the General Theory. In *The Rate of Interest and Other Essays*. Macmillan.
- Rousseau, P. & Wachtel, P. (2000). Equity markets and growth: Cross country evidence on timing and outcomes, 1980-1995. *Journal of Banking and Finance*, 24(12), 1933-1957.
- Sahay, R.; Čihák, M.; N'Diaye, P.; Barajas, A.; Bi, R.; Ayala, D.; Gao, Y., Kyobe, A., Nguyen, L., Saborowiski, C., Svirydzenka, K., & Yousefi, S. R. (2015). Rethinking financial deepening: Stability and growth in Emerging Markets. *IMF Staff Discussion Note*. SDN/15/08.
- Schumpeter, J. A (1934). *The theory of economic development: An inquiry into profits, capital, credit, interest, and the business cycle*. Harvard University Press.
- Schumpeter, J.A. (1911). *Theory of economic development*. Harvard University Press.
- Sen, A. (1983). Development: Which way now? *Economic Journal*, 93(372), 745-62. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2232744>.
- Stem, N. H. (1989). The economics of development: A survey. *Economic Journal*, 99(397), 597-685.
- Terra, F. H., Filho, F., & Fonseca, P., C. (2021). Keynes on state and economic development. *Review of Political Economy* 33(1), 88-102. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09538259.2020.1823072>.
- Wijnbergen, S. (1983). Credit policy, inflation and growth in a financially repressed economy. *Journal of Development Economics*, 13(1), 45-65.

Employee Soft Skills and Competitiveness of Commercial Banks in Rivers State

ONUNWOR, ALLWELL AZUBUIKE Ph.D

*Department of Management,
Faculty of Management Sciences,
Ignatius Ajuru University of Education
allwell.onunwor@iaue.edu.ng*

Abstract

Research Purpose: In the rapidly evolving banking sector, this study explores the relationship between employee soft skills and the competitiveness of commercial banks in Rivers State. Understanding this relationship is crucial for banks aiming to enhance their strategic planning and adapt to new technologies.

Methodology: The study utilised an exploratory survey research design, focusing on 17 commercial banks in Rivers State. Data was analysed using mean, standard deviation, and Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient to assess the reliability and relationships between variables.

Findings: The analysis revealed significant relationships: critical thinking correlates with new technology adoption, communication skills enhance workforce experience, and social intelligence improves strategic planning in commercial banks.

Conclusion: Employee soft skills, including critical thinking, communication, and social intelligence, are essential for improving the competitiveness of commercial banks. These skills enable quick adaptation to technological advancements and effective strategic planning.

Recommendations: Banks should regularly organise soft skills training, particularly in critical thinking, to enhance competitiveness. Emphasising these skills will facilitate swift adaptation to new technologies and strengthen strategic planning capabilities.

Keywords: *Employee soft skills, Commercial banks, Competitiveness, Critical thinking, Strategic planning.*

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Background to the Study

A business environment adorned with healthy competition grows at a pace faster than anticipated. Thus, it becomes pertinent to find organisations competing healthily amongst themselves. According to Wilfred *et al.* (2014), competitiveness refers to its ability to create more economic value than other competing firms. On the other hand, enterprise competitiveness refers to its ability to design (Yosuke & Shibata, 2013), produce and/or market products superior to those offered by competitors, considering the price and non-price

product qualities (Sadegh *et al*, 2015). Operationally, competitiveness is the ability of an organisation to design, produce and/or market products superior to those offered by competitors, considering the price and non-price qualities. Organisational competitiveness happens through the instrumentality of competitive processes, which are those processes which help identify the importance and current performance of core processes such as strategic management processes, human resources processes, operations management processes and technology management processes. However, organisations such as Commercial Banks that are termed to be competing favourably tend to perform outstandingly in areas such as new technology, experienced workforce and strategic planning, amongst others.

In the concept of this work, new technology is defined as any set of productive techniques which offers a significant improvement over an existing technology that has been invoked for a long time. New technology refers to any invention, discovery, improvement, or innovation, that was not available to the acquiring agency on the effective date of the contract, whether or not patentable, including, but not limited to, new processes, emerging technology, machines, and improvements to, or new applications of, existing processes, machines, manufactures and software (Salvador, 2020). Lau (2021) posited that in getting employees to speedily adopt new technology, organisations can communicate the benefits, provide adequate training, use guided learning, and ask employees for input. Experienced workforce refers to a segment of the workforce that has specialised know-how, training, and skill to carry out more complex, physical, or mental tasks than routine job functions (Hayes, 2021). As defined by the researcher, experienced workforce refers to a set of employees who possess certain skills usually attained through training and experience. The type of training varies and a skilled worker does not have to be highly educated or possess much job experience. On the last measure of competitiveness in this work (strategic planning), this study defines it as the process of determining a company's long term goals and then identifying the best approach for achieving those goals. In the View of Darbi (2012), strategic planning is a process through which managers formulate and implement strategies geared to optimising strategic goal achievement, given available environmental and internal conditions.

Studies and experience have shown that improving the skills of employees through various viable mechanisms gives diverse firm-oriented results such as organisational productivity, organisational performance, organisational resilience, etc. This implies that if management of Commercial Banks in Port Harcourt can engage their employees in soft skills such as critical thinking, communication and social intelligence, they are likely going to improve on competitiveness, amongst other variables. Operationally, this study adopts the definition of Aldulaimi (2018) to define soft skills as an individual's personal qualities, habits, attitudes, and social courtesy that enable an employee to be good and compatible with fellowship. The fellowship here in the definition depicts teamwork. Soft skills are required in interpersonal relationships and in work environments and are essential for the success of organisations

(AbuJbara *et al.*, 2018). The soft skills acquired by an employee are most times not gotten through any formal education, and can be applied in diverse areas of life. The assertion of Weber *et al.* (2011) supported this, as they stated that soft skills are interpersonal and behavioural skills which are not specific to any job function and are usually not acquired through formal education.

Statement of Problem

There appears to be a decline in the way banks (especially commercial banks) are competing amongst themselves. Obviously, the absence of vibrant and healthy competition in an economy through the various sectors will only give rise to diverse negative outcomes. This makes it important for organisations, both locally and internationally to engage in activities that stir up healthy competition for productivity and growth. The organisation is said to be competitive over its rivals, if they are dynamic, able to respond to any changes with versatility, flexible (Houshang & Babakhanian, 2015), innovative and able to create economic value than its competitors (Wilfred *et al.*, 2014). Researcher's experience and observation suggest that Commercial Banks in Rivers State do not care so much about trending technologies that are creating better experiences in the workplace, as lots of them are littered with poorly performing ATM machines, Apps, and other machines, especially those they use indoors. Expertise is not also commonly found amongst employees like sometime in the past. Both the banks and their workplace seem not to care much about this appalling situation. This present condition could be as a result of the fact that Commercial Banks in this region have for a long time not considered equipping their employees with all necessary soft skills.

Another issue that has triggered this study is the seeming dearth of empirical studies bothering on the relationship between employee soft skills and competitiveness. To buttress this, Awawdeh and Alkshali (2022) investigated the impact of soft skills on organisational innovation in Levant Food Products Company (AlDurra). Taiye and Edwinah (2021) investigated the relationship between workforce diversity and organisational competitiveness of SMEs in Rivers state, Nigeria and revealed that the dimensions of workforce diversity (professional diversity and age diversity) is significantly and positively correlated with the measures of organisational competitiveness (product differentiation and innovativeness). In another study, Abdallah, (2020) investigated the relationship between soft skills and organisational creativity at the company Telecom Egypt in regions of Suez, South Sinai, and the Red Sea. Similarly, Falola *et al.* (2018) *examined* the effectiveness of training and development on employees' performance and organisation competitive advantage in the Nigerian banking industry.

However, none of the above studies was bent on finding the relationship between employee soft skills and competitiveness of Commercial Banks in Rivers State. This implies that this aspect of research effort is seriously begging for consideration. There is therefore a need to find empirical evidence on how the dimensions of employee soft skills such as critical thinking, communication and social intelligence interact with competitiveness measuring on

new technology, experienced workforce and strategic planning of Commercial Banks in Rivers State. This is the knowledge gap that needs to be closed.

Objectives of the Study

The aim of the study was to determine the relationship between employee soft skills and competitiveness of Commercial Banks in Rivers State. The objectives of the study included to:

- i. determine the extent to which critical thinking correlates with new technology in Commercial Banks in Rivers State.
- ii. determine the extent to which communication correlates with experienced workforce in Commercial Banks in Rivers State.
- iii. investigate the extent to which social intelligence correlates with strategic planning in Commercial Banks in Rivers State.

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated for further verification in the course of the study:

H₀₁: Critical thinking does not have any relationship with new technology in Commercial Banks in Rivers State.

H₀₂: Communication does not have any relationship with experienced workforce in Commercial Banks in Rivers State.

H₀₃: Social intelligence does not have any relationship with strategic planning in Commercial Banks in Rivers State.

2.0 REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Conceptual Review

Concept of Employee Soft Skills

Soft skills and employee soft skills have been defined and explained by diverse authorities. However, it is necessary to first of all understand what soft skills imply before going into divulging what employee soft skills imply. Soft skills refer to a set of characteristics and skills possessed by the official, such as the skill of working with a team, creative thinking, time management ability, and communication skill (Al-Jaraydah & Al-Aloui, 2018). Gregory (2015) defined soft skills as the experience enjoyed by human resources as a result of their participation in training and development programs, and it is the second component of human capital, which plays an important role in dealing with the changes and developments that the organisation faces at work. Reddy (2013) sees that life skills and the skills necessary to get a job, are those aspects related to tact in speaking, good and distinguished appearance, and possession of the special qualities that distinguish the job seeker among his peers. Gibb (2014) stated that soft skills improve the quality of human capital and thus enhance the

productivity of the individual, developing the effects of soft skills facilitates performance, increases mastery experience, and engages people in work-related behaviours. Soft skills are the personality traits, behaviour and attitudes that increase professionals' interactions, career prospects and job performances. According to Robles (2012), the best feature of soft skills is that the use of these skills is not limited to a specific profession. Soft skills are personal and broadly applicable.

Soft skills are required for information professionals in their daily work, dealing with clients and colleagues effectively (Junrat *et al.*, 2014). Information specialists in large organisations develop these skills to some extent through practical experience. Soft skills are an individual's personal qualities, habits, attitudes, and social courtesy that enable an employee to be good and compatible with fellowship (Aldulaimi, 2018). Abdullah (2013) sees it as a set of personal characteristics related to the field of communication with others in a comfortable work environment in which the individual can deal with cooperation and love, and the ability to express oneself, in addition to the skills of brainstorming in smooth and attractive ways. Soft skills are a term related to personality, positive traits and competencies that enhance a person's relationships, job performance, and give market value. Skills include one's ability to listen well, communicate effectively, have a positive approach, deal with conflict, take responsibility, and show respect. Building trust, working well with others, managing time effectively, accepting criticism, working under pressure, being kind to others and showing good character (Vijayalalshmi, 2016).

Having unravelled what is implied by soft skills, now unto employee soft skills. As defined by Nathan (2022), employee soft skills are qualities that enable a worker to work both independently and as part of a team, blending unique personalities and working styles to find the best possible outcomes and solutions. Unlike hard skills, which refer to specific technical competencies, soft skills cannot be definitively measured and instead are exemplified through attitude, behaviour, self-expression, and motivation. Although not quantifiable, soft skills are an essential resource that can vastly increase efficiency, team-building, and innovation in the workplace.

Dimensions of Employee Soft Skills Critical Thinking

Critical thinking has been defined in many ways by many researchers working on the subject and has continued to develop by adding different perspectives and information from various fields such as psychology and philosophy since its first introduction (Turan *et al.*, 2019). Many researchers agree that the first definitions of critical thinking were made by John Dewey (Alkhatib, 2019; Ennis, 2018; Hitchcock, 2017; Fisher, 2011). In his work, Dewey called critical thinking as reflective thinking and described it as an active, persistent and careful evaluation of any belief or supposed form of knowledge in the light of the grounds that support it and the further conclusions to which it tends. (Dewey, 1910).

Commonly referred to as 'troubleshooting,' critical thinking refers to discerning, anticipating, and resolving problems (Nathan, 2022). Critical thinking shows employers that employees take the initiative to resolve problems rather than waiting for colleagues to come up with a solution. Since being an effective problem-solver boosts efficiency in the workplace, hiring managers often screen candidates for an ability to balance independent and collaborative work.

To be strong critical thinkers, employees need level-headedness and determination. Critical thinkers are often effective decision-makers, as they can prioritise tasks, evaluate complex situations, and weigh potential outcomes to proposed solutions. Since addressing problems or conflict can lead to unexpected situations, and new challenges can arise even as former ones are resolved, hiring managers can look for consistent problem-solving as a sign of well-developed critical thinking skills.

Moore saw critical thinking as part of effective thinking and decision-making and also stated that ideas and possibilities created by creative thinking should be tested and evaluated by critical thinking (Moore, 1967). Critical thinking is the ability and disposition to engage in reflective scepticism. Royalty stated that the acceptability of this definition stems from the distinction between having critical thinking skills and being able to apply them (Royalty, 2016). However, Matthews and Lally argued that critical thinking is not a phenomenon on its own and cannot be taught as an independent subject. According to them, critical thinking is a concept specific to a field or subject (Matthews & Lally, 2010).

Facione (2012) listed the characteristics of the critical thinking individual in his report of the American Philosophical Society's study of critical thinking as: i) inquisitive; ii) well-informed; iii) trustful of reason; iv) open-minded; v) flexible; vi) fair-minded in evaluation; vii) honest in facing personal biases; viii) willing to reconsider. Paul and Elder stated that a well-educated critical thinker would be able to formulate clearly and accurately by raising important questions and problems, collect and evaluating the necessary information and use abstract ideas to interpret them effectively, reach well thought-out results and solutions by examining them according to relevant criteria and standards and communicate effectively with other people to find solutions to complex problems (Paul & Elder, 2013).

Communication

Communication here actually refers to communication skill as required by an employee. Successful collaboration is strongly related to good communication skills. Communication skills include actively listening to colleagues and willing engagement in conflict resolution to mitigate the effects of miscommunications as well as keeping projects and organisational initiatives on track (Henry, 2019).

Communication is a way to accomplish the work of the organisation, and that communication must include conveying and understanding meanings and any idea whatever the skill of

listening, understanding and speaking clearly so that the speaker's ideas are communicated correctly (Awawdeh *et al.*, 2022). Active communication is one of the most important soft skills of leaders, which includes active listening and feedback (Levaseur, 2013). Communication skills include oral skills, in addition to written skills. Cole (2017) asserts that a leader who fails to communicate with employees will reflect on their trust and loyalty, which leads to poor performance. Shahid and Asiabinti (2011) identify a set of skills such as speaking, writing, listening and responding as types of communication skills.

The issue of communication is necessary for productive exchange between individuals, departments, and companies, particularly when sharing new ideas, inherent in thinking and responding to concerns, and listening to feedback (Nathan, 2022). Without clear communication, workplaces cannot operate effectively, since the added confusion caused by misinformation or misunderstanding often prolongs tasks unnecessarily and strains professional relationships. Especially since remote collaboration has become increasingly common, employees with strong communication skills are more highly valued than ever in the workplace.

While there are several types of communication, communication skills can be broadly categorised as either written or verbal. Well-versed in online correspondence, employees with strong written communication skills understand how to craft formal emails and follow proper messaging etiquette on professional platforms like Slack, Asana, or Microsoft Teams. On the other hand, verbal communication includes meetings, presentations, and networking. It's important to note that, whether you work domestically or internationally, coworkers and clientele may speak a variety of languages, and putting a little effort into learning the language of your collaborators can go a long way in strengthening professional relationships.

Communication is important at all levels of the organisation (Ramsoomair *et al.*, 2014). The ability to communicate effectively, both verbally and non-verbally is crucial for effective leadership (DuBrin, 2013). Poor communication skills can lead to misunderstanding and conflicts. This skill helps individuals know when, how and what to communicate. Through good communication skills, managers can create an environment within his or her team that encourages creativity and innovation.

Social Intelligence

Social intelligence refers to how aware people are of their interactions with others (Gabriel, 2021). In the workplace, well-honed social intelligence helps individuals avoid conflict, manage expectations and communicate effectively. Improving your social intelligence skills can contribute to a positive and productive work environment. Social intelligence is the ability to connect effectively with other individuals. This kind of intelligence means you are aware of others' thoughts and feelings even if they may not explicitly describe them to you. Some important traits that you might recognize in socially intelligent people include effective listening and communication, consideration for the impression they make on others and

conscious efforts to avoid arguing. According to Thompson (2021), the following are the constituents of social intelligence:

- i. Self-awareness: Self-awareness is the ability to understand one's own abilities, thoughts and feelings. Being mindful of who you are and how you respond to things are examples of self-awareness.
- i. Self-management: Self-management is one step beyond self-awareness, as it refers to how you apply your self-awareness to address any challenging situations. You might think of self-management as your internal decision-making process.
- ii. Social awareness: Social awareness is how you recognize social cues, body language and subtext when communicating with others.
- iii. Relationship management: Relationship management is how you apply your social awareness. This can include avoiding confrontation, developing empathy, understanding how your motivation might differ from others' and identifying the role you play in your social network.

In the operations of this study, social intelligence refers to a person's ability to get along with others and understand them in a way that it becomes easy to- work almost seamlessly with them. In the words of Manasi (2019), social intelligence considers both situational awareness and meaningful interaction. A socially intelligent person is able to work well with others and understand the dynamics within a group. Also, they are able to take into consideration how circumstances and environmental factors impact on people at an individual and team level. Social intelligence comprises multiple communication-based skills, including:

- i. Verbal and nonverbal fluency: The use of verbal conversation and body language are the primary forms of social intelligence. These help other people understand your intentions.
- ii. Knowledge of social rules: Social rules are the basic understanding of interactions in a group based on social status. Understanding social rules can lead to more positive interactions by considering the age, experience and position of your peers.
- iii. Active listening: Listening to your peers may allow you to connect with them more easily by learning about their perspectives. It may facilitate better conflict resolution by helping you understand a peer's emotions, allowing you to take that information and create a positive outcome.

Understanding emotions: Having strong social intelligence can allow you to better empathise with team members. Empathy can lead to communication that takes people's attributes and sensibilities into consideration, which makes your conversations more authentic.

Concept of Competitiveness

The concept of competitiveness in literature has been described as a multidimensional and relative concept (Boonthawan, 2012), that changes with context and time. It embraces

different approaches, from classical theories of mercantilism, which introduced the notion of trade rivalry between nations, to absolute advantages of notions, the theories of competitive and comparative advantages and up to neoclassical critiques of international competitiveness of countries (Razvan & Moisoiu, 2015). It constitutes a major economic objective in the current context of globalisation, rapid technical change and frequently invoked by policy makers worldwide (Salvador *et al.*, 2015). The competitiveness defines economic strength of an entity with respect to its competitor and it has the country, industrial and enterprise perspectives (Sadegh *et al.*, 2015). There is no agreed definition of national competitiveness (Chiang *et al.*, 2017). However, the WEF, 2013 refers to national competitiveness as a set of institutions, policies and factors that determines the level of productivity of a country (Schwab, 2013). Chiang *et al.* (2017) defined national competitiveness as a measure of relative ability of a nation to create and maintain an environment in which enterprises can compete so that the level of prosperity can be improved.

According to Wilfred *et al.* (2014), competitiveness refers to its ability to create more economic value than other competing firms. On the other hand, enterprise competitiveness refers to its ability to design (Yosuke & Shibata, 2013), produce and/or market products superior to those offered by competitors, considering the price and non-price product qualities (Sadegh *et al.*, 2015). Organisational competitiveness refers to continuous presence in markets, profit making and the ability to adapt production to demand (Diaz-chao *et al.*, 2013). The organisation is said to be competitive over its rivals, if they are dynamic, able to respond to any changes with versatility, flexible (Houshang & Babakhanian, 2015), innovative and able to create economic value than its competitors (Wilfred *et al.*, 2014). The organisation that seeks to build competitive advantage has to well manage its core processes and resources -human, operations, technology and financial (Sadegh *et al.*, 2015) and strive for low cost leadership. The competitiveness measurement remains paramount. The 12 pillars covering basic requirements, efficiency enhancers, innovation and sophistication are global competitiveness indices have been used to measure competitiveness among factor driven, efficiency and innovation driven economies respectively (Schwab, 2013). The policy makers, academia and business leaders focus on microeconomic and macroeconomic factors as key indicators of competitiveness (Salvador *et al.*, 2015).

The industrial competitiveness is assessed based on a number of indicators, mainly total productivity, Innovation, market share, profitability (Chiang *et al.*, 2017), finance and investments, ability to export, business environment and entrepreneurship, public administration and sustainability (Razvan & Moisoiu, 2015), product quality, price, growth rate, and the enterprises' cost leadership ability and overall ability to turn input into output in the most efficient and economic way (Wilfred *et al.*, 2014).

Competitiveness is the capability of a profit or non-profit organisation to produce goods and services that are of higher quality and perhaps quantity than those of its rivals in the regional, national, or global level (D'Cruz, 2017). Organisations feel a great sense of belonging when

they compete favourably at whatever level that satisfies them for now. The reason is because factors such as market share, net profit, and brand reputation amongst others, are taken into consideration before an organisation is termed to be competing favourably. An organisation that is on the same level or has a higher market share, net profit, brand reputation than its counterparts within a time period and a geographical entity is said to be a favourable competitor (Smith, 2017).

Measures of Competitiveness

New Technology

Obviously, digital transformation is here to stay; remote and hybrid working is now the norm. This has accelerated the growth of collaborative technologies like cloud computing, AI, and augmented reality (AR). New technology can improve all aspects of a business' operations, from scaling the business to increasing employee efficiency (Lau, 2021). But in 2020, only around 50% of businesses were adopting emerging technologies like cloud computing and SaaS marketing platforms, according to Statista. And fewer than 30% were adopting other emerging technologies. One reason for this could be worker resistance. There are many reasons workers resist new technology, including:

- i. Resenting perceived interference from management.
- ii. Lack of confidence around technology.
- iii. Failing to see a use for it.
- iv. Feeling excluded from the decision-making process.
- V. Feeling threatened and unappreciated.
- vi. Lack of communication from management.
- vii. Failing to see the benefits. ¹

Defeating employee resistance to getting new tech into the workplace can seem impossible. However, with the right strategies, organisations can help their employees not only adapt to new technology but also thrive with it, as this will also help the business to thrive. Notwithstanding, Lau (2021) outlines eight strategies organisations can use to get their employees to speedily adopt new technology. They include:

- i. Communicate the benefits; Transparency is vital when bringing in tech that affects how employees do their job, even if that tech will help them. Open dialog is the best way to promote transparency and ease the transition from old to new. Consider hosting a video meeting to communicate the benefits of the new technology and encourage questions and feedback so you can deal with any issues that may arise. After the meeting, provide a place where employees can continue to ask questions and where you can provide updates. Create a group on the instant

messaging software you use in-house and send regular email updates to keep employees in the loop,

- ii. Provide adequate training: Marketers should nurture leads; employers should nurture employees. Yet there's a big difference between what employers see as adequate training and what employees think. According to an IBM and Josh Bersin study, 74% of employers think they are helping employees learn new skills, while just 38% of employees agree. But companies that outperform their rivals make skills growth a key part of performance management. So, providing adequate training not only helps your employees but also helps you.

Use guided learning: Do not sit employees down and talk to them for two hours. Hold workshops that combine training with doing. For example, instructors could give employees bite-sized chunks of information. Then employees could try it out for themselves

Strategic Planning

Strategic planning means planning for strategies and implementing them to achieve organisational goals (Thompson et al., 2010). It starts by asking oneself simple questions like "What are we doing?" Should we continue to do it or change our product line or the way of working? What is the impact of social, political, technological and other environmental factors on our operations? Are we prepared to accept these changes etc.?

Strategic planning helps in knowing what we are and where we want to go so that environmental threats and opportunities can be exploited, given the strengths and weaknesses of the organisation. Strategic planning is "a thorough self-examination regarding the goals and means of their accomplishment so that the enterprise is given both direction and cohesion."

In the view of Darbi (2012), strategic planning is a process through which managers formulate and implement strategies geared to optimising strategic goal achievement, given available environmental and internal conditions. Strategic planning is formalisation of planning where plans are made for long periods of time for effective and efficient attainment of organisational goals. Strategic planning is based on extensive environmental scanning. It is a projection into environmental threats and opportunities and an effort to match them with the organisation's strengths and weaknesses.

Planning is something we do in advance of taking action; that is, it is anticipatory decision making. It is a process of deciding what to do and how to do it before action is required. Strategic planning can be defined as a managerial process of developing and maintaining a viable fit between an organisation's objectives, skills and resources and its changing environment (Calderpride.org., 2012). The company's strategic plan is the starting point for planning. It serves as a guide to the development of sound sub-plans to accomplish the organisational objectives. The aim of strategic planning is to help a company select and organise its businesses in a way that would keep the company healthy in spite of unexpected

changes in the environment. It purports to shape or reshape the company's businesses and products so that they yield target profits and growth.

This study defines strategic planning as the process of determining a company's long-term goals and then identifying the best approach for achieving those goals. Strategic planning is an organisation's process of defining its strategy or direction and making decisions on allocating its resources to pursue this strategy, including its capital and people (Padala & Suryanarayana, 2010). Strategic planning is a process to determine or re-assess the vision, mission and goals of an organisation and then map out objective (measurable) ways to accomplish the identified goals. One of the functions of strategic planning is to inspire people in the organisation to work towards the creation of a new state of affairs. The vision is a means of describing this desired future, but it works best to inspire and motivate if it is vivid — in other words, a vision should be a "picture" of the future. The visioning process is usually the very first step in the strategic planning process.

Theoretical Framework

This work is anchored on Diffusion of Innovation Theory by Roger in 1962.

Diffusion of Innovation Theory

Diffusion of Innovation Theory was propounded to explain how people accept new technologies and innovative skills set as cited in Amadi-George (2018). The theory assumes that:

- i. In a social system, there will always be a disparity in the level and time at which individuals within a given social system adopt new ideas, techniques, and technology.
- ii. Individuals and arms of institutions that adopt innovations early will naturally out-perform late adopters and the laggards (Rogers cited in Amadi-George, 2018).

The implication of this theory is that as some Commercial Banks find the need to equip their employees with soft skills such as critical thinking, communication and social intelligence, there will obviously be a discrepancy on the mode of adoption - some will quickly adopt while others will be reluctant about it. The reluctant ones want to first of all see how it benefits the early adopters before they make the decision whether to toll the same line or not. The fact is that management of Commercial Banks that fail to provide their employees with these soft skills early enough are likely going to experience untold difficulties, slow operations, high level inefficiency, and negative stress arising majorly from guests' complaints (Odu, 2018) while those who embrace and adopt these enhancement techniques on time enjoy speed, efficiency and high level effectiveness. This means that there will be a significant gap in the competitiveness of early and late adopters.

Empirical Review

Awawdeh and Alkshali (2022) investigated the impact of soft skills on organisational innovation in Levant Food Products Company (AlDurra). The study was conducted on a sample of 106 employees of this company. The necessary data were collected from them

through a questionnaire developed for this purpose. The study used the quantitative descriptive method. The study relied on five dimensions to measure soft skills (the independent variable), which are: communication, time management, leadership, teamwork and decision-making. With regard to organisational innovation (the dependent variable), it was measured through four dimensions: introduction of new products, improving existing product, innovating new process and improving existing processes. The study used a set of statistical methods, the most important of which is the multiple linear regression. The study concluded that there are high levels of the dimensions of both variables, and that there is a significant impact of soft skills on organisational innovation, and the most influential dimensions of soft skills on organisational innovation are: leadership, decision making and teamwork.

Taiye & Edwinah (2021) investigated the relationship between workforce diversity and organisational competitiveness of SMEs in Rivers state, Nigeria. The cross sectional survey was carried out in the study. A total of eight hundred and forty- seven (847) managers and supervisors of SMEs served as the population of the study. However, a sample of two hundred and sixty-five respondents was drawn from the population. The systematic sampling technique was used in the study in order to avoid bias in selection of the sample cases. Questionnaires were used in collecting data from respondents and the copies of the questionnaire were personally administered to the respondents. The retrieved data was analysed using spearman rank order correlation coefficient. The outcome of the analysis revealed that the dimensions of workforce diversity (professional diversity and age diversity) is significantly and positively correlated with the measures of organisational competitiveness (product differentiation and innovativeness). It was thus concluded that workforce diversity is thus essential in enhancing the competitiveness of SMEs which could thus help boost the organisation's position in the industry. Therefore, the study recommended that the owners and managers of the small and medium enterprises should ensure that employees of diverse professions are employed in the organisation in order to enhance the competitiveness of the organisation.

Abdallah, (2020) investigated the relationship between soft skills and organisational creativity at the company Telecom Egypt in regions of Suez, South Sinai, and the Red Sea. To achieve research objectives, three basic hypotheses were formulated, and tested using primary data collected through the questionnaire, consisting of 251 questionnaires. Structural equation modelling and path analysis were performed to analyse the survey data and to test study hypotheses. The study found a strong positive relationship and significant effect of the soft skills dimensions of (communication, working in a team, individual innovation; self management, critical thinking, problem-solving on organisational creativity, and the relative importance of the soft skills dimensions varies in their impact on organisational creativity, ranking as follow: critical thinking, self-management, problem -solving, communication, working in a team, individual innovation.

Falola *et al.* (2018) examined the effectiveness of training and development on employees' performance and organisation competitive advantage in the Nigerian banking industry. Descriptive research method was adopted for this study using two hundred and twenty three valid questionnaires which were completed by selected banks in Lagos State, South-West Nigeria using simple random sampling technique. The data collected were carefully analysed using descriptive statistics to represent the raw data in a meaningful manner. The results show that a strong relationship exists between training and development, employees' performance and competitive advantage. Summary of the findings indicates that there is a strong relationship between the tested dependent variable and independent construct. However, bank management should not relent in their quest to train their staff to develop new ideas that will keep improving and retaining employee performance.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The research design employed in the study was the exploratory survey research design. This research design was deemed suitable and most appropriate for the study because of reasons such as: (i) the study was conducted in the Commercial Banks at the same time; (ii) it involved the test of hypotheses which is exploratory in nature.

Research Population

The population of the study consisted of twenty-two (22) Commercial Banks operating in Rivers State, Nigeria. Arranged alphabetically, the twenty-two (22) Commercial Banks currently operating in Rivers State, Nigeria are listed overleaf:

Population Table

S/N Commercial Banks and their Head Offices in Rivers State.

1. Access Bank. No. 329A Olu Obasanja, Port Harcourt
8. CitiBank. No. 1 Trans- Amadi, Port Harcourt.
2. Eco Bank. No. 329A Olu Obasanja, Port Harcourt
5. Fidelity Bank. No. 22/24 Old Aba Road, Port Harcourt.
3. First Bank. No. 22/24 Old Aba Road, Port Harcourt.
4. First City Monument Bank. No. 22/24 Old Aba Road, Port Harcourt.
18. Globus Bank. Plot 467 Trans-Amadi, Industrial Layout, Port Harcourt.
6. Guaranty Trust Bank. No. 22/24 Old Aba Road, Port Harcourt.
7. Heritage Bank. No. 22/23 Old Aba Road, Artillery, Port Harcourt.
17. Jaiz Bank. No. 186 Aba Road, Port Harcourt.
9. Keystone Bank. No. 51. Aba Road Port Harcourt.

10. Polaris Bank. Agip Junction /Ikwerre Road, Port Harcourt.
11. Stanbic IBTC No. 58 Olu Obasanjo Road, Port Harcourt
16. Standard Chartered Bank. Plot 7 Trans-Amadi, Industrial Layout, Port Harcourt.

12. Sterling Bank. No. 142 Woji Road, GRA 2, Port Harcourt
20. Suntrust Bank. No. 16 Trans-Amadi, Nkpogu, Port Harcourt. , '
21. Titan Trust Bank. No. 5 Olu Obasanjo Road, Port Harcourt.
15. Union Bank Plot 468, Trans-Amadi, Port Harcourt.
13. United Bank for Africa No. 14B Azikiwe Road, Port Harcourt.
14. Unity Bank No. 28A Aba Road, Port Harcourt
19. Wema Bank. No. 66 Olu Obasanjo Way, Port Harcourt.
22. Zenith Bank. No. 40 Aba Road, Port Harcourt.

Source: CBN, 2023.

Instrumentation and Measurement

Structured questionnaire was used as the main instrument for the collection of primary data. The instrument was titled "Employee Soft Skills and Competitiveness Questionnaire Index (ESSCQI). The design of the questionnaire was a four (4) point rating scale format with the following response options: Very Great Extent (4), Great Extent (3), Moderate Extent (2), and Low Extent (1).

Validity of Instrument

To establish the validity of the instrument, copies of the questionnaire were submitted to the project supervisor and two other experts in the Management Department. Their comments and adjustments were used to validate the final copy of the instrument that was administered.

Reliability of Instrument

Test-retest method was used to ascertain the reliability of the instrument. This involved distributing the questionnaire twice to 30 managers in the Selected Commercial Banks in Rivers State. The two sets of scores obtained were correlated using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (r) which yielded a correlation coefficient of 0.75. This indicates an acceptable level of reliability, the researcher was able to retrieve 60 copies of the distributed questionnaires.

Method of Data Analysis

Mean and standard deviation were used to analyse the research questions while the test of hypotheses was done using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient. The formula is stated below:

$$\gamma = \frac{n\sum xy - \sum x \sum y}{\sqrt{[n\sum X^2 - (\sum X)^2] [n\sum Y^2 - (\sum Y)^2]}}$$

Where;

n = number of pairs of data

x = independent variable

y = dependent variable

$\sum xy$ = sum of the products of independent and dependent variable

$\sum x$ = sum of independent variable

$\sum y$ = sum of dependent variable

Σ = Summation

Test of Hypotheses

Ho1. Critical thinking does not have any relationship with new technology in Commercial Banks in Rivers State.

Table 1: Relationship between Critical Thinking and New Technology

S/N	X	Y	XY	X ²	Y ²
1.	13	12	156	169	144
2.	9	9	81	81	81
3.	5	6	30	25	36
4.	3	3	9	9	9
5.	12	12	144	144	144
6.	9	8	72	81	64
7.	6	6	36	36	36
8.	3	4	12	9	16
9.	11	12	132	121	144
10.	9	9	81	81	81
11.	6	7	42	36	49
12.	3	3	9	9	9

EMPLOYEE SOFT SKILLS AND COMPETITIVENESS OF COMMERCIAL BANKS IN RIVERS STATE

13.	11	12	132	121	144
14.	8	8	64	64	64
15.	7	6	42	49	36
16.	4		16	16	16
	$\Sigma x =$				
	119	$\Sigma y = 121$	$\Sigma XY = 1058$	$\Sigma X^2 = 1051$	$\Sigma Y^2 = 1073$

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

$$r = \frac{n \sum xy - \sum x \sum y}{\sqrt{[n \sum X^2 - (\sum X)^2] [n \sum Y^2 - (\sum Y)^2]}} = \frac{16 \times 1058 - 119 \times 121}{(16 \times 1051 - 119^2)(16 \times 1073 - 121^2)}$$

$$r = \frac{16928 - 14399}{\sqrt{(16816 - 14161)(17168 - 14641)}} = \frac{2529}{\sqrt{(2655)(2527)}}$$

$$\frac{2529}{\sqrt{709185}} = \frac{2529}{\sqrt{2590.2094}}$$

$\therefore Y = 0.976$ (approx.)

Table 4.5 above shows r value of 0.976, Since the calculated r value of 0.976 is greater than the critical r value of 0.441, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that there is a significant relationship between critical thinking and new technology of Commercial Banks in Rivers State.

H0₂: Communication does not have any relationship with experienced workforce in Commercial Banks in Rivers State.

Table 2: Relationship between Communication and Experienced Workforce

S/N	X	Y	XY	X ²	Y ²
1.	12	13	156	144	169
2.	9	8	72	81	64
3.	6	6	36	36	36
4.	3	3	9	9	9

EMPLOYEE SOFT SKILLS AND COMPETITIVENESS OF COMMERCIAL BANKS IN RIVERS STATE

5.	13	13	169	169	169
6.	8	8	68	64	64
7.	6	7	42	36	49
8.	2	3	6 i	4	9
9.	12	12	144	144	144
10.	9	8	72	81	64
11.	5	6	30	25	36
12.	4	4	16	16	16
13.	13	13	169	169	169
14.	7	8	56	49	64
15.	6	6	36	36	36
16.	3	4	12	9	16
		$\Sigma Y =$	$\Sigma XY =$	$\Sigma X^2 =$	
	$\Sigma X = 117$	122	1093	1072	$\Sigma XY^2 = 1114$

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

$$r = \frac{n \Sigma xy - \Sigma x \Sigma y}{\sqrt{[n \Sigma X^2 - (\Sigma X)^2] [n \Sigma Y^2 - (\Sigma Y)^2]}} = \frac{16 \times 1093 - 118 \times 122}{\sqrt{(16 \times 1072 - 118^2)(16 \times 1114 - 22^2)}}$$

$$r = \frac{17488 - 14399}{\sqrt{(7152 - 13924)(17824 - 14882)}} = \frac{3089}{\sqrt{(3228)(2942)}}$$

$$= \frac{3089}{\sqrt{9496776}} = \frac{3089}{\sqrt{3081.684}}$$

∴ Y = 1.002 (approx.)

Table 4.6 shows r value of 1.002. Since the calculated r value of 1.002 is greater than the critical r value of 0.441, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that there is a significant relationship between communication and the experienced workforce of Commercial Banks in Rivers State.

H0₃: Social intelligence does not have any relationship with strategic planning in Commercial Banks in Rivers State.

Table 3: Relationship between Social Intelligence and Strategic Planning

S/N	X	Y	XY	X ²	Y ²
-----	---	---	----	----------------	----------------

EMPLOYEE SOFT SKILLS AND COMPETITIVENESS OF COMMERCIAL BANKS IN RIVERS STATE

1	12	12	144	144	144
2	8	9	72	64	81
3	6	6	36	36	36
4	3	4	12	9	16
5	12	13	156	144	144
6	8	8	64	64	64
7	6	5	30	36	25
8	4	4	16	16	16
9	13	13	169	169	169
10	7	8	56	49	64
11	6	7	42	36	49
12	3	3	9	9	9
13	12	13	156	144	169
14	9	8	72	81	64
15	5	6	30	25	36
16	3	4	12	9	16
ZX=				ix ² =	
117		7,Y= 123	JTXY= 1076	1035	7Y ² = 1102

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

$$\gamma = \frac{n\sum xy - \sum x \sum y}{\sqrt{[n\sum X^2 - (\sum X)^2] [n\sum Y^2 - (\sum Y)^2]}} = \frac{16 \times 1076 - 117 \times 123}{(16 \times 1035 - 117^2)(16 \times 1102 - 123^2)}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma &= \frac{17216 - 14391}{\sqrt{(6560 - 13689)(17632 - 15129)}} = \frac{2825}{\sqrt{(2871)(2503)}} \\ &= \frac{2825}{\sqrt{2871(2503)}} = \frac{2825}{\sqrt{7186113}} \end{aligned}$$

∴ Y= 1.054 (approx.)

Table 4.7 shows r value of 1.054. Since the calculated r value of 1.054 is greater than the critical r value of 0.441, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that there is a significant

relationship between social intelligence and strategic planning of Commercial Banks in Rivers State.

4.0 SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

Based on the analysis of data, the following findings were made:

1. There is a significant relationship between critical thinking and new technology of Commercial Banks in Rivers State.
2. There is a significant relationship between communication and experienced workforce of Commercial Banks in Rivers State.
3. There is a significant relationship between social intelligence and strategic planning of Commercial Banks in Rivers State'

Conclusions

The findings from the study have actually suggested that there is a need for commercial banks and other organisations to inculcate critical thinking, communication skill and social intelligence in employees, as this will not just boost their competitiveness but also performance and productivity. Training an army of workforce who are skillful in these soft skills and more will place an organisation on a fast wheel of competitiveness, both locally and globally.

Therefore, the study concludes that employee soft skills such as critical thinking, communication, and social intelligence are viable instruments through which organisations such as commercial banks and others can utilise to promote their competitive ability. It becomes duty-bound on organisations to have their employees equipped with these skills for better organisational competitiveness, amongst others.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Management should periodically organise soft skills training that will also accommodate critical thinking, in order to enhance competitiveness especially in terms of quick adaptation to new technology.
2. Employee communication skills in commercial banks should be checked properly before employment, and as well as do further training on- same matter after employment.
3. Social intelligence should be taught in commercial banks and sister organisations to help their strategic planning and other indices of competitiveness.
4. Commercial banks and sister organisations should carry out yearly training on soft skills that will help promote their competitiveness, performance and productivity.

References

- Abdallah, A. A. (2020). Soft skills and its impact on an organizational creativity-A field study. *Journal of Business and Retail Management Research (JBRMR)*, 14(3), 33-51.
- Abdullah, K. (2013). *The soft skills they are looking for*. Vision Foundation for Press and Publishing.
- AbuJbara, N. K. & Worley, J. A. (2018). Leading toward new horizons with soft skills. *On the Horizon*, 26(3), 247-259.
- Aldulaimi, S. H. (2018). Leadership soft skills in higher education institutions. *Social Science Learning Education Journal*, 3(1), 01-08 .
- Al-Jaraydah, M. S. & Al-Alawi, S. H. (2018). The degree of school principals practicing soft skills in the Wilayat of Sur in the Sultanate of Oman. *Arabic Research in Specific Education Journals*, 5(12), 255-278.
- Alkhatib, O. J. (2019). A framework for implementing higher-order thinking skills (problem-solving, critical thinking, creative thinking, and decisionmaking) in engineering & humanities. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 1279-1333.
- Awawdeh, H. Z., & Alkshali, S. J. (2022). The impact of soft skills on organizational innovation in Lavant Food Products Company (AlDurra). *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 12(1), 569 - 584.
- Boonthawan, W. (2012). Effects of Entrepreneurship, organization capability: Strategic decision making and innovation toward the competitive advantage of SMES enterprises. *Journal of Management Sustainability*, 2, 137-150.
- Calderpride.org. i (2012). *Success business strategy*.
<http://www.calderdalepride.org/why-a-strategic-plan-is-important.html>
- Chiang, K., Wu, W. Y., Hsieh, W. J., & Chen, L. H. (2017). Measuring the national competitiveness of Southeast Asian countries. *European Journal of Operations Resource*, 187, 613-628.
- Cole, M. A. (2017). Become the leader followers want to follow. *Journal of Supervision*, 60(12), 182-198.
- D'Cruz, J. & Rugman, A. (2017). *New concepts for Canadian competitiveness*. Kodak Publishing.
- Darbi, W. (2012). Mission and vision statements and their potential impact on employee behavior and attitudes: The case of a public but profit-oriented tertiary institution. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 72(5), 96.
- Dewey, J. (1910). *How we think*. D. C. Heath & CO., Publishers.
- Diaz-chao, A., Sainz-Gonzalez, J., & Torrent-Sellens, J. (2015). The competitiveness of small network-firm: A practical tool. *Journal of Business Research*, 69, 1769-1774.
- DuBrin, A. J.. (2;013). *Principles of leadership (7th ed.)*. Cengage Learning, 436-' 438.
- Ennis, R. H. (2018). Critical thinking across the curriculum: A vision. *Topoi*, 165- 184.

- Facione, P. A. (2012). Critical thinking: A statement of expert consensus for purposes of educational assessment and instruction. *Research Findings and Recommendations*. American Philosophical Association.
- Falola, H. O., Osibanjo, A. O. & Ojo, S. I. (2018). Effectiveness of training and development on employees' performance and organisation competitiveness in the Nigerian banking industry. *Bulletin of the Transilvania University of Brasov*, 7(1), 56-66.
- Fisher, A. (2011). *Critical thinking: An introduction*. Cambridge University Press.
- Gabriel, U. (2021). *How to improve social intelligence at work*. <https://www.indeed.com/career-advice/career-development/how-to-improve-social-intelligence#:~:text=In%20the%20workplace%2C%20well%2Dhone,d,positive%20and%20productive%20work%20environment>.
- Gibb, S. (2014). Soft skills assessment: Theory development and the research agenda. *International Journal of Lifelong Education*, 33(4), 455-471, doi: 10.1080/02601370.2013.867546
- Gregory, H. A. (2015). *Automating business process reengineering (3rd Ed.)*. Prentice-Hall Publishing.
- Hayes, A. (2021). *Stilled labor*; <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/s/skilled-labor.asp>
- Henry, K. P. (2019). *Soft skills in the workplace*. <https://www.peoplesco.ut.com/insights/soft-skills-in-the-workplace/>
- Hitchcock, D. (2017). *On reasoning and argument: essays in informal logic and on critical thinking*. Springer International Publishing.
- Houshang, M. & Babakhanianb, M. (2015). World conference on technology, innovation and entrepreneurship: Identification of factors affecting organizational entrepreneurship in selected Sama Technical Schools. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 195, 940-947.
- Junrat, S., Jenphop, C., Suravee, R., & Kanokorn, S. (2014). Soft skills for university library staff in Thailand. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 112, 1027-1032.
- Lau, G. (2021). *8 strategies to help employees adapt to new technology in the workplace*. <https://www.spiceworks.com/hr/future-work/guest-article/8-strategies-to-help-employees-adapt-to-new-technology-in-the-workplace/>
- Levasseur, R. E. (2013). People skills: Developing soft skills—A change management perspective. *Walden University*, 43(6), 381-399.
- Manasi, B. (2019). *The relevance of social intelligence in the workplace*. <https://indiversecompany.com/the-relevance-of-social-intelligence-in-the-workplace/>
- Matthews, R. & Lally, J. (2010). *The thinking teacher's toolkit critical thinking, thinking skills and global perspectives*. Continuum International Publishing Group.
- Moore, W. E. (1967). *Creative and critical thinking*. Houghton Mifflin Company.
- Nathan, S. (2022). *Soft skills in the workplace & why they matter*. <https://preply.com/en/blog/b2b-importance-of-soft-skills-in-workplace/>

- Padala, S. & Suryanarayana, T. (2010). *Vision, mission and objectives of business*. <http://www.articlesbase.com/business-ideas-articles/vision-mission-and-objectives-of-business-3187165.html>
- Paul, R. & Elder, L. (2013). *The miniature guide to critical thinking concepts and tools*. Foundation for Critical Thinking.
- Ramsomair, F. & Howey, R. (2004). The hard realities of soft skills. *Problems and Perspectives in Management*, 2(4), 231-239.
- Razvan, V. & Moisoiu, C. (2015). Competitiveness: | Theoretical and policy approaches. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 22, 512-521.
- Reddy, G. (2013). *Soft skills for managers*. Carolinian publishing.
- Robels, M. M. (2012). Executive perceptions of the top 10 soft skills needed in today's workplace. *Business Communication Quarterly*, 75(4), 453-465.
- Royalty, J. (2016). The generalizability of critical thinking: Paranormal beliefs versus statistical reasoning. *The Journal of Genetic Psychology*, 477-488.
- Sadegh, R., Senin, A. A., & Tourani, A. (2015). Effect of organizational factors on university-industry collaboration: A conceptual model. *International Journal of Business Management*, 4(3), 28-37.
- Salvador, D. (2020). *New technology f definition*. <https://www.lawinsider.com/dictionary/new-technology#:~:text=New%20Technology%20means%20any%20invention,or%20new%20applications%20of%2C%20existing>
- Salvador, P., Rodriguez, M. B., & Luque, M. (2015). Assessing global competitiveness under a multi-criteria perspective. *Economic Modeling*, 55- 61.
- Schwab, K. (2013). *The global competitiveness report 2013-2014*. WEF Publishers.
- Shahid, S. & Asiahbinti, M. (2011). *A Study on perceived leadership soft skills, trustworthiness and structure empowerment of deans in the three Malaysian public universities*. PhD Thesis, University Saints Malaysia.
- Smith, S. (2017). World class competitiveness. *Managing Service Quality*, 5(5),36-42.
- Taiye, I. E. & Edwinah, A. (2021). Workforce diversity and organizational competitiveness of small and medium enterprises, (SMES) in Rivers State Nigeria. *International Journal of Management Sciences*, 9(1), 28-44.
- Thompson, D., Strickland, F. A., & Gamble, H. (2010). *Creating & Executing Strategy*. In Strayer University Text Book (p. 33).
- Thompson, E, M. (2021). *Why is social intelligence important in the workplace?* <https://www.indeed.com/career-advice/career-development/social-intelligence>
- Turan, U., Fidan, Y., & Yildiran, C. (2019). Critical thinking as a qualified decision-making tool. *Journal of History Culture and Art Research*, 5(4),. 1-18. doi:<http://dx.doi.org/10.7596/taksad.v8i4.2316>

- Turner, A. (2015). Generation Z: Technology and social interest. *The Journal of Individual Psychology*, 71, 103-113. doi:10.1353/jip.2015.0021
- Vijayalalshmi, V. (2016). Soft skills-the need of the hour for professional competence: A review on interpersonal skills and skills theory. *International Journal of Applied Engineering Research*, 77(4), 2859-2864.
- Weber, M. R., Crawford, A., Rivera, D., Jr., & Finley, D. A. (2011). Using Delphi panels to assess soft skill competencies in entry level managers. *Journal of Tourism Insights*, 7(1), 98-106.
- Wilfred, N. ML, Matoke, J., Yegon, R., & Egessa, R. (2014). Moderating effect of organizational factors on the relationship between diversification strategies and competitiveness: Case of sugar firms in Kenya. *European Journal of Business Management*, 5(5), 37-44.
- Yosuke, K. & Shibata, S. (2013). Organizational factors in the product design development process. *International Journal of Business Management*, 8, 15- 26.

Artificial Intelligence and Entrepreneurship: Implications for Sustainable Venture Creation in Nigeria

Nnamdi Nnabuihe Onyenandu; Timothy Oladele Ishola; Ama Udu

*Department of Business Administration,
National Open University of Nigeria, Abuja, Nigeria.*

Abstract

Research Objective: This paper explored the impact of artificial intelligence (AI) on entrepreneurship and its implications for sustainable venture creation in Nigeria, focusing on how AI enhances the sustainability of new venture processes and outcomes.

Methodology: A qualitative research approach was adopted, drawing data from various documents, journals, and artefacts to assess the influence of AI on entrepreneurial processes.

Findings: The study revealed that advancements in AI technologies facilitated the identification and exploitation of market opportunities, significantly impacting how entrepreneurs develop, design, and scale their organisations. AI led to promising innovations, accelerated production, enhanced work processes, and improved efficiency.

Conclusion: As a key driver of the Fourth Industrial Revolution, AI has transformed entrepreneurial practices, albeit with implications for job displacement.

Recommendations: The study recommends that the Nigerian government implement a policy framework to establish AI-based entrepreneurial grants and provide low-interest loans to support existing and potential entrepreneurs utilising AI technology.

Keywords: *Artificial Intelligence, Entrepreneurship, Sustainable Venture Creation, Nigeria.*

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is a rapidly evolving technology that is transforming various sectors of business by automating tasks that previously required human intelligence (Russell & Norvig, 2016). It has led to a paradigm shift in operational methods, assuming tasks previously carried out by humans (Silver, 2016). One of the notable applications of AI in healthcare is the utilisation of machines like Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) for diagnosing disorders (Katti, Ara & Shireen, 2011). AI's presence is also evident in security and surveillance, as AI-powered Closed-Circuit Television (CCTV) cameras can detect intrusions in real-time, offering remote monitoring capabilities (Choudhury *et al.*, 2018). This is possible by adapting the CCTV camera technology to mobile phones, so that with one's mobile phone, one can be monitoring his home or office even if he is in a faraway city or state (Smith *et al.*, 2020). Choudhury *et al.* (2018) corroborated this fact by asserting that technological improvements on AI has enabled the use of machines to perform complex tasks

that require human intelligence, even in a far more efficient way. The areas of application of artificial intelligence cut across entrepreneurship, sales and marketing, customer care management, e-commerce, administration, finance, social media, surveillance, healthcare, automobile engineering, agriculture, manufacturing, to mention but a few. Because of its wide applicability, artificial intelligence can be adapted into the creation of new businesses that are yet unknown and consequently contribute to economic growth, lessen social problems, alleviate poverty and improve living standards, as it paves way for business innovations (Amabile (2019). Cockburn *et al.* (2018) asserted that AI brings fundamental innovations to the tools that help us to innovate.

Seeing that AI application covers a wide spectrum of human activities, this paper explores extant literature to identify how AI can be used to create new and sustainable ventures. The paper synthesises leading theoretical underpinnings that link artificial intelligence to new venture creation with the aim of giving direction to the lines of thought of existing and potential entrepreneurs on what to consider in applying AI to business innovations. It ruminates on both the benefits and the demerits of AI application in business (Smith & Johnson, 2021). It also hinges on challenges to AI application.

The study shall be significant to government policymakers in the formulation of policies on small and medium scale enterprises, education, and economic growth and development. It will guide present and future entrepreneurs on how to create new ventures, as well as how to sustain existing businesses. It will also set the pace for further research into how potential and existing entrepreneurs can tap into the benefits that abound in artificial intelligence (Brown *et al.*, 2023).

The advancement of AI technologies has facilitated the recognition of market opportunities and their exploitation and also has profound implications for how entrepreneurs develop, design and scale their organisations. This ultimately leads to promising new venture innovations and accelerates production, enhances work processes and improves efficiency. As a formidable technological engine, AI has become a key source of the Fourth Industrial Revolution (e.g., Daemmrich, 2017). Nevertheless, there are so many factors affecting the business world as a result of the deployment of AI technology. One of them is Job displacements as they have been a subject of numerous business cases. An Oxford Study stated that more than 47% of American jobs will be under threat due to automation by the mid-2030s. Also, the World Economic Forum asserted that Artificial Intelligence automation will replace more than 75 million jobs by 2022. Some of the figures are even more intimidating. Another Mckinsey report, AI-based robots could replace 30% of the current global workforce. Furthermore, AI also brings several trust-related issues on its ability to make decisions that are fair and for the betterment of humankind. There have been various instances where Artificial Intelligence has gone wrong when Twitter Chabot started spewing abusive.

However, as AI is changing business landscape all over the world and as it is identifiable that AI cuts across several fields of endeavour (including entrepreneurship, agriculture,

e-commerce, engineering, healthcare, business, etc.), there is need to know how the application of AI can translate to the development of new ideas for new venture creation. Moreover, since artificial intelligence is a budding topic in business as it relates to Nigeria, only very few studies have been previously conducted on the subject. It is based on these foundations that this paper is proposed.

The main purpose of this study is to explore the impact of artificial intelligence on entrepreneurship and its implications on sustainable venture creation in Nigeria. Additionally, the specific objectives are to determine how AI technology causes reduction of operational time of entrepreneurial processes in Nigeria, to find out how AI technology influences operational efficiency of entrepreneurial processes in Nigeria, to determine how deployment of AI technology eliminates mistakes and human errors in entrepreneurial processes in Nigeria, and to investigate how the use of AI technology on entrepreneurial processes causes labour displacement and job destruction in Nigeria.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

Ahmed (2015) defined artificial intelligence as the art of making machines mimic human intelligence. Palanivelu (2020) defined it as a course which involves the use of computers to produce intelligent automated systems. AI technology helps to perform tasks that could have otherwise been carried out by humans, yet AI is used to perform those tasks in a more efficient way and at a higher success rate. For instance, it can be used for voice recognition, image recognition, search suggestions, virtual assistants, and so forth (Palanivelu, 2020).

Kaput (2016) sees it as a collection of various technologies, with each technology having its own functionality. That is why artificial intelligence can be found to be useful in marketing, healthcare, sales, manufacturing, teaching, and so many more. Moreover, AI technological innovations can pave the way to new venture creation.

New venture creation is an offshoot of entrepreneurship. Meanwhile, entrepreneurship is the establishment and management of a business venture. It is also defined as an activity that involves the discovery, evaluation and exploitation of opportunities to introduce new goods and services, ways of organising, markets, processes and raw materials through organising efforts that previously had not existed (Venkataraman, 1997; Shane & Venkataraman, 2000). Entrepreneurship involves uncertainty and risk, complementary managerial competence, and creative opportunism (Long, 1983). The basic characteristics of entrepreneurship include risk-taking, innovation, and exploitation of opportunities.

Considering the various entrepreneurial opportunities that are in artificial intelligence and the fact that new venture creation is about taking advantage of opportunities, let us therefore consider the factors that affect a business. Using Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Strengths (SWOT) analysis, these factors can be broken down into internal and external factors. While external factors are opportunities (positive factors) and threats (negative factors), the internal factors are strengths (positive factors) and weaknesses (negative factors) (Leigh, 2009). Among the mentioned factors, the ability to apply artificial intelligence to a

particular business solution is an opportunity for a new venture. AI creates an opportunity for a potential entrepreneur who is privileged to discover a business solution that is yet unknown. It is both an opportunity for new venture creation and a medium for the sustainability of the venture, as shall be seen in the practical applications part of this paper. AI technology can proffer solutions to previously unsolved socioeconomic problems and, as well, provide economic success to the entrepreneur. On the other hand, it can result in the loss of jobs, since its innovations involve the use of machines to perform complex tasks that could be performed by humans (Choudhury *et al.*, 2018).

The theoretical underpinnings of AI as applicable to entrepreneurship and new venture creation can be discussed in the light of generativity theory and entrepreneurial cognition theory.

This refers to the capacity of technology (for example AI technology) to allow for adaptation to various applications (Zittrain, 2006). It is the ability of digital platforms to permit recombination of its elements for the extension and redistribution of functionality (Yoo *et al.*, 2010). Generativity shapes the boundary between technology and entrepreneurship. According to Nambisan (2016), a good example of generativity can be deduced from a situation where Apple introduces more functionalities and capabilities to IOS (their digital platform). This creates entrepreneurial opportunities for IT savvy youths, e.g., application development on iPhones. Another example could be in the area of how to connect to or use data from other devices like personal computers, smart televisions, to mention but few. Parker *et al.* (2016) opines that technological generativity expands the opportunity space of entrepreneurs. The generativity theory suggests that business opportunities and ideas would increase if a technological platform is malleable enough to convert a device or its applications into various uses. This implies that an entrepreneur should pay attention to the adaptability of artificial intelligence to various technologies, devices and business ideas in the process of creating new ventures.

This theory states that for an entrepreneur to grab a business opportunity, he should be able to process information about his business environment, identify potential opportunities and strategize on how to take advantage of the opportunities. George *et al* (2016) asserts that entrepreneurial recognition is a major problem to be solved in the process of growing a new venture. The theory is linked to the social cognition theory which asserts that individuals have varying propensities of motivation to take on a business opportunity. The theory also suggests that people with entrepreneurial characteristics are able to easily perceive an opportunity compared to non-entrepreneurs (Baum and Lock, 2004). Thus, potential businessmen with low entrepreneurial characteristics have more work to do in continuously searching for business opportunities with the help of the Internet and other information sources. Arbussa *et al.* (2017) further extend entrepreneurial cognition to strategic sensitivity which refers to an entrepreneur's ability to notice changes in the internal and external environment of his business.

Entrepreneurial cognition theory implies that starting up a sustainable venture requires an entrepreneur to be intentional about continually searching for marketing opportunities, new technologies and other environmental factors that have implications on the success of their business. It also suggests the need to be sensitive to changes in the business environment.

For several decades, the traditional marketing practices of product promotion using the print media which covers magazines, newspaper, flyers, handbills, calendars, gifts, etc. and electronic media (i.e., radio and television) is taking backstage due to decline in customer attention. As the world is going global, more attention is paid to the use of computers and mobile phones than on radio, television and physical newspapers (Vishnoi & Bagga, 2019). People prefer to listen to visual or audio news, read electronic newspapers, and surf information on their areas of interest through their Android phones, iPhones or personal computers, since these gadgets are portable and user-friendly. Thus, online or digital marketing is becoming more prominent all over the world (Mahadevan, 2000). Online marketing comes in various forms which include social media optimization (the use of social media communities to generate publicity for a product/service), social media marketing (the use of social media platforms to promote a product/service), content marketing (the creation and distribution of content to a target audience), search engine optimization (the improvement of the quality and quantity of traffic from a search engine to a website), etc. (Vishnoi & Bagga, 2019).

In the mentioned areas wherein, technology is applied to marketing, artificial intelligence plays a big role in ensuring that the technology fits into the marketing/business purpose. Specific examples of artificial intelligence in marketing include recommendations and content curation which means to discover, gather, and present digital content on a particular area of interest; personalization of news feeds which is the provision of news or information access from various platforms to a network user whenever news/information is available; ad targeting which means to advertise online to audience with specific traits or characteristics (Thurman, 2018).

Asides from the mentioned points, AI systems have the capabilities of providing information about the customers' buying habits and consumption patterns, thereby providing a useful guide to customer satisfaction which is quintessential to business success (Vishnoi & Bagga, 2019).

Artificial intelligence is a potent tool for promoting campaigns through New Media (social media, websites, apps and mobile phone technologies). Opportunities abound in the use of AI-driven tools to provide marketing solutions to businesses, governments and non-governmental organisations (NGO). Firms like IBM, Google, Facebook, Jiji and Amazon are using artificial intelligence technology to create wonderful products/services (Kumar & Trakru, 2019). It is important to mention that the Generativity theory and the Entrepreneurial Cognition theory, in conjunction with AI, are both applicable in shaping the entrepreneur's thoughts in the process of new venture creation and sustainability.

The application of artificial intelligence technology is also phenomenal in electronic commerce. Some of the available AI solutions include: Artificial Intelligence Assistant (Chatbot), Recommendation Engine, Optimal Pricing, etc. (Song *et al.* (2019).

One thing is to offer sales services and another is to deliver a real-time customer service, which is very important for the retention of customers. This suggests the need for a robot-like system that can assume human intelligence by way of dialoguing with customers and attending to their needs. That system is called Artificial Intelligence Assistant or Chatbot. A Chatbot is a technology that uses a natural language processing device to respond to consumers' requests. They reply to voice commands and provide product suggestions. Using machine learning algorithms, Chatbots connect with consumers via chat dialogues on electronic commerce sites and mobile pages (Gururaj, 2021). The functionalities of Chatbots include: Assisting consumers to select their preferred products, confirming the availability of a product, comparing products, paying for the products, contacting customer support personnel for enquiries, among others.

Recommendation Engines are used to provide reliable real-time shopping experiences to consumers. It recommends products or services to consumers based on user needs. It helps businesses to understand customer behaviours via personalization and analysis of search requests and purchase history. With artificial intelligence algorithms embedded in Recommendation Engines, companies are able to predict which goods/services are likely to attract customers (Gururaj, 2021). With an appropriate understanding of the functionality of this technology, an entrepreneur can strategize on how to incorporate it into his business ideas to improve his/her competitive status in the market.

Optimal price determination is a major obstacle to the success of most businesses. Going by the price theory in Economics, the higher the price, the lower the quantity demanded for normal goods. However, that may not always be the case for abnormal goods (goods that do not obey the law of demand) (Franco, 2013). Also, the dynamism in human nature goes further to pose difficulties in optimal price determination (i.e., fixing a price that will result in the highest net sales). While determining the optimal price may be a challenge, especially where large consumer data is involved, artificial intelligence technology solves the problem of automated pricing for a wide range of commodities. The technology uses product rating, logistics costs, service quality and price trends to make forecasts. It eases the manual work involved in monitoring the competitor's costs and prices (Gururaj, 2021).

Artificial intelligence is also applicable to warehouse operations. AI-powered robotic systems help to run automated pick and pack operations in a warehouse. It has the capabilities of operating on a 24-hour per day and 7 days per week basis (Gururaj, 2021). The system is advantageous in the sense that it reduces errors in the packing and retrieval of goods. The robots can take on highly risky tasks, thereby ensuring the safety of warehouse workers. It is however, expensive to install and may require huge financial outlay if applied to large warehouses.

For the advantages, as it relates to entrepreneurship, AI systems come with financial rewards (Cagetti & De Nardi, 2006), non-commercial benefits (Blanchflower, 2004), satisfaction (Binder & Coad, 2016), earnings (Astebro & Chen, 2014), wellbeing (Wiklund *et al.*, 2019); autonomy, independence and flexibility (Carter, 2011).

At the same time, the disadvantages of AI include growing inequality and an unhealthy competitive business environment created by a skewed application of the AI technology. Another disadvantage is in the area of labour displacement (Wiklund *et al.*, 2019).

The lack of or inadequacy of the required technical skills to man an AI-enabled system remains the biggest challenge to its functionality in an organisation. Another challenge is the dearth of data needed to process information about the business solution intended by an entrepreneur (Palanivelu, 2020). Other challenges include lack of awareness of the availability or applicability of an AI technology, due to poor knowledge about trends in the AI technology environment.

Framework for new Venture Creation

AI can be considered as a digital external enabler of new venture ideas (Briel *et al.*, 2018).

The overall impacts of AI on the antecedents of venture formation, the firm-level activities, and the potential implications for entrepreneurial outcomes are shown in the figure below.

Figure 1: Framework for the Study

Initiative of New Venture Creation

In Vogel’s (2017) framework for understanding the new venture formation, he points to triggers and idea generation as early stages of this process. Such activities can be affected by both individual and external system-level factors (McMullen & Shepherd, 2006) and therefore AI deployed either selectively or ubiquitously has the potential to impact on both the likelihood of an individual deciding to start a venture and the type of venture that they start.

Prospecting of New Venture Ideas

Turning now to venture-level activities, Cockburn *et al.* (2018) suggest that AI is leading to a new “innovation playbook” that leverages large datasets and learning algorithms to precisely predict phenomena. It’s therefore logical to assume that such datasets and algorithms could be

turned towards entrepreneurial opportunity identification and exploitation. The originality of these AI systems for innovation search processes lies in the ability to see patterns or detail in data that are difficult to perceive by humans. In a medical science context this might involve applications that can recognize cancer at an earlier stage than human experts (Leachman & Merlino, 2017; Miller & Brown, 2018) or new technology firms such as Atomwise (Agrawal *et al.*, 2019) who use AI to predict the outcome of chemical interactions, removing the need to manually test hundreds to thousands of compounds and in doing so reducing discovery and optimization processes that take years to a matter of weeks. This superhuman information search and prediction is also being applied to a range of commercial contexts. The real estate company Skyline2 collects millions of data points on property trends such as yield levels and default rates to predict where investors should buy. Scoop Markets3 meanwhile analyses the content of Twitter messages to predict which breaking news stories may influence exchange prices, thus enabling equity traders to act before markets move.

Organisational Design of New Venture Creation

Thus far, AI has only had a moderate impact on the venture's structure (Brock & von Wangenheim, 2019). Surveys of business executives confirm that AI has typically been used for discrete local problems (Fountain *et al.*, 2019), or in an experimental manner and has not yet been widely used "at scale" in organisations (Ransbotham *et al.*, 2018). Of the limited empirical research that has examined the impact of AI on organisational structure, Davenport and Ronanki (2018) suggests an emerging division of labour in some firms for routine tasks to be automated with higher-value, customer-facing tasks performed by humans. While AI may destroy jobs, new roles will be created too (Daugherty *et al.*, 2019). Wilson *et al.* (2017) anticipates three new employee categories that will be required as firms adjust to the wide diffusion of AI. They include trainers, who improve algorithms by adding nuance to decision-making and interpretation; explainers who bridge the technical gap between AI systems and business managers; and finally, sustainers who will manage ethics and the ongoing management of the system.

Exploiting New Venture Ideas

The final firm-level activity are the tasks associated with exploiting new venture ideas as may be impacted by AI. Opportunity exploitation is a multidimensional construct within entrepreneurial activities and is taken by some to constitute mobilising resources and building capabilities (Sarason *et al.*, 2006) while others focus on market selection (Hsieh *et al.*, 2007) or market exchange (Dimov, 2011). However, for this study, the focus is on two AI-relevant exploiting activities: selling and scaling the venture. Selling has been underexplored by entrepreneurship scholars, despite the fundamental importance of the activity to the sustainability and growth of new ventures (Gimmon & Levie, 2020; Matthews *et al.*, 2018). It is an area that entrepreneurs promoting innovative market offerings identify as a challenge (Renko, 2013) and is one of the main skill deficits that restrict venture growth (Fogel *et al.*, 2012). In short, many entrepreneurial ventures fail or underperform, not because of weak

product-market fit, but because they have insufficient sales capabilities to capitalise on the venture idea.

Perceived Risk

Perceived risk has long been a factor in entrepreneurial studies. Scholars have emphasised the critical role of risk in venture selection and creation. Das and Teng (1997, p.70) emphasised that “risk taking appears to be one of the most distinctive features of entrepreneurial behaviour, since creating new ventures is by definition a risky business”. Keh *et al.* (2002) further stressed that entrepreneurs are likely to evaluate a business idea more favourably when they perceive less risk in the execution of the idea.

Entrepreneurial Intention

A small segment of entrepreneurs is guided by an entrepreneurial spirit at birth while others need to be led, trained, and educated to initiate entrepreneurial intention. Bird (1988) emphasised the notion of entrepreneurial intention, which he clarified as the entrepreneur’s state of mind that directs his attention, experience, and action toward a business concept. According to the author, entrepreneurial intention sets the form and direction of the business venture at its inception. He also indicated that intention is a psychological process aimed at either creating a new venture or creating new values in existing ventures. Basically, the quintessence of the entrepreneurial intention is the entrepreneur’s mindset that is directed toward innovation and wealth creation. The subject of entrepreneurs’ intention has long been an important field of research and investigation in entrepreneurship literature. Busenitz and Lou (1996) observed that the way one thinks could have a significant impact on the intention to start a new venture, while Zhang and Cain (2017) declared that entrepreneurial intention is considered a valuable and practical approach to understanding entrepreneurial behaviour. Boukamcha (2015) studied the linkage mechanism by which training influences intentions. Quan (2012) makes a distinction between two levels of entrepreneurial intention: (a) impulsive entrepreneurial intention and (b) deliberate entrepreneurial intention. Impulsive intention, according to the author, is swayed by the individual’s cultural background and personal characteristics, while deliberate entrepreneurial intention is influenced by prior experience and social networks of the individual. The creation of a new venture to pursue an opportunity is labelled the *entrepreneurial event*, while the individual who perceives an opportunity is called an *entrepreneur* (Bygrave and Hofer, 1991). Some scholars (e.g., Low and MacMillan, 1988) use the term *entrepreneurship* to mean the creation of new ventures. Sarason *et al.* (2006), asserted that the act of entrepreneurship occurs as the entrepreneur specifies, integrates, and acts upon the sources of opportunity.

Entrepreneurial Outcome

With the foregoing discussion on entrepreneurial antecedent, prospecting, organisational design, exploiting and risk taking, it is important to consider what potential outcomes in terms of how entrepreneurial rewards may be derived from AI-enabled entrepreneurship. Entrepreneurial rewards have been analysed by a number of scholars who have identified

different constituent parts of rewards including financial rewards (Cagetti & De Nardi, 2006), nonpecuniary benefits (Blanchflower, 2004), satisfaction (Binder & Coad, 2016), earnings (Astebro & Chen, 2014), and wellbeing (Wiklund et al., 2019). Being autonomous, independent, and having some levels of flexibility have also been stressed as benefits of being one's own boss but are often overly simplistic in their explanation of the reasons for pursuing entrepreneurship (Carter, 2011). Consistent within such characterizations is seeking to understand the outcomes that entrepreneurs achieve in their efforts, which can unveil motivations and behaviours across the wider entrepreneurial process. The nature and role of such differentials may change when AI-enabled entrepreneurship starts to become more commonplace.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

The research approach adopted for this paper is qualitative. Qualitative research relies on data obtained by the researcher from first-hand observation, focus groups, recordings made in natural settings, documents, and artefacts. The data are generally nonnumerical (Creswell, 2017). Contemporary qualitative data analyses can be supported by computer programs (termed computer-assisted qualitative data analysis software). A central issue in qualitative research is trustworthiness (also known as credibility or, in quantitative studies, validity). There are many ways of establishing trustworthiness, including member check, interviewer corroboration, peer debriefing, negative case analysis, auditability, confirmability Lincoln et al (2015). The limitations of qualitative research include participant reactivity, the potential for a qualitative investigator to over-identify with one or more study participants etc. Consequently, the researcher did a review of extant literature of both artificial intelligence and entrepreneurship, so as to incorporate both constructs and come up with practical implications of AI technology to both existing and potential entrepreneurs. A review was preferred for this paper because of its ability to provide sufficient information on past studies on the subject matter. Ten (10) journal articles on artificial intelligence and ten on entrepreneurship with a focus on new venture creation were reviewed. Information linkage of both categories to the constructs of the paper was done together with analysis of both the advantages and disadvantages of artificial intelligence. The factors to be considered in applying artificial intelligence to venture creation were explored and finally the information about the challenges of artificial intelligence implementation in business was articulated.

4.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The study revealed that AI technology influenced the reduction of operational time through automation and optimization of entrepreneurial routine processes and tasks. It was established that AI technology significantly influenced the productivity and operational efficiency of entrepreneurial processes

It was also revealed that deployment of AI technology eliminated mistakes and human error in entrepreneurial processes

The study showed that AI technology deployment on entrepreneurial processes caused labour displacement and job destruction.

The integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) into the realm of entrepreneurship has brought forth significant implications for sustainable venture creation in Nigeria

The findings of this study highlight the transformative potential of AI in shaping traditional business models. AI-driven automation and data-driven decision-making enable entrepreneurs in Nigeria to optimise processes, reduce operational costs, and enhance the quality of their products and services.

The integration of AI technologies, such as chatbots and personalised recommendation systems, enhances customer engagement and provides a more tailored experience. Nigerian entrepreneurs can leverage AI-powered customer analytics to understand consumer behaviour, thereby enabling them to develop targeted marketing strategies and build stronger customer relationships.

Nigeria's entrepreneurial ecosystem often grapples with resource constraints, inhibiting growth and innovation. The study underscores how AI can serve as a catalyst for overcoming these challenges. By automating repetitive tasks and streamlining operations, AI enables entrepreneurs to focus on strategic decision-making and innovation, even in resource-constrained environments.

As AI systems gain autonomy, concerns arise regarding data privacy, algorithmic bias, and potential job displacement. In the Nigerian context, these concerns are intertwined with socioeconomic factors. Policymakers and entrepreneurs alike must collaborate to develop frameworks that address these challenges and ensure that AI-driven entrepreneurship contributes to equitable economic growth.

The study sheds light on the evolving skill requirements within the Nigerian entrepreneurial landscape. Entrepreneurs need to acquire new skills to effectively harness AI technologies. This has implications for education and training programs, which must adapt to equip aspiring entrepreneurs with the necessary technical and analytical skills.

The findings underscore the importance of fostering collaborative ecosystems that bring together entrepreneurs, AI experts, policymakers, and academia. These collaborations can facilitate knowledge exchange, technology transfer, and the co-creation of innovative AI-driven ventures.

As AI continues to evolve, several avenues for future research and practice emerge. Longitudinal studies tracking the long-term impact of AI integration on venture sustainability and economic growth in Nigeria could provide valuable insights. Additionally, exploring the role of AI in social entrepreneurship and its potential to address pressing societal challenges remains an uncharted territory worthy of exploration.

5.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

This paper is intended to raise the awareness of entrepreneurs, especially would-be entrepreneurs, of AI-based entrepreneurial opportunities. The advancement of AI technologies has facilitated the recognition of market opportunities and their exploitation and also has profound implications for how entrepreneurs develop, design and scale their organisations. This ultimately leads to promising new venture innovations and accelerates production, enhances work processes and improves efficiency. As a formidable technological engine, AI has become a key source of the Fourth Industrial Revolution (e.g., Daemrich, 2017). The paper reveals that despite the numerous benefits of AI-based entrepreneurial opportunities, there are still pitfalls such as labour displacement and job destruction.

Recommendations

Government should put in place a policy framework that would establish AI-based entrepreneurial business grants and provide low-interest loans to existing entrepreneurs and potential entrepreneurs with AI technology-based business ventures. Government should also intensify efforts towards organising AI Technology Competition programmes for young Nigerians with enticing prizes for winners, as that would encourage our young talents to invent new technologies that will offer solutions to several economic problems of the country, ranging from agriculture to manufacturing and so forth.

The paper also suggests the need for further research into the link between artificial intelligence and entrepreneurship particularly in the areas of application of artificial intelligence to tackle business challenges and taking balanced business decisions.

References

- Ahmed, K. (2015). Google's Demis Hassabis – Misuse of artificial intelligence 'could do harm'. <http://www.bbc.com/news/business-34266425> Accessed: 6 November 2018.
- Amabile, T. (2019). GUIDEPOST: Creativity, artificial intelligence, and a world of surprises. Guidepost letter for Academy of management discoveries. Academy of Management Discoveries, 0(ja), null. <https://doi.org/10.5465/amd.2019.0075>
- Arbussa, A., Bikfalvi, A., & Marquès, P. (2017). Strategic agility-driven business model renewal: the case of an SME. *Manag. Decis.* 55, 271–293. doi: 10.1108/MD-05-2016-0355
- Astebro, T., & Chen, J. (2014). *The entrepreneurial earnings puzzle: Mismeasurement or real?* *Journal of Business Venturing*, 29(1), 88–105.
- Baum, J. R., & Locke, E. A. (2004). The relationship of entrepreneurial traits, skill, and motivation to subsequent venture growth. *J. Appl. Psychol.* 89, 587–598. doi: 10.1037/0021-9010.89.4.587
- Binder, M., & Coad, A. (2016). *How satisfied are the self-employed? A life domain view.* *Journal of Happiness Studies*, 17(4), 1409–1433.
- Blanchflower, D. G. (2004). Self-employment: More may not be better. *Swedish Economic Policy Review*, 11(2), 15–74.
- Cagetti, M., & De Nardi, M. (2006). Entrepreneurship, frictions, and wealth. *Journal of Political Economy*, 114(5), 835–870.

- Carter, S. (2011). The rewards of entrepreneurship: Exploring the incomes, wealth, and economic wellbeing of entrepreneurial households. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 35(1), 39–55. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-6520.2010.00422.x>
- Choudhury, P., Starr, E., & Agarwal, R. (2018). *Machine learning and human capital: experimental evidence on productivity complementarities*. Harvard Business School.
- Cockburn, I. M., Henderson, R., & Stern, S. (2018). *The impact of artificial intelligence on innovation*. National Bureau of Economic Research.
- Leigh, D. (2009). *SWOT Analysis*. Handbook of Improving Performance in the Work Place, Vol. 1. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9780470592663.ch24>
- Ekbia, H.R. (2009). Digital artifacts as quasi-objects: Qualification, mediation, and materiality. *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 60(12), 2554–2566.
- Franco, J. Agustín (2013). Principles of Econometrics from the Giffen Demand. *Technological and economic development of economy*, 21(4), 557–576
- Gaskin, J., Berente, N., Lyytinen, K., & Yoo, Y. (2014). Toward generalizable sociomaterial inquiry: A computational approach for zooming in and out of sociomaterial routines. *MIS Quarterly*, 38(3), 849–871.
- George et al (2016). Toward the development of a big data analytics capability. *Information & Management* 53(8),1049-1064.
- Girish K, Syeda A & Ayesha S (2011). Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) –A Review. *International Journal of Dental Clinics* 2011:3(1):65-70.
- Gururaj, P. (2021). Artificial intelligence-application in the field of e-commerce. *International Journal of Research - 9(4)*, 170–177.
- Kaput, M. (2016). *The Marketer's Guide to Artificial Intelligence Terminology*. <https://www.marketingainstitute.com/blog/themarketers-guidetoartificialintelligenceterminology>.
- Kumar, V., Rajan, B., Venkatesan, R., & Lecinski, J. (2019). Understanding the role of intelligence in personalized engagement marketing. *California Management Review*, 61(4),135–155. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0008125619859317>
- Lincoln, Y. & Guba, E. G. (1985) *Naturalistic Inquiry*. Newbury Park, CA: Sage Publications.
- Mahadevan, B. (2000). *Business Models for Internet-Based E-Commerce: An Anatomy*. California Management Review, 55-69.
- Majchrzak, A. & Malhotra, A. (2013). Towards an information systems perspective and research agenda on crowdsourcing for innovation. *Journal of Strategic Information Systems*, 22, 257–268.
- Majchrzak, A. & Markus, M. (2013). *Technology affordances and constraints theory (of MIS)*. In E. Kessler (Ed.), *Encyclopedia of management theory* (pp. 832–836). Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE Publications.
- Nambisan, S. & Zahra, S.A. (2016). The role of demand-side narratives in opportunity formation and enactment. *Journal of Business Venturing Insights*, 5, 70–75.
- Palanivelu, V. R. & Vasanthi, B. (2020) *Role of artificial intelligence in business transformation*. *International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology* 29(4), 392-400.

- Parker, G., Van Alstyne, M., & Choudary, S.P. (2016). *Platform revolution: How networked markets are transforming the economy—and how to make them work for you*. New York: W.W. Norton Publishing.
- Shane, S., & Venkataraman, S. (2000). The promise of entrepreneurship as a field of research. *Academy of Management Review*, 25(1), 217–226.
<https://doi.org/10.5465/amr.2000.2791611>(Long, 1983).
- Song, X., Yang, S., Huang, Z., & Huang, T. (2019). The Application of Artificial Intelligence in Electronic Commerce. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* (3), 1302–1302.
- Thurman, N. (2018). Personalization of News. In: Vos, T. P., Hanusch, F., Dimitrakopoulou, D., Geertsema-Sligh, M. and Sehl, A. (Eds.), *The International Encyclopedia of Journalism Studies*. Massachusetts, USA: Wiley-Blackwell.
- Vishnoi, S. K. & Bagga, T. (2019). Artificial intelligence enabled marketing solutions: a review. *Indian Journal of Artificial Intelligence Economics & Business, Vo Enabled Marketing* 17(4),67-17
- Wiklund, J., Wright, M., & Zahra, S. A. (2019). Conquering relevance: Entrepreneurship research's grand challenge. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 43(3), 419–436.
- Yoo *et al.* (2010). The new organizing logic of digital innovation: An agenda for information systems research. *Information Systems Research*, 21(4), 724–735
- Zittrain, J. (2006). *The generative Internet*. *Harvard Law Review*, 119(7), 1975–2040.

Analysing the Effects of Ownership Structure on Financial Performance of Oil Firms in Nigeria

Ejiofor Emmanuel Onyeka, PhD¹ & Abada Uchechukwu Daniel, PhD²

¹Department of Banking and Finance; ²Department of Accountancy,

¹ & ²Madonna University Nigeria, Okija Campus

¹ emmaejiofor7@gmail.com

Correspondence: ² ucheabada3@gmail.com; 0802 386 2353

Abstract

Research Objective: This study investigated the impact of ownership structure on the financial performance of listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria's capital market.

Methodology: A quantitative approach was employed, using secondary data from publicly available financial reports of the listed firms. Panel data regression analysis was conducted to examine the relationship between ownership structure and financial performance, specifically return on assets.

Findings: The regression results revealed that ownership structure has a positive but insignificant effect on return on assets, indicating a potential but limited influence on financial performance for the sampled firms.

Conclusion: The findings suggest that while ownership structure may have a positive effect on financial performance, it is not a significant determinant for oil and gas firms in Nigeria.

Recommendations: Policymakers and investors should consider other corporate governance factors alongside ownership structure when seeking to enhance firm performance. Further research could explore additional variables that may have a more substantial impact on financial outcomes.

Key words: Corporate Governance, Financial Performance, ownership structure, oil & gas firms.

1.0 Introduction

Corporate governance therefore can be defined as a set of processes, customs, policies, laws, and institutions affecting the way a corporation is directed, administered, or controlled. It is about building effective mechanisms and measures, either to satisfy current social expectations or to satisfy the narrower expectations of shareholders. Corporate governance also deals with how

suppliers of finance to corporations assure themselves of getting a return on their investment. Corporate governance systems can be categorised according to the degree of ownership concentration and the identity of controlling shareholders (Duke & Kankpang, 2011).

Corporate governance could also be seen as a concept that includes communication channels, separation of roles and responsibilities, behaviour among the shareholders, the board of directors (both executives and non-executives), and the chief executive officer (CEO).

In 2001, the Enron scandal marked the commencement of a period in which corporate governance of, in particular, listed companies became a global discussion (Al-Malkawi & Pillai, 2012). The primary goal is to impose good behaviour on listed and now, non-listed firms (George & Karibo, 2014).

In Nigeria's oil and gas sector, ownership structures can be categorised into three main types: state-owned enterprises, privately owned companies, and multinational corporations. State owned enterprises like the Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation (NNPC) dominate production but often face challenges related to bureaucratic inefficiencies. Conversely, privately owned firms may exhibit greater agility and responsiveness to market changes but might lack the capital resources available to larger entities. Multinational corporations bring substantial investment and technological expertise but may prioritise profit repatriation over local reinvestment.

The effects of ownership structure on the financial performance of oil and gas firms in Nigeria presents a complex and multifaceted challenge such as: data availability and quality, defining ownership structure, measuring financial performance, economic and political instability, corruption and inefficiency etc. Addressing these challenges can contribute to a better understanding of the effect of ownership structure on financial performance in the Nigerian oil and gas sector, ultimately leading to improved governance and economic development.

The objective of this study is to:

Establish the influence of ownership structure on return on assets (ROA) of oil & gas firms in Nigeria.

The following research question will, therefore guide the study:

How far does ownership structure influence the return on assets (ROA) of oil & gas firms in Nigeria?

Statement of Hypotheses:

Ho. Ownership structure does not have a positive and significant influence on return on assets (ROA) of oil & gas firms in Nigeria.

The study assessed the influence of corporate governance on firm financial performance of listed oil and gas firms on the Nigerian Stock Exchange for 11 years (2012-2022). The researchers' choice of 2012 as the base year arose as a result of Nigeria's adoption of "International Financial Reporting Standard (IFRS)," in that year. In line with the objective set out in the study, the index used is Ownership Structure.

2.0 Review of Related Literature

Corporate governance gives ultimate authority and complete responsibility to the board of directors, and ensures transparency which in turn ensures strong and balanced economic development. The beauty of corporate governance is that it has a broad scope which includes both social and institutional aspects, and ultimately encourages a trustworthy, moral, as well as ethical environment (Akinleye, Olarewaju & Fajuyagbe, 2019).

Effective Corporate Governance Practice

Board governance normally includes the interests of all company stakeholders and considers the impacts of environment, social, and governance (ESG) risks and opportunities. "Jurisdictions across the world aim to influence the private sector through their own international corporate governance framework. These are mainly a regulatory mix of company and securities law, as well as listing rules and corporate governance codes," (Osundina, Olayinka & Chukwuma, 2016). As noted by OECD (2017), "these elements of 'self-law' are derived from company law and explain how the responsibilities and obligations of directors are effectively discharged."

However, the underlying goal of corporate governance legislation is to promote transparency and integrity in business. The flexible nature of this legislation acknowledges the individuality of companies, whereby each company has its own distinct institutional profile and unique blend of history and legacy.

Although there is no one universal system of effective corporate governance, there are opportunities for companies to apply commonly accepted international practices that promote market confidence and encourage more efficient global capital markets, (Narwal & Jindal, 2015).

According to Tricker (2015), corporate governance codes around the world have come together due to attributing factors such as globalisation of markets, companies, securities regulation and the increased activity of international institutional investors. Despite international convergence, the national bodies that publish and regulate local corporate governance codes vary significantly between countries.

Investors are recognizing corporate governance disclosures as a crucial insight into a company's practices, culture, data management and authenticity of reporting. The presence of effective governance structures and metrics is a key element that can contribute to investor confidence in

non-financial information and can help investors gain a better understanding of a company's prospects (WBCSD & PWC, 2018).

This shift has encouraged boards to focus on a long time horizon that will account for ESG-related risks and opportunities that may only materialise in future (maybe in 5 to 10 years rather than next financial quarter). "This inclusive and integrated approach to governance requires directors to act in the best interests of the company by acknowledging the legitimate needs, interests and expectations of all material stakeholders," (Babatunde & Akeju 2015).

Ownership Structure

Ownership structure refers to the types and composition of shareholders in a corporation. Ownership structure comprises some observable measures of ownership concentration or the extent of inside ownership (Ryu & Yoo, 2011). According to Yang, Chun & Ramadili (2009), there are two broad classifications for ownership structures. The first classification is according to the proportion of shares owned by insiders and outsiders while the second is the proportion of shares owned by institutional and individual shareholders (Anis, Chizema, Lui & Fakhreldin, 2017).

"This acquisition is deemed to be useful in reducing agency conflicts and aligning the interests of management and shareholders. Secondly, some outsiders who own a significant number of the firms' shares have more power and more incentive to monitor management activity, particularly the financial reporting process, thereby reducing the likelihood of earnings management," (Kim & Lu, 2011).

Classification of ownership structure considers the way control and ownership rights are developed and implemented. Ownership is considered from two main dimensions: ownership concentration and ownership identity. Ownership concentration refers to the number of shares owned by the majority shareholders while ownership identity relies on the people who have shares in the firm and how they use such shares to generate revenues for the shareholders (Mokhtar & Mellett, 2013).

"In a system of concentrated ownership, collective action problems allow controlling families to exercise influence on legislative outcomes, stifling the enactment of investor protection law," (Anderson & Reeb, 2003). Institutional investors are another important class of shareholders that usually may have the interest and profile to fill the monitoring role in widely held corporations.

"As always, large institutional investors have been pioneers in setting up corporate governance rules," (Gugler, Mueller & Yurtoglu, 2007). As their objective is to earn a profit from their stakes, they are naturally sensitive to firm performance and are likely to create noise in the markets and wield significant influence on boards of directors.

Ownership structure is a significant factor in corporate governance. Companies with CEO Ownership, where the chief executive officer holds a significant stake in the company, often exhibit distinct characteristics. These characteristics can influence the company's culture, decision making, and overall performance. These characteristics include: alignment of interests, decision-making and risk tolerance, company culture and employee engagement, financial performance etc. CEO ownership can be a powerful driver for long-term growth and success, as it fosters alignment of interests, encourages conservative decision-making, and promotes a culture of ownership and responsibility.

3.0 Methodology

The study employed the Ex-Post facto design. "The ex-post facto research design also known as causal-comparative research involves the ascertaining of past factor(s) on the present happening or event". The study was carried out on the quoted companies listed on Nigerian Stock Exchange. However, all the studied firms are domiciled and operate within the geographical boundaries of Nigeria. The study concentrated on the oil and gas sector of The Nigerian Stock Exchange. This sector includes all companies engaged in operating and/or developing oil and gas field properties, and companies primarily engaged in recovering and producing liquid hydrocarbons from oil and gas field gases.

Secondary data were utilised in this study for the analysis. The data for this research work were sourced from annual reports of the sampled companies. The data collated were analysed using panel data analysis that provided the description analogies such as mean, median, standard deviation, etc. Data analysis was processed with the aid of E-views 10.0 statistical software. Presently, there are eleven (11) listed companies in the oil and gas sector of the Nigerian Stock Exchange thus:

1. 11 PLC (Mobil).
2. Ardova PLC
3. Capital Oil PLC
4. Conoil PLC
5. Eterna PLC
6. Japaul Gold & Ventures PLC
7. MRS Oil Nigeria PLC
8. Oando PLC
9. Rak Unity Pet. Co PLC

10. Seplant Pet. Dev. Co PLC

11. Total Nigeria PLC

The period of study covered is eight (11) years (2012 – 2022).

The sampling method used for this study is the purposive sampling method. This method is also known as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling. The type of purposive sampling applied to this work is the total population sampling as it enables the researcher the choice to examine the entire population that has one or more shared characteristics and this is common to studies of particular groups within larger populations. The sample of this study is therefore drawn from the eleven (11) companies listed in the oil and gas sector of the Nigerian Stock Exchange. In the course of this study, a sectional sample of five (5) listed companies in the oil and gas sector was conducted. The decision to study five (5) out of the eleven (11) firms listed in the oil and gas sector of the Exchange was informed by the fact that some of the firms were on technical suspension and some moribund. Hence, six (6) firms were therefore dropped for the reason of inactivity in the capital market.

This selection of five (5) out of the eleven (11) listed companies was accomplished by picking the companies that were active in the capital market during the period of study.

The companies considered are listed below:

1. Conoil Plc
2. 11 Plc
3. MRS Nigeria Plc
4. Oando Plc
5. Total Nigeria Plc

Model Specification

In this research, corporate governance characteristics will serve as the independent variables while firms' financial performance represented by returns on assets (ROA) will serve as the dependent variable. The model is expressed in implicit and explicit forms below:

$$P = \beta_1 (CG) + \varepsilon$$

Where:

P = Profitability

CG = Corporate Governance

ε = Error Term

Econometrically, the model used to estimate the relationship between corporate governance

(Measured as ownership concentration) and profitability (measured as return on assets (ROA)) is:

$$ROA_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 OC_{it} + \varepsilon_{it}$$

ROA = Return on Assets, which is an indicator of how profitable a company is relative to its total assets.

β_0 = Intercept

β_1 = Regression coefficient of the independent and control variables.

OC = Ownership Concentration, which represents the percentage of shares held by the top shareholders.

ε = Error Term

i = Number of companies

t = Time period (in years).

4.0 Data Presentation and Analysis

Table 1: Panel Data for the Focal and Explanatory Variables of the Sampled Oil and Gas

OIL & GAS				
	YEA R	OS	ROA	FA
			₦	
CON OIL	2012	1	0.05	52
	2013	1	0.17	53
	2014	1	0.05	54
	2015	1	0.13	55
	2016	1	0.15	56
	2017	1	0.09	57
	2018	1	0.10	58

THE EFFECTS OF OWNERSHIP STRUCTURE ON FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF OIL FIRMS IN NIGERIA

	2019	1	0.10	59
	2020	1	0.03	60
	2021	1	0.06	61
	2022	1	0.08	62
MRS NIG. PLC	2012	1	0.11	43
	2013	1	0.03	44
	2014	1	0.04	45
	2015	1	0.04	46
	2016	1	0.07	47
	2017	1	0.06	48
	2018	1	(0.06)	49
	2019	1	(0.09)	50
	2020	1	(0.13)	51
	2021	1	0.02	52
	2022	1	0.07	53
TOTAL NIG. PLC	2012	1	0.06	56
	2013	1	0.06	57
	2014	1	0.06	58
	2015	1	0.05	59
	2016	1	0.11	60
	2017	1	0.07	61
	2018	1	0.06	62
	2019	1	0.02	63
	2020	1	0.01	64

THE EFFECTS OF OWNERSHIP STRUCTURE ON FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF OIL FIRMS IN NIGERIA

	2021	1	0.08	65
	2022	1	0.05	66
OANDO NIG PLC	2012	1	0.05	56
	2013	1	0.009	57
	2014	1	-3.34	58
	2015	1	-0.98	59
	2016	1	0.02	60
	2017	1	0.08	61
	2018	1	0.10	62
	2019	1	0.009	63
	2020	1	(2.08)	64
	2021	1	(0.25)	65
	2022	1	(0.41)	66
11 NIG. PLC. (MOBILE)	2012	1	0.55	62
	2013	1	0.50	63
	2014	1	0.46	64
	2015	1	0.27	65
	2016	1	0.41	66
	2017	1	0.27	67
	2018	1	0.28	68
	2019	1	0.23	69
	2020	1	0.15	70
	2021	1	0.02	71
	2022	1	0.03	72

Sources: Annual Report and Accounts of Sampled Oil and Gas Companies in Nigeria (2012-2022)

Where:

- OS - Ownership Structure
- ROA - Return on Assets
- FA - Firm Age

The table above displays data gathered from annual reports and accounts of selected oil and gas companies in Nigeria. This information was sourced from the corporate websites of the respective firms, the Nigeria Stock Exchange Library, and online sources. The variables listed exhibit varying degrees of linearity, as indicated by subsequent analyses.

INDUSTRY PANEL DATA ANALYSIS

Table 2: Descriptive Statistic of the Industry Level Panel Data

	OS	ROA	FA
Mean	1.000000	-0.033127	58.800000
Median	1.000000	0.060000	60.000000
Maximum	1.000000	0.550000	72.000000
Minimum	1.000000	-3.340000	43.000000
Std. Dev.	0.000000	0.578622	7.090421
Skewness	0.000000	1.817053	-0.399600
Kurtosis	0.000000	27.62053	2.534997
Jarque-Bera	0.000000	1113.877	1.959255
Probability	0.000000	0.500000	0.375451
Sum	55.000000	-1.822000	3234.000
Sum Sq. Dev.	0.000000	18.07940	2714.800
Observations	55	55	55

Source: Computed by Researcher Using Eviews 10.0 Statistical Software

Table 2 above presents the variable descriptions derived from 55 observations of time series panel data concerning the sampled oil and gas companies in Nigeria. Within the table, the industry's minimum values are as follows: Ownership structure 1.00, Return on Assets -3.34, and firm age of 43. Conversely, the maximum values for the companies include Ownership structure 1.00, Return on Assets 0.55, and firm age of 72. Meanwhile, the industry means for the variables are as follows: Ownership structure 1.00, Return on Assets -0.0331, and firm age at 58.

The normality of the data distribution is evident through the coefficients of Skewness, Kurtosis, and Jarque-Bera Probability. As per Table 2, the Jarque-Bera Statistics probabilities for all variables (both focal and explanatory) have insignificant p-values. The insignificance of these p-values suggests a normal distribution for all studied variables. This observation is corroborated by the skewness coefficients, which indicate that outliers are not significantly distant from one for all variables. Additionally, the kurtosis coefficient provides further confirmation of normal distribution for all variables. These findings pertain to data extracted from annual reports and accounts of sampled oil and gas firms in Nigeria.

Table 3: Regression Analysis Result of the Industry Level Panel Data

Dependent Variable: ROA

Method: Panel Least Squares

Date: 05/16/24 Time: 14:17

Sample: 2012 2022

Periods included: 11

Cross-sections included: 5

Total panel (balanced) observations: 55

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
OS	0.19098	0.489246	0.390356	0.66386
C	4.996847	3.422343	1.460066	0.14601
R-squared	0.740828	Mean dependent var		10.66613

Adjusted R-squared	0.702797	S.D. dependent var	19.88069
S.E. of regression	10.14137	Akaike info criterion	7.344772
Sum squared resid	3572.596	Schwarz criterion	7.625548
Log likelihood	-140.245	Hannan-Quinn criter.	7.446292
F-statistic	18.50546	Durbin-Watson stat	1.497187
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000		

Source: *Computed by Researcher Using Eviews 11 Statistical Software*

Table 3 presents the impact of the independent variable on return on assets. Ownership structure exhibits a positive effect on return on assets but is not statistically significant, with a p-value of 0.66386. The adjusted R-squared (R²) value suggests that approximately 70% of the variations in return on assets are explained by the explanatory variable, ownership structure. The remaining 30% may be attributed to other factors influencing return on assets in the context of sampled oil and gas firms in Nigeria, as well as additional remote factors captured by the error term. Moreover, the probability of the F-statistic is significant, indicating the statistical adequacy of the multiple regression model and its results. Additionally, there is an absence of serial autocorrelation in the panel data extracted from the annual reports and accounts of the sampled oil and gas firms.

Test of Hypothesis

Restatement of the Hypothesis in Null and Alternate forms:

Null Hypothesis: Ownership Structure does not have a positive and significant influence on return on assets (ROA) of oil & gas firms in Nigeria.

Alternative Hypothesis: Ownership Structure has a positive and significant influence on return on assets (ROA) of oil & gas firms in Nigeria.

Statement of Decision Rule:

Reject the null hypothesis (H₀), if the p-value of the t-statistics is less than 0.05. Otherwise accept the null hypothesis and reject the alternative hypothesis.

Decision

In Table 3, the regression results indicate that ownership structure has a positive but insignificant influence on return on assets. This suggests that an increase in ownership structure may have a positive effect on return on assets for the sampled oil and gas firms in Nigeria, but this

relationship is not statistically significant. With a p-value of 0.66386 for ownership structure, which is greater than the significance level of 0.05, the null hypothesis cannot be rejected, and the alternative hypothesis is not supported. Therefore, the study concludes that ownership structure exerts positive and insignificant effects on the return on assets of the sampled oil and gas firms in Nigeria.

Summary of Findings

Ownership structure demonstrates a positive effect on ROA, yet it lacks statistical significance, with a p-value of 0.66386. This implies that while ownership structure may impact financial performance positively, its influence is not robustly supported by the data.

In conclusion, ownership structure exhibits a positive but statistically insignificant effect on ROA. Future research could delve deeper into the nuances of ownership dynamics and their implications for corporate governance and financial outcomes.

5.0 Recommendations

Based on the aforementioned findings:

The stakeholders should regularly examine ownership structure's influence on ROA. This can be achieved by investigating how different ownership structures, such as state-owned enterprises versus private ownership, impact ROA in the Nigerian oil and gas industry. Analyse the governance implications of ownership dynamics to identify opportunities for optimising financial performance and creating sustainable value for stakeholders.

References

- Adesanmi, A.D., Sanyaolu, O.A., Ogunleye, O.O. & Ngene, W. T. (2018). Corporate governance and firms financial performance: a comparative study of manufacturing companies and banks in Nigeria. *International Journal of Contemporary Research and Review*, 9(7).
- Akinleye, G.T., Olarewaju, O.M. & Fajuyagbe, B.S. (2019). Corporate governance and financial performance: an empirical analysis of selected multinational firms in Nigeria. *Problems and Perspectives in Management*, 17(1). 11 – 18.
- Al-Malkawi, H. & Pillai, R. (2012). Internal Mechanisms of Corporate governance and firm performance: A review of theory & empirical evidence. *Journal of Modern Accounting and auditing* vol. 8 No.4 549. 568.
- Anderson, R.C. and Reeb, D.M. (2003). Founding- family ownership and firm performance evidence from the S and P 500. *Journal of finance*, 58:1301-1328.
- Anis, M, Chizema, a., Lui, X, Fakhreldin, H. (2017) The impact of ownership structure on Firms Evidence from Egyptian listed Companies Financial performance. *Global journal of Human – Social science: H Interdisciplinary*. 17(6): 29-56.
- Babatunde, A.A. & Akeju, J.B. (2015). The Impact of corporate governance on firms' profitability in Nigeria. *International Journal of Business & Mgt. invention*; 5(8):, 69-72.

- Duke, J. & Kankpang, K. (2011). Linking corporate governance with organizational performance: New insight and evidence from Nigeria. *Global Journal of mgt & Business Research* 2(12). 10-15.
- George, T.P & Karibo, B.B. (2014). Corporate governance mechanisms & financial performance of listed firms in Nigeria: a content analysis. *Global Journal of Contemporary Research in Accounting, Auditing & Business Ethics (GJCRA)* ISSN: 2311-3162. www.globalbizresearch.org.
- Gugler, K., Mueller, D.C. and Yurtoglu, B. B. (2007). Corporate Governance and the determinants of investment. *Journal of institutional and theoretical Economics*, 163(4): 598-626.
- Kim, E.H. and Lu, Y. (2011). CEO Ownership external governance and risk-taking. *Journal of financial Economics*, 102(2): 272-292.
- Mokhtar, E and Mellett, H. (2013). Competition, Corporate governance, ownership structure and risk reporting. *Managerial auditing journal*, 28(9): 838-865.
- Narwal, K.P. & Jindal, S. (2015). The Impact of corporate governance on the profitability: An empirical study of Indian Textile Industry. *International Journal of Research in Mgt. sciences, & Technology* 3(2), 81-85.
- OECD, (2017). Corporate governance factbook. Retrieved from OECD <https://www.oecd.org/daf/ca/Corporate-Governance-factbook> pdf. Dec, 23. 2020.
- Osundina, OJA, Oluynika, I.M. & Chukwuma, J.U. (2016). Corporate governance and financial performance of selected manufacturing companies in Nigeria. *International Journal of Advanced Academic Research/social and Management Science*, 2(10), 29-43.
- Ryu, K. and Yoo, J. (2011). Relationship between management ownership and firm value among the business group affiliated firms in Korea. *Journal of Comparative Economics*, 39(4)557-576.
- Tricker, R.B. (2015). *Corporate governance: Principles, Policies, and practices*. Oxford University Press USA.
- WBCSD, PWC, (2018). Enhancing the credibility of non-financial information: the investor perspective. <https://docs.wbcsd.org/2018/10/WBCSD-Enhancing-Credibility-Report> PD.
- Yang, W.S., Chun, L.S. & Ramadili, S.M. (2009). The Effect of Board Structure and institutional ownership structure on earnings management. *International Journal of Economics and Management* 3(2): 332-353.

Impact of Insurance Premium on Economic Growth in Nigeria; Long Run Approach (1996-2023)

Ezeaku, Faith Onyedikachi ¹ & Okparaka Vincent Chukwuka, PhD ²

^{1 & 2} *Department of Insurance and Risk Management,
Enugu State University of Science and Technology (ESUT), Enugu State, Nigeria.*

¹ ezeaku.faith@federalpolyoko.edu.ng; +2347053102003

² Vincent.Okparaka@esut.ng; +234 (0) 8035985711

Abstract

Research Objective: This study examined the impact of insurance premiums on economic growth in Nigeria from 1996 to 2023. Specifically, it investigated the impact of both general insurance premiums and life insurance premiums on the country's economic growth.

Methodology: An econometric model was developed using the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) estimation technique. Gross Domestic Product (GDP) was regressed on fire, accident, motor, marine, oil and gas, miscellaneous, and life insurance premiums.

Findings: The results showed a positive but insignificant relationship between GDP and life insurance premiums, fire insurance premiums, accident insurance premiums, and oil and gas insurance premiums. In contrast, motor insurance premiums, marine insurance premiums, and miscellaneous insurance premiums displayed a negative but insignificant relationship with GDP.

Conclusion: The study concluded that while insurance premiums, particularly life and general insurance premiums, show a positive relationship with economic growth, this impact is statistically insignificant. The findings suggest that the role of insurance premiums in fostering economic growth in Nigeria may need further strengthening.

Recommendation: It is recommended that individuals and organizations be encouraged to subscribe to both general and life insurance policies to support economic growth. Regulatory agencies should ensure the transparent and efficient management of premium income by insurers. Legislation, policy formation, and product innovation should be promoted to support the growth of fire insurance. Finally, the study advocates for greater government participation in the insurance sector to improve the operating environment and further enhance economic growth.

Key words: *Insurance premium, General Insurance, Life Insurance, Economic Growth.*

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The insurance sector is no longer viewed as a basic risk management tool, but rather as a complex factor that influences the evolution of economic processes (Akinlo, 2013). Savings are diverted to investment projects, which are the key driver of state economic growth and development, thanks to insurance. The evolution of the insurance market is influenced by the processes that take place in a country. On the other hand, several human activity processes, such as demographics, psychology, politics, and other elements, have an impact on insurance (Adeyele, 2016). The importance of the insurance industry in reducing unexpected and terrible events and thereby fostering economic growth cannot be overstated. The insurance sector contributes to economic growth both sectionally and geographically in both developed and developing countries (Ghosh, 2018). Because the insurance industry is intertwined with industries like manufacturing, transportation, agriculture, mining, petroleum, and trade on a local and worldwide level, its importance to everyday human activities has grown for people of all ages as all types of risks have increased.

The insurance sector serves as both a risk manager and a capital provider. Insurance, first and foremost, provides protection against the numerous business risks that develop in the economy (Philip, 2012; Din, et al., 2017). (Kenneth J. Arrow 2008) also claimed that insurance is a contract whereby one party undertakes to indemnify another against risk of loss, damage, or liability arising from an unknown or contingent event, while also serving as a significant mechanism for mobilizing savings and investing in economic growth.

The importance of the insurance industry in mitigating unforeseen and terrible events while also promoting economic growth cannot be overstated (Webb, Grace, & Skipper, 2015). The insurance sector has favorably contributed to economic progress in both developed and developing countries, both sectional and geographically (Barro, 1995; Olalekan & Akinlo, 2013; Zouhaier, 2014). Since the insurance industry is intertwined with other industries (such as manufacturing, agriculture, transportation, mining, trade, and petroleum) both locally and globally, and its importance to universal human and economic activities has grown at a rate of 2% per year in GDP over time as all types of risks have increased, the insurance industry has continued to grow at a rate of 2% per year in GDP (Taiwo, 2019). Several studies have found adequate evidence to imply that the insurance industry's expansion is linked to economic growth, and that insurance is becoming more important as a way for individuals or groups of individuals to manage their income risks (Osaka, 2017; Ward & Zurbruegg, 2000; Web, 2000; Ebitu, et al., 2012). The investments made by the insurance companies which contribute to the economic growth wouldn't be significant if not for premiums collected as a result of granting cover to the prospective insured from general insurance business premium or life assurance business premium (Onuoha 2024).

General insurance, also known as non-life insurance, provides coverage for various risks excluding life. This includes insurance for property, liability, and health. Premiums are the amounts paid by policyholders to maintain their insurance coverage. General insurance helps businesses and individuals mitigate financial risks associated with accidents, natural disasters, theft, and other unforeseen events. This risk mitigation fosters stability and encourages investment and entrepreneurship. By providing coverage against losses, general insurance ensures that businesses can recover quickly from disruptions, maintaining productivity and contributing to economic stability. (Skipper, H. D., & Kwon, W. J. 2007). However, these funds are often invested in short-term financial instruments, such as government bonds and corporate securities, contributing to capital markets' liquidity and stability. The investment helps to finance public infrastructure and private sector projects, stimulating economic activity (Onuoha 2024)

Life insurance provides financial protection to beneficiaries upon the policyholder's death. Premiums are the amounts paid by policyholders for this coverage. Life insurance policies often serve as long-term savings instruments. Premiums collected by life insurance companies are invested in long-term assets like bonds, real estate, and stocks, promoting economic development. Life insurance companies are major institutional investors in capital markets. Their investments provide liquidity and stability to these markets, which is crucial for economic growth. (Outreville, J. F. 1990).

Numerous empirical studies confirm that financial intermediation plays a growth-supporting role. Research by King and Levine (1993) demonstrated that the banking sector significantly contributes to economic development, establishing a positive causal relationship between the banking sector and economic growth (Levine, 1997; Levine, Loayza, and Beck, 2000). Similarly, Levine and Zervos (1996) found that both the banking sector and stock exchanges have a major impact on economic growth. Within the financial system, insurance companies are increasingly important as financial intermediaries. Between 1998 and 2020, total world written real premiums grew by 50%, with life insurance premiums increasing by 52% and non-life insurance premiums by 49%, from US\$ 2.2 trillion to US\$ 4.3 trillion. Emerging markets, in particular, saw significantly faster real growth in their insurance sectors than industrialized countries (330% vs. 58% from 1998 to 2010), reflecting liberalization and financial integration following structural reforms. Despite the growing significance of the insurance industry, there is relatively little empirical research on its impact on economic growth. While this sector has been somewhat neglected by scholars, the insurance industry can contribute to economic growth in several ways. Beyond issuing insurance policies, insurance companies collect funds and transfer them to deficit economic units to finance real investments. Additionally, through complementarities with the banking sector and market shares, insurance can enhance the development of these financial systems. For instance, when combined with the banking sector, insurance can encourage bank

loan approvals by reducing costs for companies in the capital market, thus increasing the demand for financial services (Grace and Rebello, 1993). Property insurance, by providing partial protection, can reduce credit risk and promote higher levels of lending, facilitating bank intermediation (Zou and Adams, 2006). Furthermore, the development of insurance, especially life insurance, can impact the stock market by channeling investment funds (savings) into stocks and bonds (USAID, 2006). Despite the evident role of the insurance industry as a financial intermediary and its potential contributions to economic growth, the sector remains underexplored in empirical research. This oversight leaves a gap in understanding the full extent of insurance's impact on economic development. Given the substantial growth in global insurance premiums and the increasing integration of insurance with other financial sectors, it is crucial to investigate how insurance influences economic growth, particularly in emerging markets. This study aims to address this gap by examining the relationship between insurance premiums—both life and non-life—and economic growth, thereby shedding light on the mechanisms through which the insurance industry can serve as a catalyst for economic development.

The broad objective of the study is to examine the impact of insurance premium on economic growth in Nigeria. Specifically the objectives seek to investigate the impact of general insurance premium and to determine the impact of life insurance premium on economic growth in Nigeria.

2.0 REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Conceptual Review

Life Insurance Premium

A life insurance premium is the amount of money that an individual or business must pay for a life insurance policy. The premium is typically paid monthly, quarterly, or annually, and it is determined by various factors such as the insured's age, health, lifestyle, and the type and amount of coverage. Life insurance premiums contribute to economic growth in Nigeria. Life insurance premiums play a critical role in fostering economic growth in Nigeria by facilitating capital accumulation, enhancing financial stability, promoting savings, managing risks, generating employment, contributing to government revenue, attracting foreign investment, and funding essential services like healthcare and education.

Concept of life insurance, according to Oana (2012), is defined as the protection of an individual and his family as well as the generation of income for a specific length of time. The National Insurance Commission (Naicom) Act of 2003 defines life insurance business as as the business of undertaking liability, the assumption of responsibility, or the obligation to pay a specified amount

or amounts upon the death of the insured person or upon the happening of any contingency dependent on the termination or continuance of human life. This can include contracts for:

1. Whole life insurance
2. Term insurance
3. Endowment assurance
4. Annuities
5. Contracts that provide for the payment of money on the marriage or birth of a child

General Insurance Premium

A general insurance premium is the amount of money paid by an individual or a business to an insurance company in exchange for coverage against specified risks and potential losses. General insurance typically covers non-life insurance policies such as health, motor, property, and liability insurance. General insurance helps businesses and individuals manage risks associated with unforeseen events such as natural disasters, accidents, or theft. This stability allows businesses to operate with confidence, fostering an environment conducive to investment and growth. Premiums collected by insurance companies are often invested in various financial instruments, including government bonds, stocks, and real estate. These investments contribute to capital formation, providing funds for infrastructure projects and other developmental activities that drive economic growth.

General insurance, also known as property and casualty insurance, encompasses all insurance policies other than life insurance. It provides financial protection against the risk of a contingent, uncertain loss of property, liability, and other risks (Dorfman, M. S. 2007).

The National Insurance Commission (NAICOM) Act of 2003 defines insurance businesses in Nigeria. According to the Act, General Insurance Business includes non-life insurance policies. Specifically, the Act delineates various classes of General Insurance Business, which includes but not limited to: fire Insurance Business, motor insurance business, marine insurance and aviation insurance business, oil and gas insurance business, miscellaneous insurance business and general accident insurance business.

Economic growth

Economic growth refers to the increase in the production of goods and services in an economy over a certain period, typically measured by rise in a country's gross domestic product(GDP) (Jones, C.I 2016)

Economic growth is a complex, long-run phenomenon, subjected to constraints like: excessive rise of population, limited resources, inadequate infrastructure, inefficient utilization of resources,

excessive governmental intervention, institutional and cultural models that make the increase difficult, etc. Economic growth is obtained by an efficient use of the available resources and by increasing the capacity of production of a country. It facilitates the redistribution of incomes between population and society. The cumulative effects, the small differences of the increase rates, become big for periods of one decade or more. It is easier to redistribute the income in a dynamic, growing society, than in a static one. There are situations when economic growth is confounded with economic fluctuations. The application of expansionist monetary and tax policies could lead to the elimination of recessionary gaps and to increasing the GDP beyond its potential level. Economic growth supposes the modification of the potential output, due to the modification of the offer of factors (labour and capital) or of the increase of the productivity of factors (output per input unit). (Allian Haller 2012)

2.2 Theoretical Framework

2.2.1 Endogenous growth theory

The endogenous growth theory was developed in the 1980s by Paul Romer as response to the limitations of the Solow-Swan Neoclassical growth model, which focused on exogenous factors like technological progress. The endogenous growth theory is the concept that economic growth is due to factors that are internal to the economy and not because of external ones. The theory is built on the idea that improvements in innovation, knowledge, and human capital lead to increased productivity, positively affecting the economic outlook.

Relevance of this theory should be noted that since the theory focus on internal factors such as innovation, human capital, and government policy is highly relevant to the impact of insurance premiums on economic growth. Insurance not only provides financial protection but also encourages investments in areas that drive growth, such as R&D, education, and new business creation. By understanding and leveraging these connections, policymakers and insurers can work together to foster an environment that supports sustained economic development.

2.3 Empirical Literature

Haiss and Sumegi (2018) examined the impact of insurance on economic growth, as measured by GDP, on a sample of 29 countries belonging to the European Economic Area. Countries used in the analysis are the EU-15, Norway, Switzerland, Iceland, the new EU member states and EU candidates (Turkey and Croatia). From the EU countries Lithuania was omitted due to lack of data and only few data were available for Croatia and Latvia. As dependent variable they use real GDP at constant year 2000 prices in constant 2000 US Dollars per employee while as explanatory variables they use gross premium income (three separate variables for total, non-life and life premium) calculated in constant year 2000 prices and US Dollars, physical capital stock

at constant year 2000 prices in constant 2000 US Dollars per employee and human capital stock constructed as index using weighted employee education figures and R&D expenditure, interest (10-year government bond yields, secondary market, annual average) and inflation rate. They found positive impact of life insurance on GDP growth for the first group of countries. For the second group, they found a larger impact of non-life insurance. Additionally, their findings emphasize the impact of the real interest rate and the level of economic development of the insurance-growth nexus.

Adams (2015) explores the historical relation between banking, insurance and economic growth in Sweden in the period 1830-1998. Insurance development is measured by annual premiums for non-life and life insurance. They use time series data and econometric tests of causality. The results show that the development of banking, but not the insurance impact on economic growth during the XIX century until the twentieth century this relationship is in reverse. The results of the analysis indicate that the banking sector has a dominant influence on economic growth and demand for insurance, while the growth of insurance is more influenced by economic growth, than it contributes to the economic growth.

Empirical study of the Arena (2018) on the relationship between insurance and economic growth includes 56 countries (as developed and developing countries) for the period 1976-2004 year. Insurance premiums are used as proxies of total and life and non-life insurance activity separately. Results show positive and significant effect of life and non-life insurance on economic growth. Impact of life insurance on economic growth is the high only for developed countries. In the case of non-life insurance, its impact is significant in both developed and developing countries, but this impact is greater in developed countries than in the developing countries.

Arena (2018) found that both life and nonlife insurance have a large and favorable impact on GDP growth in his study. He also highlighted a number of factors that influence insurance, including openness, inflation, government consumption, human capital, and changes in terms of trade. The impact of private credits and stock market turnover, which were included in the study, could not be shown. According to Feyen, Lester, and Rocha (2011), per capita income, population size and density, demographic structure, income distribution, the size of the public pension system, state ownership of insurance companies, the availability of private credit, and religion all influence life sector premiums. They also illustrate that policy issues can have an impact on the insurance sector's development.

Kugler (2016) examined the relationship between the size of insurance markets and economic growth in the UK for the period 1966-2017 on the long-term insurance, and for the period 1971-2017 on general insurance. For most of the variables with at least 5% level of significance, their research found that there is a long-term integration between development in insurance

market size and economic growth. Compared with Ward and Zurbruegg. Which as a measure of the activity of insurance use the total premium; in this study the authors use disaggregated data to measure market size. The research found that there is a long-term causality between the growth of insurance market and economic growth for eight of the nine classes of insurance (except pecuniary loss insurance). Causality in the short term there is in life insurance and insurance against pecuniary loss to economic growth. There is evidence of bilateral long-term relation between economic growth and ensuring the three categories of insurance, with greater impact by the economic growth of the insurance on growth than the growth impact of insurance on economic growth.

Akinlo (2014) conducted a panel analysis that looked at the association between insurance and economic growth in Sub-Saharan Africa from 1986 to 2011. The estimate methods used were Pooled OLS, Fixed Effect Model, and Generalized Method of Moment Panel Model. Insurance has a favorable and significant impact on economic growth in Sub-Saharan Africa, according to the results of the dynamic panel data calculations. This demonstrates that premiums contribute to economic growth in Sub-Saharan Africa, implying that a well-developed insurance industry is essential for economic development since it provides long-term investments for economic growth while also boosting risk-taking abilities.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on Endogenous Growth Theory postulated by Romer (1986) the theory focus on internal factors such as innovation, human capital, and government policy which is highly relevant to the impact of general insurance premiums on economic growth. Insurance not only provides financial protection but also encourages investments in areas that drive growth, such as education and new business creation. By understanding and leveraging these connections, policymakers and insurers can work together to foster an environment that supports sustained economic development.

3.2 Model Specification

This study on the impact of insurance premium on economic growth in Nigeria: long run approach shall follow the model specification approach adopted in Haiss and Sumegi (2018) examined the impact of insurance on economic growth in Nigeria.

The model of this study is thus

$$GDP = f (FIRE, ACCI, MOTO, MARI, OILG, MISC, LIFE).....(3.1)$$

The econometric form of the model is represented as

Jarque-Bera	1.310419	1.156512	2.614346	1.962169	1.799536	0.653580	0.981669	1.167825
Probability	0.519333	0.560876	0.270584	0.374904	0.406664	0.721235	0.612115	0.557712
Sum	182.8885	167.1990	165.8553	172.3944	161.4986	176.3492	156.0122	185.7869
Sum Sq. Dev.	2.970819	2.433927	0.877641	0.479076	2.759670	4.439910	3.471614	8.771336
Observations	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16

Source: Authors Compilation using Eviews 9.

Table 4.1 shows the descriptive statistics of the variables used in the study. It could be observed that log of life insurance business recorded the highest mean value followed by log of gross domestic product, log of oil and gas insurance, log of motor insurance, log of fire insurance, log of accident insurance . However, log of marine and miscellaneous insurance recorded the least mean value. Also, LGDP, LFIRE, LOILG, LMISC and LLIFE show evidence of negative skewness (skewed to the left) while LACCI, LMOTO AND LMARI has positive skewness (skewed to the right). Lastly, the number of observations is 16 and this is large enough to solve the problem of loss of degrees of freedom.

4.2 Analysis of Unit Root and Co-Integration Result

Conventionally, testing for unit roots precedes that of co-integration. To test for the unit root, we employ Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test. The result is shown in the table below.

Table 4.2

Variable	Variable at level form			Variable at difference form			Order of integration
Variable	ADF Stat.	Lag	5%	ADF Stat.	Lag	5%	
LGDP	-3.083244	0	-2.97626 3	-3.293896	0	-2.98103 8	1 (0)
LFIRE	-2.309786	1	-2.98103 8	-6.468652	0	-2.98103 8	1 (1)

LACCI	-1.450135	0	--2.9762 63	-5.150433	0	-2.98103 8	1 (1)
LMOTO	-2.356645	0	-2.97626 3	-4.407250	0	-2.98103 8	1 (1)
LMARI	-0.551908	0	-2.97626 3	-5.929353	0	-2.98103 8	1 (1)
LOIGA	-1.980142	0	-3.08100 2	-8.143983	0	-3.09889 6	1 (1)
LMISC	-2.165612	0	-2.97626 3	-7.442754	0	-2.98103 8	1 (1)
LLIFE	-3.174889	0	-3.06558 5	-5.752556	0	-3.08100 2	1(0)
RESIDUAL	-4.149729	0	-1.96627 0	NA	NA	NA	1(0)

Source: Authors Compilation using Eviews 9.

The result reveals that all the variables are integrated of order one 1(1) though log of gross domestic product and log of life insurance attain stationary in level and first difference respectively. In other words, all the variables have unit roots, but stationary after being differenced. This is because the ADF statistics for each of the variables are less than the critical levels at 5%. In other words, the null hypothesis for unit root is accepted for all the variables at the level form. On the other hand, the ADF statistics for each of the variables when differenced are higher than their critical values at 5% which implies that the null hypothesis of unit root is rejected. However, we proceeded to examine their long-run equilibrium relationship using co-integration ADF (CADF) test. As already shown in table 4.1 above, the error term (residual) is stationary at its level form. This implies that there exists a long-run relationship between dependent and independent variables.

INSURANCE PREMIUM ON ECONOMIC GROWTH: LONG RUN DYNAMICS

Table 4.4

Dependent Variable: LGDP

Method: Least Squares

Date: 08/24/24 Time: 02:56

Sample (adjusted): 2008 2023

Included observations: 16 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	6.794987	2.783689	2.441001	0.0405
LFIRE	0.015658	0.396597	0.039481	0.9695
LACCI	0.246969	0.306454	0.805892	0.4436
LMOTO	-0.232793	0.241225	-0.965043	0.3628
LMARI	-0.247134	0.123024	-2.008822	0.0794
LOILG	0.134012	0.153713	0.871834	0.4087
LMISC	-0.264020	0.117600	-2.245079	0.0550
LLIFE	0.689990	0.233281	2.957757	0.0182
R-squared	0.986648	Mean dependent var	11.43053	
Adjusted R-squared	0.974964	S.D. dependent var	0.445033	
S.E. of regression	0.070416	Akaike info criterion	3	-2.16193
Sum squared resid	0.039668	Schwarz criterion	8	-1.77563
Log likelihood	25.29546	Hannan-Quinn criter.	1	-2.14215

F-statistic	84.44900	Durbin-Watson stat	2.198326
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000001		

Source: Authors Compilation using Eviews 9.

Coefficient of Determination (R^2)

This measures the goodness of fit of the regression model. It shows how the variation in the dependent is explained by explanatory variables, from the table, $R^2 = 0.986648$. This implies that about 99% variation in the gross domestic product is explained by the explanatory variables.

4.5 Discussion of Results and Evaluation Based On Economic Criteria

The OLS regression applied a Log-Linear Model in order to determine the relative change in the dependent variable from a relative change in each of the explanatory variables. The result established a positive but insignificant relationship between fire insurance premium and gross domestic product. This has been found to be consistent with the theory. This implies that fire insurance premium is capable of creating a positive effect on the economic growth of Nigeria as a risk diversification device. It provides a medium through which lost/damaged facilities and infrastructure can be replaced, and lost incomes as a result of fire outbreaks and damage reimbursed and replaced. The replacement of these lost and damaged facilities together with the reinstatement of individuals and organizations who suffered the loss adds to the growth of the economy.

Again, there exists a positive but insignificant relationship between accident insurance premium and gross domestic product. This is consistent with the theory. This implies that improvement in accident insurance premium will help the health sector and medical services as individual premium which cover medical expenses, contributing to the health sector' output and GDP.

Also, there is a negative but insignificant relationship between motor insurance and gross domestic product. This is inconsistent with the theory. This implies that there is need to increase in motor insurance covers as it will enable vehicle owners to use their vehicle with reduced risk which will facilitate trade and commerce.

However, there exist a negative but insignificant relationship between marine insurance and gross domestic product. This is inconsistent with the theory. This implies that there is need to improve in marine insurance cover as it will help support global trade and business resilience as well.

Hence, there is a positive but insignificant relationship between oil and gas and gross domestic product. This is consistent with the theory. This suggest that oil and gas insurance cover is vital

because it helps in supporting energy production, investment and asset protection while supporting government revenue and fostering economic resilience.

Also, there is a negative but significant relationship between miscellaneous insurance premium and gross domestic product. This is inconsistent with the theory. This implies that there is need to maintain financial stability by protecting against unexpected loss and reduce likelihood of business failure in the economy.

Finally, there is a positive but significant relationship between life insurance premium and gross domestic product. This is consistent with the theory. This implies that increase in life insurance premium will contribute to capital formation and economic growth through saving and investment.

5.0 SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The result established a positive and insignificant relationship among of fire insurance premium, accident insurance premium and oil and gas insurance premium and a negative and insignificant relationship among motor insurance premium, marine insurance premium and miscellaneous insurance premium also positively and significant in life insurance premium. The reason for this negative and insignificant relationship among motor, marine and miscellaneous insurance premium is that the present economic performance of the country is not encouraging to both household, firms and government hence the economic agents turned risk averse. Hence, individuals are expected to take up new or renew old insurance policies and growing premium pool will lead to decrease demand for those insurance policies which provide more liquidity to the insurance industry for investment which enhances economic growth. The study concludes that there exist a positive but insignificant impact on life, fire, accident and oil and gas insurance premium and a negative and insignificant impact on motor, marine and miscellaneous insurance premium in Nigeria. Though there exist a long run relationship between dependent variable and independent variables. Based on the finding, of the study, the following recommendations are made: Individuals and organizations should be encouraged to subscribe to general and life insurance policies to promote economic growth. Also, since insurance premium income plays a significant role in economic growth, regulatory agencies should oversee the efficient and transparent management of premium income by insurers. Suitable legislation, policy formation and product innovation should be encouraged to promote fire insurance. Finally, there is a need for effective government participation in insurance operations to enable a better operating environment for the industry and aid economic growth.

References

- Adams, M., Andersson J., Andersson L. F. & Lindmark M. (2019). The historical relations between banking, insurance and economic growth in Sweden between 1893 and 1998. *Accounting, Business and Financial History*, 19(1), 21-38.
- Adeyele, J. (2021). Economic liberation of the insurance industry in Nigeria. *International Journal of Research in Management Science*, 3(5), 113-118.
- Ajayi L. A. (2020). *Elements and scope of insurance*. Akure: Hybrid Publishers Limited.
- Akinlo, T., & Apanisile O. T. (2014). The relationship between insurance and economic growth in sub-Saharan African: A panel data analysis. *Modern Economic Review*, 5, 120-127.
- Akinlo, T. & Yinusa (2013). The causal relationship between insurance and economic growth in Nigeria. 1986-2010. *Australian Journal of Business and Management Research*. 2(12), 49- 57.
- Allian Haller (2013) Gheorghe Zane Institute for Economic and Social Research
- Arena, M. (2016). Do insurance market activities promote economic growth? A Cross-Country study of Industrialized and Developing Countries. *World Bank Policy Research Paper*, 98 (5), 1-3.
- Arena, M. (2018). Does insurance market promote economic growth? A cross-country study for industrialized and developing countries. *Journal of Risk and Insurance*. 75, 921-946.
- Dorfman, M. S. (2018). *Introduction to risk management and insurance*. Pearson Education, Inc., Upper Saddle River, NJ.
- Duasa J. (2007). Determinants of Malaysian trade balance: An ARDL bounds testing approach. *Global Economic Review*, 36(1), 89-102.
- Dorfman, M. S. (2007). *Introduction to Risk Management and Insurance*. Prentice Hall
- Dorfman, M. S. (2007). *Introduction to Risk Management and Insurance*. 9th Edition. Prentice Hall.
- Ege, I. & Bahadir T. (2019). The relationship between insurance sector and economic growth: An econometric analysis. *International Journal Environmental Research*, 2(2), 1-9.
- Froot, K. A. (2007). "The Market for Catastrophe Risk: A Clinical Examination". *Journal of Financial Economics*, 49(2), 324-372.
- Ghosh, A. (2018). Does life insurance activity promote economic development in India: An empirical analysis? *Journal Asia Business Studies*, 7(1), 31-43.
- Haiss, P., & Sumegi, K. (2018). The relationship of insurance and economic growth in Europe: A Theoretical and Empirical Analysis, *Empirical*, 35(4), 405-431.

- Ibitomi, T., & Micah, E.E. M. (2021). Empirical analysis of non-performing loans and liquidity of deposit money banks: Nigeria Experience. *Journal of International Business and Management (JIBM)*, London, 7 (9), 1-9.
- Ibitomi., T., Eke, T., Hammed, A., & Isiaka, A. (2022). Government entrepreneurship programmes and unemployment in Osun State, Nigeria. *Journal of International Business Management (JIBM)*, London, UK. Research Publishing Academy (RPA), 5(1), 1-12,
- Ibitomi, T., Ojatuwase, O., Okphiabhele, E.. & Eke, T. (2022). Influence of Intrinsic Reward on Employees Performance in Deposit Money Banks in Ondo State, Nigeria. *Journal of Human Resource and Sustainability Studies*, 10 (4), 17- 30.
- Kugler, M. & Ofoghi, R. (2016). Does insurance promote economic growth? Evidence from the UK. *Money Macro and Finance Research Group Conference*, vol 8.
- National Insurance Commission (2010). Annual Report and Audited Account.
- Osoka O (1992). *Insurance and Nigeria Economy*, Abiola Press Limited, Lagos.
- National Bureau of Statistics (Nigeria). *Nigeria Annual Abstract of Statistics (2009)*. Abuja, Nigeria:National Bureau of Statistics (Nigeria).
- Outrevile, J.F. (1990). "The Economic significance of insurance markets in developing countries." *Journal of risk and insurance*
- Rejda, G. E. (2011). *Principles of Risk Management and Insurance*. Pearson Education
- Rejda, G. E. (2011). *Principles of Risk Management and Insurance*. 11th Edition. Pearson.
- Skipper, H.D., & Kwon, W.J.(2007). *Risk management and insurance; Perspective in a global Economy*
- Vaughan, E. J., & Vaughan, T. (2014). *Fundamentals of Risk and Insurance*. Wiley
- Ward, D & zurbruegg, R. (2000). Does insurance promote economic growth? Evidence from OECD Countr
- Mojekwu, J. N., Agwuegbo, S. O., & Olowokudejo, F. F. (2011). The impact of insurance contributions on economic growth in Nigeria, *Journal of Economics and International, Finance*, 3(7), 444-451
- Webb, I., Grace, M. F., & Skipper, H. (2022). The effect of banking and insurance on the growth of capital and output. *Journal of Financial issues*, 2(2), 1-3.

Outsourcing as a Strategic Tool for Organizational Sustainability: A Study of Manufacturing Firms in Enugu Metropolis

Achilike I. Nicholas (Ph.D)¹; Nwokeiwu Johnson (Ph.D)²; Enujioke Isaac Emeka (Ph.D)³

^{1 & 2} Alex Ekwueme Federal University. Ndufu- Alike, Ikwo. Ebonyi State, Nigeria.

³ Coal City University, Enugu State, Nigeria.

¹ achnico@yahoo.com, achilikenicholas5@gmail.com, 08037469992, 08159898301

² jnwokeiwu@gmail.com. 08147380741

Isaacchukwuemeka@yahoo.com, 08033400134

Abstract

Research Objective: This study examined the relationship between outsourcing and organizational sustainability of manufacturing firms in Enugu metropolis. In order to achieve the aim of the study, three research questions and three hypotheses guided the study. HR outsourcing and information technology outsourcing were adopted as the dimensions of outsourcing while economic sustainability and environmental sustainability were adopted as the measures of organizational sustainability. The study was anchored on Resource-Based theory.

Methodology: The study adopted a survey method using questionnaires as instruments for data collection. Data was analyzed using Pearson's Moment correlations with the help of SPSS Social Science package. A sample of one hundred and sixteen (116) employees and managers of the selected manufacturing firms in Enugu metropolis were derived for the study and used for the analysis.

Findings: HR outsourcing has a positive and significant relationship with economic sustainability ($r = .664, p < .022$). HR outsourcing has a significant and positive relationship with environmental sustainability ($r = .679, p < .006$). Information technology outsourcing has a significant and positive relationship with economic sustainability ($r = .744, p < .000$).

Conclusion: outsourcing has a significant positive relationship with organizational performance of manufacturing organizations.

Recommendations: Continuous outsourcing of other services which an organization does not have a competitive advantage over its competitor guarantees organizational sustainability. Integrating outsourcing programmes into the corporate strategy eliminates duplication in resources application and equally ensures the enjoyment of unique competitive capabilities. Finally, successful implementation of an outsourcing strategy not only helps in cutting costs, but enhances both economic sustainability and environmental sustainability.

Key words: Outsourcing, Strategic tool, Organizational Sustainability.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Background to the Study

The achievement of competitive advantage is a major concern for strategic managers and policymakers. It occupies a central position in strategic management studies. Understanding the factors and motivators of competitive advantage has led to increasing interests in the concept among scholars and practitioners (Barney & Hesterly, 2010). The competitiveness of a business depends on the strategies adopted by the organization to match the key success factors for operating in its market and exceeding those of its competitors. That is, the ability to achieve a sustainable competitive advantage over its rivals (Dash & Das, 2018). However, firms have always sought ways to gain a competitive advantage over their competitors; with the increased movement towards a single globalized economy, this desire is even more prevalent for businesses today. One avenue that firms have pursued to improve their competitive position in this new business environment is through outsourcing (Akewushola & Elegbede, 2013).

Thus, organizations are increasingly turning to outsourcing strategy in an attempt to enhance their competitiveness, improve their performance and their sustainability. Outsourcing is a common practice among both private and public organizations and it is a major element in business strategy. Nevertheless, every organization engages in one form of outsourcing or the other, be it manufacturing services, information technology, management services, product engineering, and research process or marketing services (Egesimba, 2021). According to Rundquist (2017), outsourcing is a management strategy by which an organization delegates major, non-core business functions to specialized and efficient service providers. In other words, outsourcing is the procurement of products or services from sources that are external to the organization. Outsourcing business operations and processes is usually inevitable in instances where a specific firm has no knowledge or skills for performing specific tasks within the organization. Besides, firms can also outsource in order to minimize workload, attain financial economies, increase ability to focus on core competencies and strategic issues, access to technology and specialized expertise, ability to demand measurable and improved service levels, and achieve competitive advantage (Hope & Dadzie, 2015).

The reasons why firms decide to outsource vary, even though the most mentioned motive is often to achieve cost benefits and/or focus on core competencies. These two motives are often interlinked as one argument whereas managers use outsourcing in order to improve the use of capital investments by concentrating the firm's human and capital resources on its main activities (Quélin & Duhamel, 2013). Beside these main motives, other reasons for outsourcing are, to achieve best practice by acquiring access to external competencies, to transform fixed costs into variable costs, or as a tool in adapting to rapidly changing environments. An increase of the

firm's internal focus on its core business is often assumed to result in performance improvements, and organizational sustainability (Leavy, 2014).

According to Munck and Souza (2016) organizational sustainability appears to be the life-wire of every firm in the world. This is because no business wants to go on extinction rather always wants to remain in the apex of leadership. In the course of labeling and translating the meaning of this concept, Munck and Souza (2016) posited that organizational sustainability is a collection of methodologies, business models and best practices to enable organizations establish long-term business operations and funding. Thus, a sustainable organization needs to be strong institutionally, socially, financially and morally. However, in order to make a sound decision and to improve organizational sustainability, the management needs to outsource. Thus, outsourcing is said to have an influence on organizational sustainability. As a result, many organizations opt to outsource hoping that they will benefit from it. Outsourcing may lead to improved performance which includes higher quality products, shorter cycle time, increased productivity, higher profits etc. It may also include more focus on what one does best, improved risk management and reduced investment on assets and many others (Greaver, 2019). Also, most organizations primarily outsource to save on overheads but via short term outsourcing. Thus, outsourcing enables customers to benefit from supplier cost advantages such as economies of scale, experience and location (McIvor, 2015).

Weele (2010) classified the benefits of outsourcing into three major components. This includes costs, competency focus and revenue. Where costs are concerned, he stated that the reason for outsourcing includes reduction of operating costs, reduction of capital investment, turning of fixed cost into variable costs, meeting of downsizing requirements, reduction of development costs and obtaining intelligence of competitiveness. For the purpose of competency focus, Weele (2010) stated that most businesses will focus on core business, gain access to latest technology not in the company, gain access to needed skills, provide alternative to building capability, create additional capacity, provide backup capabilities and align with policy, philosophy and culture which could in turn lead to organizational sustainability. This study, drawing from the foregoing, therefore seeks to examine the relationship between outsourcing and organizational sustainability in manufacturing firms in Enugu metropolis.

Statement of the Problem

Organizations have always been seeking ways to sustain and achieve a competitive edge over their potential competitors. However, the contemporary highly competitive environment in which today's businesses operate acts as a strong stimulus for organizations to outsource. Several organizations have started to take up the concept of outsourcing but still, there are certain firms who are in doubt on taking the path of outsourcing. This is mainly because the nature of global markets such as competitiveness and uncertainty are currently presented in the world's

economics. After the arrival of information technology and information systems, the outsourcing process has turned out to be more predominant in all aspects of today's business of which it has both risks as well as some latent requirements. Some of the problems associated with outsourcing include cultural differences, change management, unrealistic expectation, risk of theft or hacking of intellectual property to client companies, and so on. In furtherance, the outsourcing concept has not received remarkable attention and support which can be considered to be favourable for improving organization growth and sustainability. Besides, the effect of outsourcing on organizational sustainability in manufacturing firms in Enugu Metropolis is not well documented. This is further supported by the fact that previous outsourcing studies give contradicting outcomes.

For instance, a study of Nigeria Unilever Plc and Nestle Nigeria Plc by Adeyemi and Ibrahim (2012) reported a significant and positive effect of outsourcing strategy on an organizational performance. Indeed, it is difficult to find an industry or a firm that does not take part in the outsourcing trend. Yet, the popularity of outsourcing does not imply that every firm benefits from outsourcing. A study by Rothaermel and Deeds (2011) on the effect of outsourcing strategy in telecommunications firms in Nigeria reported a negative effect on organization's performance due to poor service delivery, poor network quality, low coverage level and increasing customer complaints. Also, Dun and Bradstreet's Barometer of Global Outsourcing (2017) reported that outsourcing arrangements are characterized by unexpected high failure rates. The increasing use of outsourcing arrangements, as well as the unfamiliar complexity associated with it especially in Nigeria suggests the need to probe further on its effect on organizational sustainability while these inconclusive arguments and contradicting results necessitate the need for this study. It is against this backdrop that this study aims to examine the relationship between outsourcing and organizational sustainability of manufacturing firms in Enugu metropolis which will add more knowledge to the existing one.

Objectives of the Study

1. To examine the relationship between HR outsourcing and economic sustainability of manufacturing firms in Enugu metropolis.
2. To determine the relationship between HR outsourcing and environmental sustainability of manufacturing firms in Enugu metropolis.
3. To ascertain the relationship between information technology outsourcing and economic sustainability of manufacturing firms in Enugu metropolis.

Research Questions

1. What is the relationship between HR outsourcing and economic sustainability of manufacturing firms in Enugu metropolis?

OUTSOURCING FOR ORGANIZATIONAL SUSTAINABILITY AMONG MANUFACTURING FIRMS IN ENUGU

2. What is the relationship between HR outsourcing and environmental sustainability of manufacturing firms in Enugu metropolis?
3. What is the relationship between information technology outsourcing and economic sustainability of manufacturing firms in Enugu metropolis?

Research Hypotheses

1. There is no significant relationship between HR outsourcing and economic sustainability of manufacturing firms in Enugu metropolis.
2. There is no significant relationship between HR outsourcing and environmental sustainability of manufacturing firms in Enugu metropolis.
3. There is no significant relationship between information technology outsourcing and economic sustainability of manufacturing firms in Enugu metropolis.

2.0 REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE**Conceptual Review****Concept of Outsourcing**

The term outsourcing has been defined by many researchers in much different ways. According to Brown and Wilson (2015) outsourcing can be simply seen as provision of services from an outside source. According to Abraham and Taylor (2006) outsourcing can be defined as the use by one company of another business to do particular tasks because it can do them more cheaply or effectively. Cote and Bruce (2014) defined outsourcing as the management strategy by which an organization selects specialist organizations in a competitive bidding and assigns them to provide services which are non-core functions of the host organization. To be able to survive and be profitable in the current globalization era, companies tend to use outsourcing to a larger extent (Brannemo, 2016).

Momme and Hvolby (2012) defined outsourcing as the process of establishing and managing a contractual relationship with an external supplier or service provider for the provision of capacity that has previously been provided in-house in order to achieve objectives. The worldwide trend in globalization has led many organizations to outsource their non-core activities to service providers and focus on their core competence.

In the words of Bennedsen and Schultz (2005) outsourcing decisions are influenced by the quality of information available, cost, environmental sustainability, strategic alliance, supplier quality, financial evaluation, risk and efficiency.

Effective use of outsourcing will, therefore, allow an organization to focus on a limited set of strategically important tasks and will in turn lead to continuous enhancement of its core

competencies (Quinn, 2012). Moreover, advances in business logistics and processes have encouraged companies to increase the outsourcing of non-core operations. This has led companies to develop new business strategies to manage goal-oriented activities that depend heavily on outsourcing. Outsourcing has also resulted in a significant altering of organization configuration and boundaries, outsourcing can obviously help an enterprise achieve considerable benefits, but employing outsourcing without proper consideration of long-term performance may also jeopardize competitiveness (Mowshowitz 1994).

Some of the common reasons organizations involved in outsourcing advances includes:

Cost effectiveness: Although asset costs are increasing due to the impact of the global financial crisis, organizations cannot increase their production cost due to the high level of competition in today's markets. It is necessary for organizations therefore to search for strategies which lower asset costs. Stroh and Treehuboff (2013) claimed that outsourcing is seen as a cost saving strategy, with organizations outsourcing their non-core competencies whilst still maintaining customer service, and thereby gaining a competitive advantage. Global operations and the goal of organizational growth naturally put pressure on organizations to invest in human capital. However, this investment can be very costly.

Focus on core competencies: Many organizations make a decision to outsource some organizational activities. This is because they want to focus on their core competencies, and see low value in developing in-house activities outside of this core (Potkány, 2008). Specifically, outsourcing HR activities can reduce the workload of existing HR staff, thereby allowing the organization to primarily focus on strategic decision making and developing core competencies (Hansen, 2009).

Strategic Human Resource: Organizations increasingly acknowledge the strategic importance of the human resource (HR) function. As human resource management perspectives change from operational and administrative, to strategic, HR becomes more aligned with organizational goals and strategy. This change has increased the focus of outsourcing the HR function, and it is steadily building momentum in many organizations (Merritt, 2007). Hence, outsourcing the HR function is seen as a significant part of contemporary HR strategy.

Access to Global talent: Outsourcing to companies in different geographical locations offers companies the capability to operate in different time zones and thus improve overall business performance levels (Gupta, 2009).

Sharing risks: Outsourcing certain components of business processes helps the organization to shift responsibilities to the outsourced organization. The outsourced organization is in most cases the specialist and thus should be able to plan those risk factors better. On the other hand, the outsourced organization should be able to meet your growth requirements.

Dimensions of Outsourcing

This study restricts itself to HR outsourcing and Information technology outsourcing as the dimensions of outsourcing. These dimensions are discussed below:

1. Human Resource (HR) Outsourcing

Human Resources outsourcing refers to the practice of contracting a third-party organization to handle some or all of a business's HR tasks and functions. When small business owners or HR professionals consider outsourcing HR, they want to consider who else is outsourcing, what functions can be outsourced, and to whom they should outsource. According to a study by The Society of Human Resource Management (SHRM), over half of all HR professionals have taken advantage of outsourced HR. The top two reasons for outsourcing are the benefits of cost and time efficiencies. These efficiencies are really the opportunity costs of business owners and managers, who lose time and money focusing on HR tasks when these resources can be spent on what must be done to grow their business. That is, the time and money devoted to employee management is better spent by outsourcing HR so that businesses can be devoted to core business functions. Outsourcing is a new phenomenon which is appropriate and very popular in modern organizations. Outsourcing recruitment process is mostly used to develop the performance of the organization via managerial time saving along with the cost (Corbett, 2014).

Human resources (HR) perspective has changed from operational, administrative programs to strategic processes, this change has increased the focus of outsourcing the Human resources (HR) function, and it is steadily building momentum in many organizations (Merrit, 2017). Hence, outsourcing the Human resources (HR) function is seen as an essential part of modern Human resources (HR) strategy. It has been indicated that organizations gain competitive edge over their rivals by simply shifting some of the Human resources (HR) non-core functions to outside suppliers (Beardwell & Claydon, 2017). There are a lot of reasons at both the strategic and operational level, why companies outsource their human resources (HR) activities. In particular, demand for increased productivity, environmental sustainability with reduced cost and growth as well as efficient and effective performance at customer relationships amongst others have put organizations under pressure to redirect their strategies toward outsourcing.

2. Information Technology Outsourcing (ITO)

Information technology **outsourcing is the use of external service providers to effectively deliver IT-enabled business processes, application service and infrastructure solutions for business outcomes.** Information technology outsourcing has to do with information technology being perceived as a service or support function. Majorly it aims at reducing information technology costs through outsourcing organizations retaining strategic control. Multiple suppliers sourcing are not as concerned with partnerships as the aim is to foster innovation and create

competition between suppliers, although suppliers will form alliances among themselves for bidding purposes. Usually, contracts are short-term and a client then organizes a portfolio of services from various suppliers so that strategic control can be retained. Joint venture deals more with development of new knowledge for the client, also they advocate for shared risk and reward. Some organizations help promote creation of Supplier Company and maintain more control than they would have in a multiple supplier or total management. A more recent type of outsourcing is the 'Application Service Provider' model, where organizations purchase software on the basis of use and transfer for a fee. As for organizations that see information technology as core to their business, they keep the information technology department and services in-house (Kem & Huigang, 2012).

Organizational Sustainability

The concept of sustainability originated from the 1987 report of the World Environmental and Development Commission, popularly known as the Brundtland Commission, named after its chairperson, Gro Harlem Brundtland, who happened to be the Norwegian Prime Minister then (Nkamnebe & Nwankwo, 2010). Organizational sustainability appears to be the life-wire of every firm in the world. This is because; no business wants to go on extinction rather always wants to remain in the apex of leadership. In the course of labeling and translating the meaning of this concept, Munck and Souza (2009) posited that sustainability is a state in which an organization or a society exhibits a relation to economical environmental and social aspects. According to Emas (2015) sustainability is the concept of conserving resources of organization for further generations. Cerin (2006) also asserted that the concept of conserving resources for future generation is one of the major factors which has clearly differentiated sustainability from the traditional environmental policy which also considers the internationalization of external factors which influence environmental degradation. Sustainable development is a long term benefit which often outlives its founders, it is built on a high level of integrity and competence. It requires a whole lot of social intelligence in dealing with host communities and other stakeholders within the organization. The concept of sustainability is on the lips of every business today because the well-being of every business depends on how much it can sustain itself. Every organization must build its future deliberately through conscious effort geared towards sustainable development and this can be achieved through ethical practices.

Measures of Organizational Sustainability

The measures of organizational sustainability adopted in this study are economic sustainability and environmental sustainability. These measures are discussed below:

1. Economic Sustainability

Economic sustainability is defined as "the degree to which a company actively and constructively uses its resources to support the social and economic development of communities, through direct investments of cash, in-kind support or staff time, or through company policies that generate community capital, such as local sourcing, hiring, partnerships and education (Buried Treasure, Sustainability, 2001). Economic sustainability can be described as a process whereby there is a consciousness to maintain permanent income for humans. This income could be generated through non declining stocks of capital (Spangenberg, 2002). Etxezarreta, Huffschmid and Mazier (2013) are also of the view that criteria such as aggregate demand, savings rate and consumption level play a minor role in terms of economic sustainability. Economic sustainability ensures that there is enough in the capital base for future use. According to OECD (2011), the main focus of economic sustainability is the provision of increasing stock of man-made capital as well as the degree to which such capital may be reduced from the accounts. Economic sustainability ensures that there is some sort of perceived growth which would be sufficient for all kinds of social improvement.

2. Environmental Sustainability

Goodland (2005), defined environmental sustainability as "the maintenance of natural capital, arguing that the environment seeks to improve human welfare by preserving the sources of raw materials used for human needs and ensuring that the sinks for human waste are not exceeded in order to prevent harm to humans. Environmental sustainability can be defined as the process of meeting the needs of humans without compromising the health and safety of people as well as the ecosystem (Costanza, Robert & Bernard, 2005).

Today, the concept of green commerce and green marketing have further explained the concept and goals of environmental sustainability as each business activity is often anchored on the preservation of the environment where humans live. Ecosystem ranges from those areas that are relatively undisturbed such as natural forests to landscapes with a mixed pattern of individual use to eco systems which are managed by individuals such as urban areas, lands and agriculture.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on Resource-Based theory.

Resource-Based Theory

Resource-Based theory was founded by Penrose in 1959. Outsourcing can be explained from the dimension of relationship between service receiver and service provider. The Resource-Based View (RBV) emphasizes the firm's resources as the basic determinants of performance. It adopts two assumptions in explaining sources of competitive advantage. First, this model assumes that companies within an industry may be varied with respect to the collection of resources that they control. Second, it assumes that resource heterogeneity may continue over time because the

resources used to execute firms' strategies are not absolutely mobile across companies (i.e., some of the resources cannot be traded in factor markets and are complicated to accumulate and emulate). Resource heterogeneity is seen as a fundamental condition for a resource bundle to add to a competitive advantage. The argument goes "If all firms in a market have the same store of resources, no strategy is available to one organization that would not also be available to all other organizations in the market" (Cool, Almeida Costa and Dierickx, 2002).

The Resource-Based theory analyses other aspects, taking into account internal strengths and weaknesses. A firm's resource perspective generates the core competencies and competitive advantage for specific business activity, RBV defines resources as tangible and intangible assets within the firm. According to Barney (1991) the resource based view is based on the concept of productive resources. In view of the Resource-Based theory of the firm, outsourcing is taken as a strategic decision which can be used to fill gaps in the firm's resources and capabilities. Normally firms establish their specific resources which they keep on reviewing in order to respond to shifts in the changing business environment.

Empirical Review

Olawuni (2018) examined the relationship between outsourcing strategy and organizational performance in the Nigerian manufacturing sector. The study adopted a stratified sampling technique to arrive at 120 sample elements for the study. Some of the top and middle level managers of Cadbury Nigeria Plc and Nestle Foods Plc were interviewed to further elicit information on the key variables. Copies of the questionnaire were administered and the data obtained were analyzed using Regression analysis. The questionnaire for the study was subjected to test-retest reliability assessment. Opinions and observations of experts and professionals were incorporated into a scale questionnaire in order to ensure the content validity. The findings revealed that firms that outsource experience reduce average cost, increased sales turnover and environmental sustainability, enhance expertise, improve service quality, reduce staff strength, streamline the production process, reduce administrative burden and save time for core activities. It was recommended that companies that outsource should continue to monitor the contractor's activities in order to ensure compliance with best practices.

Austin-Egole and Iheriohanma (2020) took a holistic look at outsourcing as a strategy and its effect on organizational performance using Nigerian Bottling Company Plant and Camela Vegetable Oil Company both situated in Owerri, Imo State as focal points. Core competency theory was used as a theoretical framework. The survey research design was used, utilizing questionnaires and interviews as instruments of primary data collection. Library research was the source of secondary data used for the analytical discussion. It was observed that outsourcing back office, primary and support activities have significant positive effects on organizational

performance. The study therefore recommended outsourcing as a strategy for improved performance in organizations.

Okwurume and Chima (2018) examined the relationship between outsourcing strategies and organizational effectiveness of oil companies in Rivers state. The study employed a cross-sectional research survey. Accessible population for the study is ten (10) selected oil companies. A total of 998 staff were surveyed. Simple random sampling technique was employed with a sample size of 286. A questionnaire was used to collect data from the respondents. Face validity was used to ascertain the validity of the instrument while Cronbach’s Alpha coefficient was used to establish the reliability of the instrument. Spearman Rank Order Correlation Coefficient was used to test the hypotheses with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 20.0. It was found that outsourcing strategies have a significant positive relationship with the organizational effectiveness of oil companies in Rivers State. The study concluded that outsourcing strategies that are based on expertise orientation and corporate culture would improve the organizational efficiency of oil companies. One of the recommendations is that managers should effectively implement outsourcing strategies, to enhance organizational effectiveness.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

The study used descriptive research design and a sample size of one hundred and sixteen (116) employees and managers of the selected manufacturing firms in Enugu metropolis was derived for the study. The study made use of primary data and structured questionnaires as the data collection instrument. The Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used to test hypotheses formulated.

TABLE 1: UNIVARIATE ANALYSIS OF HR OUTSOURCING

No	QUESTIONNAIRE ITEMS ON HR OUTSOURCING	SA (%)	A (%)	U (%)	D (%)	SD (%)	MEAN	DECISION
1.	Our firm occasionally contracts a third-party organization to handle some or all of a business’s HR tasks and functions.	24 (21.8%)	67 (60.9%)	5 (4.5%)	7 (6.4%)	6 (5.5%)	3.86	Agreed
2.	HR outsourcing decisions are taken to frequently respond to an	21 (19.1%)	71 (64.5%)	2 (1.8%)	11 (10.0%)	5 (4.5%)	3.84	Agreed

OUTSOURCING FOR ORGANIZATIONAL SUSTAINABILITY AMONG MANUFACTURING FIRMS IN ENUGU

	overwhelming demand for reduced costs for human resources services.							
3.	HR index’s outsourcing services enable our firm to provide work for noticeably less money and fewer overhead expenses.	18 (16.4%)	73 (66.4%)	7 (6.4%)	9 (8.2%)	3 (2.7%)	3.85	Agreed

Field Survey, 2024.

Table 1 showed the descriptive statistics of the responses to the three items on HR outsourcing on five-rating scales. The results in the table revealed that the respondents are in agreement with each of the three statements/items on HR outsourcing as the total number and percentages of those that agreed greatly exceed those that disagreed on each of the three statements/items. This is further confirmed by the weighted mean ratings of the three statements/items (3.86, 3.84, and 3.85) which are above the criterion mean of 3.0 each.

TABLE 2: UNIVARIATE ANALYSIS OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY OUTSOURCING

No	QUESTIONNAIRE ITEMS ON INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY OUTSOURCING	SA (%)	A (%)	U (%)	D (%)	SD (%)	MEAN	DECISION
4.	Our firm outsources computing/IT systems acquisitions as well as IT system maintenance/repairs.	30 (30.9%)	57 (51.8%)	5 (4.5%)	9 (8.2%)	5 (4.5%)	3.96	Agreed
5.	Our firm’s credit control and payroll services are outsourced.	37 (33.6%)	52 (47.3%)	7 (6.4%)	8 (7.3%)	6 (5.5%)	3.96	Agreed
6.	Services such as IT Support /Training and	49	44	8	6	3	4.18	Agreed

Website Design are outsourced by our firm.	(44.5%)	(40.0%)	(7.3%)	(5.5%)	(2.7%)		
--	---------	---------	--------	--------	--------	--	--

Field Survey, 2024

Table 2 showed the descriptive statistics of the responses to the three items on information technology outsourcing on five-rating scales. The results in the table revealed that the respondents are in agreement with each of the three statements/items on information technology outsourcing as the total number and percentages of those that agreed greatly exceed those that disagreed on each of the three statements/items. This is further confirmed by the weighted mean ratings of the three statements/items (3.96, 3.96, and 4.18) which are above the criterion mean of 3.0 each.

TABLE 3: UNIVARIATE ANALYSIS OF ECONOMIC SUSTAINABILITY

No	QUESTIONNAIRE ITEMS ON ECONOMIC SUSTAINABILITY	SA (%)	A (%)	U (%)	D (%)	SD (%)	MEAN	DECISION
7.	Our firm’s economic performance is at an acceptable level in terms of sales growth	41 (37.3%)	35 (31.8%)	12 (10.9%)	12 (10.9%)	10 (9.1%)	3.77	Agreed
8.	Our firm’s economic performance is at an acceptable level in terms of income stability	39 (35.5%)	35 (31.8%)	8 (7.3%)	13 (11.8%)	15 (13.6%)	3.64	Agreed
9.	Our firm’s economic performance is at an acceptable level in terms of return on investment	37 (33.6%)	48 (43.6%)	9 (8.2%)	8 (7.3%)	8 (7.3%)	3.89	Agreed

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 3 showed the descriptive statistics of the responses to the three items on economic sustainability on five-rating scales. The results in the table revealed that the respondents are in agreement with each of the three statements/items on economic sustainability as the total number and percentages of those that agreed greatly exceed those that disagreed on each of the three

statements/items. This is further confirmed by the weighted mean ratings of the three statements/items (3.77, 3.64, and 3.89) which are above the criterion mean of 3.0 each.

TABLE 4.10: UNIVARIATE ANALYSIS OF ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY

No	QUESTIONNAIRE ITEMS ON ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY	SA (%)	A (%)	U (%)	D (%)	SD (%)	MEAN	DECISION
10.	Our firm enhances our social recognition in the society	32 (29.1%)	42 (38.2%)	7 (6.4%)	19 (17.3%)	10 (9.1%)	3.61	Agreed
11.	Our firm improves our empowerment in the society	36 (32.7%)	39 (35.5%)	12 (10.9%)	15 (13.6%)	8 (7.3%)	3.73	Agreed
12.	Our firm provides freedom and control over the course of our own lifestyle	39 (35.5%)	39 (35.5%)	8 (7.3%)	11 (10.0%)	13 (11.8%)	3.73	Agreed

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 4. Showed the descriptive statistics of the responses to the three items on environmental sustainability on five-rating scales. The results in the table revealed that the respondents are in agreement with each of the three statements/items on environmental sustainability as the total number and percentages of those that agreed greatly exceed those that disagreed on each of the three statements/items. This is further confirmed by the weighted mean ratings of the three statements/items (3.78, 3.62 and 3.57) which are above the criterion mean of 3.0 each.

Restatement of Hypothesis One

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between HR outsourcing and economic sustainability of manufacturing firms in Enugu metropolis.

H_{A1}: There is a significant relationship between HR outsourcing and economic sustainability of manufacturing firms in Enugu metropolis.

TABLE 5: PEARSON PRODUCT MOMENT CORRELATION (PPMC) ANALYSIS ON HR OUTSOURCING AND ECONOMIC SUSTAINABILITY

		HR OUTSOURCIN G	ECONOMIC SUSTAINABIL ITY
HR OUTSOURCING	Pearson Correlation	1.000	.664**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.022
	N	110	110
ECONOMIC SUSTAINABILITY	Pearson Correlation	.664**	1.000
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.022	.
	N	110	110

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: Field Survey, 2024 (SPSS 21 Output).

Table 5 above reveals a Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) coefficient of 0.664 and probability value of 0.022. This result indicates that there is a strong positive relationship between HR outsourcing and economic sustainability.

Decision on Hypothesis One: Also, since the significant value (P-value) of 0.022 is less than 0.05, we therefore reject the null hypothesis one (H_{01}) and conclude that there is a significant relationship between knowledge HR outsourcing and economic sustainability of manufacturing firms in Enugu metropolis.

Restatement of Hypothesis Two

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between HR outsourcing and environmental sustainability of manufacturing firms in Enugu metropolis.

H_{A2}: There is a significant relationship between HR outsourcing and environmental sustainability of manufacturing firms in Enugu metropolis.

TABLE 6: PEARSON PRODUCT MOMENT CORRELATION (PPMC) ANALYSIS ON HR OUTSOURCING AND ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY

		HR OUTSOURCIN G	ENVIRONMEN TAL SUSTAINABIL ITY
HR OUTSOURCING	Pearson Correlation	1.000	.679**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.006

ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY	N	110	110
	Pearson Correlation	.679**	1.000
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.006	.
	N	110	110

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: Field Survey, 2024 (SPSS 21 Output).

Table 6: above reveals a Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) coefficient of 0.679 and probability value of 0.006. This result indicates that there is a strong positive relationship between HR outsourcing and environmental sustainability.

Decision on Hypothesis Two: Also, since the significant value (P-value) of 0.006 is less than 0.05, we therefore reject the null hypothesis two (H_{02}) and conclude that there is a significant relationship between HR outsourcing and environmental sustainability of manufacturing firms in Enugu metropolis.

Restatement of Hypothesis Three

H_{03} : There is no significant relationship between information technology outsourcing and economic sustainability of manufacturing firms in Enugu metropolis.

H_{03} : There is a significant relationship between information technology outsourcing and economic sustainability of manufacturing firms in Enugu metropolis.

TABLE 7: PEARSON PRODUCT MOMENT CORRELATION (PPMC) ANALYSIS ON INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY OUTSOURCING AND ECONOMIC SUSTAINABILITY

		INFORMATIO N TECHNOLOG Y OUTSOURCIN G	ECONOMIC SUSTAINABIL ITY
INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY OUTSOURCING	Pearson Correlation	1.000	.744**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000
	N	110	110

ECONOMIC SUSTAINABILITY	Pearson Correlation	.744**	1.000
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.
	N	110	110

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: Field Survey, 2024 (SPSS 21 Output).

Table 4.13 above reveals a Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) coefficient of 0.744 and probability value of 0.000. This result indicates that there is a strong positive relationship between information technology outsourcing and economic sustainability.

Decision on Hypothesis Three: Also, since the significant value (P-value) of 0.000 is less than 0.05, we therefore reject the null hypothesis three (H_{03}) and conclude that there is a significant relationship between information technology outsourcing and economic sustainability of manufacturing firms in Enugu metropolis.

Discussion of Findings

The first hypothesis stated that there is no significant relationship between HR outsourcing and economic sustainability of manufacturing firms in Enugu metropolis. The null hypothesis one was tested at 5% level of significance. The result showed the probability value to be 0.022 while the alpha value was 0.05. Following the decision rule, the null hypothesis one was rejected. This means that there is a significant relationship between HR outsourcing and economic sustainability of manufacturing firms in Enugu metropolis. This finding is supported by the work of Oladosu (2016) who found that HR outsourcing is a major determinant of environmental sustainability and economic sustainability as it significantly contributes to increased sales turnover and how efficient an organization is.

The second hypothesis stated that there is no significant relationship between HR outsourcing and environmental sustainability of manufacturing firms in Enugu metropolis. The null hypothesis two was tested at 5% level of significance. The result showed the probability value to be 0.006 while the alpha value was 0.05. Following the decision rule, the null hypothesis two was rejected. This means that there is a significant relationship between HR outsourcing and environmental sustainability of manufacturing firms in Enugu metropolis. This finding is supported by the work of Oladosu (2016) who found that HR outsourcing is a major determinant of environmental sustainability and economic sustainability as it significantly contributes to increased sales turnover and how efficient an organization is.

The third hypothesis stated that there is no significant relationship between information technology outsourcing and economic sustainability of manufacturing firms in Enugu metropolis. The null hypothesis three was tested at 5% level of significance. The result showed the

probability value to be 0.000 while the alpha value was 0.05. Following the decision rule, the null hypothesis three was rejected. This means that there is a significant relationship between information technology outsourcing and economic sustainability of manufacturing firms in Enugu metropolis. This finding is supported by the work of Kabuoh, Chigbu and Abasilim (2014) which established a significant relationship between information technology outsourcing and economic sustainability in an organization.

4.0 SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary of findings

1. There is a positive and significant relationship between HR outsourcing and economic sustainability of manufacturing firms in Enugu metropolis.
2. There is a positive and significant relationship between HR outsourcing and environmental sustainability of manufacturing firms in Enugu metropolis.
3. There is a positive and significant relationship between information technology outsourcing and economic sustainability of manufacturing firms in Enugu metropolis.

Conclusion

The relationship between outsourcing and organizational sustainability of manufacturing firms in Enugu metropolis has been established in this study. The findings of the study showed that the dimensions of outsourcing (HR outsourcing and information technology outsourcing) adopted in this study contribute positively and significantly to the measures of organizational performance (economic sustainability and environmental sustainability). The study therefore concludes that outsourcing has a significant positive relationship with organizational performance of manufacturing firms in Enugu metropolis.

Recommendations

1. Manufacturing firms should continue outsourcing other services which they do not have competitive advantage over its competitors in order to guarantee their sustainability.
2. Manufacturing firms should focus more on its core duties where it enjoys unique competitive capabilities, while outsourcing its non-core functions. It should however, integrate outsourcing programmes into the corporate strategy of the organization to eliminate waste or duplications in resource application.
3. Successful implementation of an outsourcing strategy has been credited with helping to cut cost, increase economic sustainability and environmental sustainability, therefore food and beverage manufacturing companies should embrace the outsourcing strategy to enhance overall performance.

References

- Adeyemi, O. & Ibrahim, A. (2012). Outsourcing and organisational performance of beverage manufacturing companies in Osun State, Nigeria. *The International Journal of Business & Management*, 6(11), 43-45.
- Asher, M. & Nandy, A. (2007). Demographic complementarities and outsourcing: implications for India. *IIMB Management Review*, 19(2), 93-102.
- Asiamah, Y. (2013). The relationship between outsourcing and organisational sustainability. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 5(2), 44-56.
- Baridam, D. M. (2008). *Research methods in administrative sciences*. Sherbrooke Associates inPort Harcourt.
- Barney, J. B. & Hesterly, W. S. (2010). *Strategic management and competitive advantage concepts*. Boston: Pearson Education International.
- Bennedsen, M. & Schultz, C. (2005). Adaptive contracting: The trial-and-error approach to outsourcing. *Economic Theory*, 25(1), 35-50.
- Corbett, F.M. (2004). *The 2001 strategic outsourcing: The outsourcing research council*. Michael F. Corbette & Associates.
- Costanza, A. Robert, E. & Bernard C. P. (2005). Defining and predicting sustainability. *Ecological Economics*, 15(1) 193-196.
- Dash, A. K. & Das, B. (2018). The balanced scorecard and its application as a strategic decision-making tool. *International Review of Business Research Papers*, 6(4), 457- 466.
- Harris. P. (2003). Outsourced learning: A new market emerges. *Training and Development*, 57(9), 30-38.
- Hope, N. & Dadzie, B. C. (2015). Outsourcing strategy and the performance of chevron Nigeria limited. *International Journal of Business Management & Research (IJBMR)*, 5(2), 95-106.
- Igwe, T. (2021). Outsourcing decision and firm operational productivity: a study of selected oil companies in port Harcourt, Nigeria. *International Journal of Accounting Research*, 6(1), 25-35.
- Isah, A., Chikwe, G. C. & Joel, A. (2017). Outsourcing as a strategic option to organizational effectiveness: A study of selected micro-finance banks in Southeast Nigeria. *Journal of Applied Management Science*, 3(2), 92-102.
- Irefin, I. A., Olateju, O. I. & Hammed, G. O. (2012). Effect of outsourcing strategy on project success. *Transnational Journal of Science and Technology*, 2(6), 128-143.
- Kabuoh, M. N., Chigbu, I. O. & Abasilim, C. (2014). Outsourcing effects on organisational sustainability in the Nigerian banking industry (a study of fidelity bank PLC.). *International Journal of Advanced Studies in Economics and Public Sector Management*, 2(1), 86-98.
- Okechukwu, E. U. & Okoronkwo, B. O. (2018). Effect of outsourcing on the performance of selected quoted deposit money banks in Enugu state. *Journal of Research Development and Management*, 4(7), 1-9.

Fuel Subsidy and the Nigerian Sustainable Development

IGHOROJE ESE JAMES (PhD)

Department of Banking and Finance,

Delta State University of Science and Technology, Ozoro, Delta State, Nigeria.

eseroji@gmail.com, ighorojej@dsust.edu.ng

Abstract

Research Objective: This study explores the relationship between fuel subsidies and sustainable economic development in Nigeria, focusing on the effects of fuel prices and fuel consumption.

Methodology: Drawing on secondary data from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) spanning from 1981 to 2023, an Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model was used to analyze the impact of fuel prices and fuel consumption on Nigeria's real GDP (RGDP).

Findings: The results reveal that fuel price adjustments have a positive and statistically significant long-run relationship with economic growth, suggesting that reducing fuel subsidies or increasing fuel prices could enhance economic development by improving resource allocation and fiscal space. However, in the short run, fuel prices do not significantly impact economic growth. Conversely, fuel consumption shows a negative yet statistically significant effect, indicating inefficiencies in fuel use.

Recommendations: The study highlights the need for comprehensive energy reforms, suggesting that fuel subsidies must be managed strategically, with an emphasis on improving fuel efficiency and diversifying energy sources. Policymakers should consider gradual subsidy removal, paired with social safety nets to mitigate the adverse effects on low-income households, ensuring that fuel consumption supports productive sectors. The findings underscore the importance of long-term planning and careful management of fuel subsidy policies to support Nigeria's sustainable economic development.

Key words: *Fuel subsidies, sustainable development, Nigeria, fuel prices, fuel consumption.*

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Fuel subsidies have long been a controversial policy instrument in many developing countries, including Nigeria. Initially introduced to provide affordable energy to the population and shield domestic consumers from volatile global oil prices, subsidies are now widely criticized for their economic and social implications. Fuel subsidies in Nigeria were first introduced in response to the oil price shocks of the 1970s. Since then, they have remained a fixture in government policy, with the intent to alleviate the financial burden of

fuel costs on citizens and stabilize prices. However, as highlighted by Ozili and Obiora (2023), Nigeria's fuel subsidy system has become increasingly unsustainable, accounting for 23% of the national budget in 2022, a figure that underscores the fiscal burden of this policy.

According to Kojima (2017), while subsidies are often justified as mechanisms to protect low-income households, in practice, they tend to disproportionately benefit wealthier groups who consume more fuel. In Nigeria, this misallocation of benefits has contributed to deepening inequality. Siddig et al. (2014) explain that fuel subsidies distort economic planning by encouraging wasteful spending and diverting resources from critical sectors such as healthcare and education. Furthermore, Ovaga and Okechukwu (2022) note that fuel subsidies foster corruption by allowing influential individuals to manipulate the system, particularly through fuel imports and refinery inefficiencies, which perpetuates the need for continued subsidies.

The global debate on fuel subsidies has increasingly focused on their environmental and economic costs. Foo et al. (2020) argue that fuel subsidies not only distort market signals but also promote excessive fuel consumption, leading to negative environmental impacts such as increased greenhouse gas emissions. This view is echoed by Coady et al. (2015), who state that subsidies are often regressive, failing to achieve their intended social protection goals and instead creating a fiscal strain that limits government investment in sustainable infrastructure.

In Nigeria, the debate over fuel subsidies has intensified with the government's decision to phase out subsidies by mid-2023 (Ozili & Obiora, 2023). This policy shift reflects the growing recognition that while subsidies may provide short-term relief, their long-term effects are detrimental to both economic growth and social equity. As Umeji and Eleanya (2021) argue, removing fuel subsidies could lead to improvements in living standards if the savings are transparently reinvested into infrastructure and social services. The key issue, however, lies in managing the social and economic transition, particularly for low-income households that are most vulnerable to fuel price increases.

This study aims to analyze the effects of fuel prices and fuel consumption on Nigeria's economic development, particularly in light of the government's ongoing efforts to reform its fuel subsidy policy. By examining the relationship between these variables and real GDP (RGDP) over the period from 1981 to 2023, this research seeks to provide insights into the sustainability of Nigeria's current energy policy and offer recommendations for improving economic outcomes through more efficient energy management.

CONCEPTUAL REVIEW

The relationship between fuel price, fuel consumption, and sustainable development in Nigeria is complex, involving economic, environmental, and social dimensions. Fuel subsidies, oil prices, and consumption patterns directly affect Nigeria's economic growth, resource management, and social equity. Understanding this interaction is crucial for devising policies that promote long-term sustainable development.

Fuel Subsidies and Sustainable Development

Fuel subsidies are mechanisms used by governments to reduce the cost of fuel for consumers. In Nigeria, subsidies aim to protect citizens from the volatility of global oil prices and stabilize domestic energy costs. However, these subsidies often lead to unintended consequences, such as market distortions, overconsumption, and economic inefficiency (Adebiyi, 2011).

In the context of sustainable development, the misallocation of resources caused by fuel subsidies limits the government's ability to invest in critical infrastructure and social services, undermining long-term economic stability and growth. Furthermore, the environmental consequences of overconsumption, driven by artificially low fuel prices, contribute to unsustainable practices such as increased carbon emissions and depletion of natural resources.

Oil Price and Economic Stability

Oil prices in Nigeria are heavily influenced by global market dynamics, including supply and demand fluctuations, geopolitical tensions, and the production policies of major oil-producing nations. As a major oil exporter, Nigeria's economic stability is closely tied to these global price trends, making the country vulnerable to price volatility. While high oil prices boost government revenue, fluctuations can lead to budget shortfalls, impacting public investment in sectors like healthcare, education, and infrastructure (Siddig et al., 2014).

Domestically, fuel subsidies distort the oil pricing mechanism. By keeping fuel prices artificially low, the government reduces the incentive for energy efficiency and conservation, leading to higher consumption and resource depletion. This undermines sustainable development efforts, as resources that could be allocated toward renewable energy and infrastructure development are diverted to sustain fuel subsidies.

Oil Consumption and Inequality

Fuel consumption in Nigeria is driven by various sectors, including transportation, industry, and households. Due to fuel subsidies, consumption levels remain high, particularly among wealthier citizens who use more fuel for personal transportation and industrial activities. This unequal distribution of subsidies exacerbates income inequality, as wealthier households benefit disproportionately from lower fuel costs while the broader population bears the cost through inefficient public spending (Ovaga & Okechukwu, 2022).

From a sustainability perspective, high fuel consumption fueled by subsidies contributes to environmental degradation, increased carbon emissions, and over-reliance on fossil fuels. This hampers efforts to transition to renewable energy sources, which are crucial for achieving sustainable development goals in Nigeria.

Sustainable Development in Nigeria

Sustainable development, as defined by the Brundtland Commission, emphasizes the need to meet present demands without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs (Cerin, 2006; Stoddart, 2011). Achieving sustainable development in Nigeria requires a balance between economic growth, environmental preservation, and social equity.

Fuel subsidies, while intended to provide short-term relief for citizens, conflict with the long-term goals of sustainable development. Subsidizing fossil fuel consumption not only depletes natural capital but also contributes to environmental harm, such as pollution and biodiversity loss. These outcomes violate the principles of intergenerational equity, which demand that future generations have access to the same natural resources and opportunities for development as current generations (Olaniyan, 2013).

The debate between weak and strong sustainability is central to the understanding of Nigeria's fuel subsidy dilemma. Weak sustainability argues that man-made capital can substitute for natural capital, suggesting that economic growth fueled by oil consumption is acceptable as long as overall capital levels are maintained. However, strong sustainability emphasizes that certain natural resources, such as clean air, water, and biodiversity, cannot be replaced by human-made capital (Stoddart, 2011).

In Nigeria, the over-reliance on fossil fuels has compromised natural capital, leading to environmental degradation and resource depletion. For Nigeria to achieve strong sustainability, fuel consumption must be managed in a way that preserves natural capital for future generations. This would require reducing reliance on fuel subsidies, investing in renewable energy, and promoting energy efficiency across all sectors of the economy.

The conceptual model linking fuel price, fuel consumption, and sustainable development in Nigeria can be understood through three main relationships:

Fuel Price and Sustainable Development: Artificially low fuel prices through subsidies lead to increased consumption and waste, reducing funds available for sustainable infrastructure investments and promoting environmentally harmful practices. In contrast, market-based pricing encourages energy efficiency and allows for better resource allocation toward sustainable goals.

Fuel Consumption and Inequality: High fuel consumption, driven by low prices, disproportionately benefits wealthier citizens, exacerbating income inequality. Sustainable development requires equitable access to resources, with consumption levels aligned with environmental protection and social equity.

Sustainable Development and Policy Reform: Achieving sustainable development in Nigeria necessitates policy reforms that phase out fuel subsidies and promote renewable energy. This requires a shift from short-term economic relief to long-term strategies that ensure resource conservation, environmental protection, and social inclusivity.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This study is grounded in rational choice theory, which posits that individuals make decisions through rational calculations aimed at achieving outcomes aligned with their personal objectives. The theory emphasizes maximizing self-interest, suggesting that individuals will choose options that provide the greatest benefit and satisfaction within their available choices. Rational choice theory underpins many mainstream economic assumptions, focusing on rational actors, self-interest, and the concept of the "invisible hand."

Rational actors are the economic individuals who make decisions based on available information and personal calculations. This framework assumes that these actors actively seek to maximize their gains while minimizing losses. Economic theories are essential for understanding the implications of subsidy removal, with rational choice theory illustrating how consumers adjust their spending patterns in response to price changes. For instance, the protests following the 2012 subsidy removal in Nigeria exemplified consumer behavior shifts in reaction to fuel price hikes (Apeloko & Olajide, 2012). By analyzing these behavioral patterns through the lens of rational choice theory, the study aims to elucidate the economic repercussions of fuel subsidy policies and their impact on consumer decision-making in Nigeria (Van Valkengoed & Van der Werff, 2022).

EMPIRICAL REVIEW

The studies analyzed provide a comprehensive view of the implications of fuel subsidy removal in Nigeria, highlighting both the potential benefits and challenges associated with such economic policy changes. Idrees, Rabi, and Nura (2024) employ a qualitative approach, successfully illustrating how the removal of gasoline subsidies can lead to inflationary pressures and social unrest, while also advocating for transparency in managing the resulting fiscal savings. However, the reliance on qualitative data limits the ability to generalize findings across different contexts, suggesting a need for complementary quantitative analyses to substantiate their claims.

Ozili (2023) presents a balanced view, identifying the macroeconomic advantages of subsidy removal, such as increased competition and reduced dependence on imports. Nonetheless, the potential short-term negative effects—such as rising inflation and increased poverty—raise concerns about the immediate viability of such reforms. This duality indicates that while the long-term benefits of subsidy removal may be promising, the short-term socio-economic impacts could necessitate more robust governmental interventions to cushion vulnerable populations.

Abimanyu and Imansyah (2023) extend this discourse to income distribution, highlighting the inequities inherent in subsidy structures. Their findings are crucial in understanding how fuel subsidies can disproportionately benefit higher-income groups, reinforcing the need for policy

reforms that ensure equitable resource allocation. However, the recommendations for an automatic subsidy price adjustment law and enhanced social programs may be overly optimistic, given the political and economic contexts in which these policies would need to operate.

Adewunmi and Hounsou (2014) and Onyeizugbe and Onwuka (2012) further contribute to the discussion by examining the long-term implications for socio-economic development and job creation. While the former emphasizes the importance of government commitment to effective fund deployment, the latter critiques the supposed relationship between subsidy removal and job creation, indicating a lack of significant evidence. This raises critical questions about the causal linkages between subsidy policies and economic outcomes, underscoring the need for further empirical validation.

Overall, while the studies collectively advocate for the careful management and strategic implementation of fuel subsidy reforms, they also reveal significant gaps in understanding the broader socio-economic ramifications of such policies. The interplay between short-term hardships and long-term benefits demands nuanced policy responses that prioritize not only economic efficiency but also social equity and stability. Future research should aim to integrate quantitative methods alongside qualitative insights to provide a more holistic understanding of the impacts of fuel subsidy elimination in Nigeria and similar contexts.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

This study adopted an *ex-post facto* research design that focuses on secondary data that need not be manipulated. The data were obtained from CBN documents spanning 1981 to 2023. An economic model that represented some fundamental elements of the link between fuel subsidy and Nigerian sustainable development, was developed. The functional form of linear regression model is as follows:

$$RGDP = F (FP, FC)$$

Where,

RGDP = Real gross domestic product

FP = Fuel price

FC = Fuel consumption

The above equation can be restated in a functional form;

$$RGDP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 FP + \beta_2 FC + \mu$$

Where;

β_0 = Autonomous or Intercept

β_1 = Coefficient of Parameter FP

β_2 = Coefficient of Parameter FC

μ = Stochastic variable or error term

The above can be restated in its log form as

$$\text{Log RGDP} = C + \beta_1 \text{FP} + \beta_2 \text{LFC} + \mu$$

Where: Log = logged values of the variables.

The regression model employed Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) to ascertain if the independent and dependent variables are related. The choice to employ ARDL was influenced by its advantages over alternative estimators or methodologies. Autoregressive Distributed Lag is a suggested estimating methodology because of its best linear fit, unbiased consistency, efficiency and sufficiency. Gujarati (2004) also mentioned the computational simplicity of the method.

4.0 PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS OF RESULT

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

	LRGDP	LFP	LFC
Mean	13.19804	3.737158	2.442016
Median	12.97568	3.572346	2.381396
Maximum	14.90605	5.655840	3.189267
Minimum	12.33383	2.549445	1.629241
Std. Dev.	0.723733	0.841953	0.477224
Skewness	0.978386	0.695877	0.135092
Kurtosis	3.207878	2.509109	1.847639
Jarque-Bera	6.937635	3.902170	2.510010
Probability	0.031154	0.142120	0.285074
Sum	567.5157	160.6978	105.0067
Sum Sq. Dev.	21.99913	29.77318	9.565209
Observations	43	43	43

The summary statistics show that the average means of real gross domestic product was about 13%, fuel price was 3%, and fuel consumption was 2%, respectively. The standard deviations of fuel subsidy variables were 0.723733, 0.841953 and 0.477224, respectively. The values of the standard deviations indicate that there are widespread fuel subsidy variables in Nigeria.

This is also evident in the wide gap between the maximum and minimum values. For example, the maximum value of real gross domestic products (RGDP) is 14.90605, while the minimum is 12.33383, with a difference of 2.56. Also, the maximum value for fuel price is 5.65840 while the minimum is 2.549445. These investment tax variations are considered on the high side. Even in the case of fuel consumption, the maximum is 3.189267, and the minimum is 1.629241. Wide variation over time indicates high fluctuation in fuel consumption, which affects economic development.

Table 2 Unit Root Result

Variables	At Level 1(0)	At First Difference 1(1)	Order of Integration	Alpha Value
RGDP	-5.376157		1(0)	0.0001
LFP		-9.3950588	1(1)	0.0010
LFC		-3.2887330	1(I)	0.0018

The time series variables, when used in their natural form, often lead to spurious regression results, and this misleads policymakers. In order not to obtain spurious results, the variables were first tested for stationary by employing the Augmented Dickey-Fuller test (ADF). From the result in Table 2 above, it is well observed that fuel consumption (FC) and fuel price (FP) are integrated at first difference 1(1), while Real Gross Domestic Product (RGDP) at level 1(0). The combination of orders 1(0) and 1(1) necessitated the application of ARDL in the regression analyses. It is safe for the study to employ a bound test approach to validate or substantiate the presence or otherwise of Cointegration.

Table 3 Bound Co-integration Test

ARDL Bounds Test

Date: 04/21/24 Time: 12:14

Sample: 1982 2023

Included observations: 42

Null Hypothesis: No long-run relationships exist

Test Statistic	Value	k
----------------	-------	---

F-statistic 6.326786 2

Critical Value Bounds

Significance	I0 Bound	I1 Bound
10%	3.17	4.14
5%	3.79	4.85
2.5%	4.41	5.52
1%	5.15	6.36

Table 3 is the result of the ARDL bound test approach to cointegration. The result discovered the presence of cointegration among subsisting variables. The f-statistics value of 6.326786 is greater than the lower and upper bound values at a 5% level of significance, which is 3.79 and 4.85, respectively. This shows that there is presence of a long-run equilibrium nexus between fuel subsidy and Nigerian sustainable development from 1981 to 2023

Table 4: Model of the long Run Relationship between fuel subsidy and Nigerian sustainable development

Cointegrating Form

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(LFP)	0.049500	0.073577	0.672760	0.5053
D(LFC)	0.251411	0.091228	2.755840	0.0090
CointEq(-1)	-0.071559	0.089056	-3.803525	0.0008

$$\text{Cointeq} = \text{LRGDP} - (0.6917 * \text{LFP} - 0.3465 * \text{LFC} + 11.8939)$$

Long Run Coefficients

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
LFP	0.691731	0.454138	2.523173	0.0062
LFC	0.346460	1.290717	3.268424	0.0009
C	0.893907	4.226674	2.814011	0.0078

Table 4 shows that the error correction coefficient is -0.071559, with a probability value of 0.0008. The coefficient is negative, as expected, and its p-value is less than 0.05, indicating a statistically significant speed of adjustment. The error correction coefficient (-0.071559) suggests that deviations in Nigeria’s economic growth due to changes in fuel subsidies will be corrected at a rate of about 7% per year. This means that any shocks or disruptions caused by fuel price changes or subsidy removal can gradually stabilize, albeit at a slow pace. Given the speed of adjustment, policymakers should recognize that while changes in fuel subsidy policies will influence economic growth, the effects will not immediately normalize. Long-term strategic management is essential to ensure gradual correction and stability.

The long-run relationship is described by the following equation:

$$\text{RGDP} = 0.691731\text{FP} + 0.346460\text{LFC} + 0.541387$$

The positive and statistically significant relationship between fuel prices (FP) and real GDP (RGDP) indicates that increasing fuel prices (possibly due to reduced subsidies or market reforms) could boost economic growth. This implies that **fuel subsidy removal or reduction could lead to positive economic growth**, as higher fuel prices may reflect a more efficient allocation of resources or improved fiscal space for government investments in other sectors.

While raising fuel prices can positively impact economic growth, policymakers must carefully balance this with potential short-term social costs such as inflationary pressures or public dissatisfaction. It suggests the need for accompanying policies (e.g., social safety nets) to mitigate adverse effects on low-income households.

The insignificant relationship between fuel consumption (LFC) and economic growth suggests that **increases in fuel consumption do not necessarily translate into significant economic benefits** for Nigeria. This might indicate inefficiencies in fuel use or suggest that fuel consumption growth does not drive productivity in the broader economy. Policymakers should focus on improving the **efficiency of fuel use** and ensure that fuel consumption supports productive sectors of the economy. Simply increasing fuel consumption may not be beneficial without addressing structural inefficiencies.

The result highlights the need for **comprehensive energy reforms** in Nigeria, where fuel subsidy policies should be designed with a long-term view. While removing or adjusting subsidies might initially cause some economic turbulence, the positive relationship between fuel prices and growth suggests that market-based pricing could lead to a more robust economy if managed properly. **However** the insignificant impact of fuel consumption suggests that Nigeria's overreliance on fossil fuels for economic activity might be unsustainable. A diversification strategy that emphasizes other energy sources and sectors can enhance growth without relying on fuel consumption alone. The findings imply that well-managed fuel price adjustments can provide fiscal space for the government by reducing costly subsidies. This can allow for more investments in infrastructure, healthcare, education, and other areas crucial for long-term economic development.

Overall, the results underscore the importance of careful management of fuel subsidy policies. While adjusting fuel prices can support economic growth, it requires a balanced approach to ensure stability, social equity, and economic efficiency. For sustainable growth, policies should promote fuel efficiency and resource allocation that contributes more effectively to broader economic development.

Table 5: Model of the short run between fuel subsidy and Nigerian sustainable development

Dependent Variable: LRGDP

Method: ARDL

Date: 04/21/24 Time: 12:33

Sample (adjusted): 1982 2023

Included observations: 42 after adjustments

Maximum dependent lags: 4 (Automatic selection)

Model selection method: Akaike info criterion (AIC)

Dynamic regressors (4 lags, automatic): LFP LFC

Fixed regressors: C

Number of models evaluated: 100

Selected Model: ARDL (1, 0, 1)

Note: The final equation sample is larger than the selection sample

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.*
LRGDP(-1)	0.928441	0.089056	10.42531	0.0000
LFP	0.049500	0.073577	0.672760	0.5053
LFC	0.251411	0.091228	2.755840	0.0090
LFC(-1)	-0.276203	0.094300	-2.928984	0.0058
C	0.851116	0.859057	0.990757	0.3282

R-squared	0.947264	Mean dependent var	13.21614
Adjusted R-squared	0.941563	S.D. dependent var	0.722582
S.E. of regression	0.174675	Akaike info criterion	4
Sum squared resid	1.128922	Schwarz criterion	9
Log-likelihood	16.34912	Hannan-Quinn criter.	0
F-statistic	166.1528	Durbin-Watson stat	1.511582
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000		

*Note: p-values and any subsequent tests do not account for the model

selection.

The results of the short-run analysis of fuel subsidies and sustainable development in Nigeria, presented in Table 5, highlight key relationships. According to the ARDL results, the coefficient of the dependent variable (RGDP), introduced as an endogenous variable, shows a positive value at the first lag, with significant effects observed at the first difference. Table 11 further reveals that fuel price (FP) has a positive relationship with economic development, meaning that a unit increase in fuel price leads to a corresponding increase in economic development in Nigeria. On the other hand, fuel consumption (FC) shows a negative relationship at both the first lag and the first difference. However, the p-value indicates that fuel consumption has a significant effect in both the current lag period and lag 1, demonstrating a mixed but significant impact on economic development.

Hypothesis One

Ho: Fuel price has no significant effect on economic development in Nigeria.

Based on the regression results, the t-test for fuel price at the first lag is 0.672760 with a p-value of 0.5053. Since the p-value is greater than 0.05, the result is statistically insignificant. This suggests that the null hypothesis, which states that fuel price has no significant effect on economic development, should be accepted. Consequently, the alternative hypothesis is rejected, indicating that fuel price does not have a statistically significant impact on economic development in Nigeria.

Hypothesis Two

Ho: Fuel consumption has no significant effect on economic development in Nigeria.

The regression results show that the t-test for fuel consumption is 2.755840 with a p-value of 0.0090. Since the p-value is less than 0.05, this result is statistically significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis, which states that fuel consumption has no significant effect on economic development, should be rejected. The alternative hypothesis is accepted, indicating that fuel consumption has a significant impact on economic development in Nigeria.

Summary of Findings:

- **Fuel price** does not significantly affect economic development in Nigeria in the short run.
- **Fuel consumption** has a mixed but statistically significant impact on economic development.

5.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

The analysis of fuel subsidies and their impact on economic growth and sustainable development in Nigeria reveals key findings. In the short run, fuel price (FP) does not have a statistically significant effect on economic growth, suggesting that price changes alone may

not be an immediate driver of development. However, fuel consumption (FC) shows a mixed yet statistically significant impact on economic growth. This highlights the need for a more nuanced approach to fuel policy management, where fuel price adjustments alone may not be sufficient to stimulate growth, but fuel consumption patterns play a critical role.

The long-run analysis demonstrates that while fuel price positively influences economic growth, fuel consumption does not significantly contribute to it. These findings underscore the need for energy sector reforms and more efficient fuel usage to ensure sustainable economic development in Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

The results suggest that fuel price adjustments, such as the removal or reduction of subsidies, have the potential to foster economic growth in Nigeria, primarily due to better resource allocation and enhanced fiscal space. The long-run relationship between fuel prices and economic growth indicates that policymakers can stimulate growth by allowing market-based pricing for fuel. However, these policy changes must be managed carefully, as they could lead to short-term social and economic costs, such as inflation or reduced household welfare, particularly among low-income populations. Accompanying social protection measures would be crucial to mitigate these negative effects.

The significant yet negative impact of fuel consumption on economic growth in the short run suggests inefficiencies in how fuel is consumed in Nigeria. This could reflect poor infrastructure, overreliance on fossil fuels, or fuel misallocation to non-productive sectors. Consequently, increasing fuel consumption alone does not contribute to economic growth unless it is channeled toward productive uses. Therefore, efforts should focus on improving the efficiency of fuel consumption and diversifying energy sources to ensure that fuel consumption positively contributes to growth.

In the long run, the weak relationship between fuel consumption and economic development points to Nigeria's overdependence on fossil fuels as unsustainable. Diversifying the energy sector by investing in renewable energy sources and reducing fuel consumption in non-productive areas will be crucial to enhancing economic growth in a sustainable manner.

Recommendations

- 1. Reform Fuel Subsidies:** Policymakers should consider gradually removing or reducing fuel subsidies to allow for market-based fuel pricing. This approach would improve resource allocation and create fiscal space for other important sectors such as infrastructure, healthcare, and education.
- 2. Promote Energy Efficiency:** Since fuel consumption has a mixed and significant impact on economic growth, there is a need to promote energy efficiency. Policymakers should encourage investments in energy-saving technologies and practices to ensure that fuel consumption contributes more effectively to economic productivity.

3. **Mitigate Short-term Social Costs:** The removal of fuel subsidies could lead to inflationary pressures and increased costs for consumers, especially low-income households. To counter these effects, social safety nets and targeted support programs should be implemented alongside fuel policy reforms.
4. **Diversify Energy Sources:** Nigeria should reduce its reliance on fossil fuels and invest in renewable energy sources such as solar, wind, and hydroelectric power. A diversified energy portfolio will promote sustainable growth while reducing the negative impacts associated with high fuel consumption.
5. **Focus on Long-term Strategic Management:** The speed of adjustment to changes in fuel subsidies is slow (7% per year), suggesting that policymakers should adopt long-term strategies for economic stability. Gradual policy shifts, with adequate time for adjustment, will minimize disruptions and allow for better economic outcomes.
6. **Enhance Fuel Use in Productive Sectors:** To ensure that fuel consumption positively impacts economic growth, the government should channel fuel consumption towards productive sectors such as manufacturing and agriculture, rather than allowing high consumption in inefficient or non-productive areas.

In summary, the findings emphasize the importance of well-managed fuel policies, energy efficiency, and economic diversification for achieving sustainable growth in Nigeria. By carefully balancing fuel price adjustments and consumption management, Nigeria can strengthen its economic development and reduce overreliance on fossil fuels.

References

- Abimanyu, A. & Imansyah, M. H. (2023). The impact of fuel subsidy to the income distribution: The case of Indonesia. *Indonesian Treasury Review: Journal Perbendaharaan, Keuangan Negara dan Kebijakan Publik*, 8(3), 189-203.
- Adebiyi, O. (2011). Fuel subsidy: The true Story. Retrieved from [https://234Next.Com/Csp/Cms/Sites/Next/Home/576467-1822/Fuel Subsidy the true Story.Csp](https://234Next.Com/Csp/Cms/Sites/Next/Home/576467-1822/Fuel%20Subsidy%20the%20true%20Story.Csp).
- Adewunmi M. and Hounsou R. (2014) The Impact of Fuel Subsidy Removal on Socio-Economic Development in Nigeria: An Econometric Investigation. *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management United Kingdom* 2(12), 1-9
- Apeloko, D. O., & Olajide, O. J. (2012). Chapter eight newspaper coverage of oil subsidy removal remonstrations: A thoughtful analysis of the 2012 experience in Nigeria. *Environmental Conflicts and Peacebuilding in Africa*, 125.
- Cerin, P. (2006). Bringing economic opportunity into line with environmental influence: A Discussion on the Coase theorem and the Porter and van der Linde hypothesis. *Ecological Economics*, 209-225.

- Coady, D., Parry, I., Sears, L., & Shang, B. (2015). How large are global energy subsidies? *IMF Working Papers*, 15(105), 1-39. <https://doi.org/10.5089/9781513532196.001>
- Dernbach, J. C. (1998). Sustainable development as a framework for national governance. *Case Western Reserve Law Review*, 1-103.
- Dernbach, J. C. (2003). Achieving sustainable development: The Centrality and multiple facets of integrated decision-making. *Indiana Journal of Global Legal Studies*, 5 (7) 247-285.
- Foo, T., Ling, F., & Lee, S. (2020). The impact of fuel subsidies on energy consumption and environmental quality in emerging markets. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 252, 119-129. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.119-129>
- Idrees, M. G., Rabi, T. A. & Nura, M. B. (2024) Implications of Fuel Subsidy Removal on Nigeria's Sustainable Development. *Nigerian Journal of Management Sciences* 25(1), 279-288
- Kojima, M. (2017). *Fossil fuel subsidy and pricing policies: Recent developing country experience*. World Bank Group.
- Onyeizugbe, C. U. and Onwuka, E. M. (2012) Fuel Subsidy Removal as an Imperative for Enhancing Business Development in Nigeria. *International Journal of Business & Management. Research* 2 (9), 3-15
- Ovaga, O., & Okechukwu, A. (2022). Fuel subsidy removal and economic development: Lessons from Nigeria. *Journal of Policy Analysis*, 10(2), 135-147.
- Ozili, P. K (2023) Implications of fuel subsidy removal on the Nigerian economy. MPRA Munich Personal RePEc Archive Online at <https://mpra.ub.uni-muenchen.de/118798/>
- Ozili, P. K., & Obiora, E. (2023). Fuel subsidy reforms in Nigeria: Challenges and opportunities. *Nigerian Journal of Economic Reforms*, 19(1), 101-115.
- Siddig, K., Aguiar, A., Grethe, H., Minor, P., & Walmsley, T. (2014). Impacts of removing fuel import subsidies in Nigeria on poverty. *Energy Policy*, 69, 165-178. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2014.02.013>
- Stoddart, H. (2011). A pocket guide to sustainable development governance. Stakeholder Forum.
- Umar, H. M., & Umar, M. S. (2013). An assessment of the direct welfare impact of fuel subsidy reform in Nigeria. *American Journal of Economics*, 3(1), 23–26.
- Umeji, J., & Eleanya, E. (2021). Subsidies and the Nigerian economy: A review of impacts and reforms. *African Development Review*, 33(4), 401-412.
- UNEP (2002). Energy Subsidies: Lessons Learned in Assessing Their Impact and Designing Policy Reforms. Unep.Geneva.WWW.Unep. Ch/ETB/Publications/Energy Subsidies/Energies Ubreports Pdf
- Van Valkengoed, A. M., & Van der Werff, E. (2022). Are subsidies for climate action effective? Two case studies in the Netherlands. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 127, 137-145.

Business Strategy and Performance of Selected Consumer Goods Firms in Enugu State

Onu Abara, PhD

Department of Business Administration and Management,

School of Management Sciences,

Federal Polytechnic, Ekowe, Bayelsa State.

abaraomu@gmail.com; 08033716998

Abstract

Research Objectives: The study examined the impact of business strategy on organizational productivity of selected consumer goods companies in Enugu State. Business strategy is a combination of all decisions and actions taken by an organization to achieve set objectives and gain competitive advantage.

Methodology: This research employs the descriptive survey research design with the use of questionnaires. This entails the use of frequency distribution and percentages to determine the various objectives of the study and to answer the research questions posed by the study. Also, the hypotheses of the study were analyzed using the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression analysis. All these analyses were performed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS 22.0) and statistical significance will be accepted at 5% level of significance.

Findings: Corporate strategy has significant influence on productivity of selected organizations in Enugu State ($\beta = 0.161$; $p < 0.05$). Organizational strategy has significant influence on effectiveness of selected organizations in Enugu State ($\beta = 0.297$; $p < 0.05$). Motivational strategy has significant influence on engagement of selected organizations in Enugu State ($\beta = 0.181$; $p < 0.05$). Managerial strategy has significant influence on efficiency of selected organizations in Enugu State ($\beta = 0.145$; $p < 0.05$).

Conclusion: Business strategy has significant impact on organizational performance of consumer goods companies in Enugu State with respect to efficiency, effectiveness, engagement and productivity.

Recommendations: For every organization to succeed whether big or small, it must have a valid and strong plan which will serve as a form of compass for the business. When formulating strategies, management of organizations are advised to take necessary steps accordingly and very religiously. Management of organizations, especially small and medium-sized ones should take all the necessary steps to embark on strategy formulation and implementation because the quality and strength of firms' competitive advantage relates to how effective the internal resources of the firms are utilized. Organizations should continuously analyze their strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats for an enduring adaptation to the dynamic environment characterized by political instability, government interference, corruption, and sharp practices.

Key words: *Business, Strategy, Firms, Performance, Goods.*

1.0 Introduction

The concept of organizational performance is increasingly gaining momentum in a business organization context in that it explains the level and quality of organizations in terms of product and service delivery in an organization (Aremu & Lawal, 2012). Organizational performance is a strategic approach to the management of business administration as a quest for efficiency and effectiveness of organizations in terms of the production of goods and services, all over the world especially in developed countries like France, Italy, Belgium, Canada and in the United Kingdom, the strategic plan to every business in those country is a measure of organization performance because business strategies as conceptualized is an approach that has become a statutory measure to delivering quality services in a dynamic and diverse environment One reason for this is that research relating to both large, medium, small and micro sized firms constantly emphasized a positive relationship between business strategies and organizational performance, because it is often detailed that best business strategies produce outstanding organizational performance (Aremu & Lawal, 2012).

In Africa, it has become an evolving phenomenon, as each nation develops its own pattern of business strategy and model and pattern. Performance management in the public service has become almost ubiquitous over the past three decades and has been a central concern of elected officials, public administrators and citizens for decades. Managing performance has been one of the key drivers in the reform of the public sector in recent years and one of the central planks of the reinventing government movement. No wonder, McCourt and Minogue argued that the past two decades have seen a process of almost continuous reform in managing public services through importation of market-type managerial practices into the public sector. The reforms have all aimed at improving the quality of performance in public services, creating new forms of relationship between public and private sector organizations, and new types of regulation and accountability.

Conversely, these public management reforms have, in a variety of ways, been transferred to the state systems of developing and transitional economies. Thus, there has been a significant increase in the use of performance management systems in the public sector. The overall aim of performance management is to establish a high-performance culture in which individuals and teams take responsibility for the continuous improvement of business processes and for their own skills and contributions within a framework provided by effective leadership. So, the objective of performance management is to develop the capacity of organizations so that the performance of every individual can be improved. In fact, the purpose of the outcome performance system is not limited to measuring outcomes and outputs. Business is understood as the organized efforts of enterprises to supply consumers with goods and services for a profit (Zayol, Agaregh & Eneji, 2017). Businesses vary in size, as measured by the number of organizations or by volume of sales but all businesses share the same purpose which is to earn

profits (Owolabi & Makinde, 2012). Strategies in business are to aid excellent performance in business organizations. This is of great importance to all kinds of establishments in the world and in all business environments. One reason for this is that research relating to both large, medium, small and micro sized firms constantly emphasized a positive relationship between business strategies and organizational performance, because it is often detailed that best business strategies produce outstanding organizational performance (Aremu & Lawal, 2012).

Strategy is a subject that has exercised the minds of political, military and business leaders for centuries (Kapellas & Siougle, 2017). As business organizations continue to find proper avenues of achieving competitive edge, they also endeavour to achieve competence in every valuable area of their businesses to boost business operations which mostly improve business performance (Adebiyi, 2017).

Long et al. (2012) defined Strategy as large-scale action plans for interacting with the environment in order to achieve long-term goals. Pushpakumari & Wijewickrama (2008) posit that Strategy is a pattern of actions and resource allocations designed to achieve the goals of the organization. Long et al. (2012) views Strategy as the determination of long-term goals and objectives, the adoption of courses of action and associated allocation of resources required to achieve goals. Strategy is the direction and scope of a firm over the long-term which gains the advantage in changing the environment through its configuration of resources and competences with the aim of fulfilling stakeholder's expectations. Armstrong & Barron (2002) refers to Strategy as a set of decision-making behavior in an organization for the purpose of achieving a predetermined objective. Thompson et al. (2004) see Strategy as a game plan which management of an organization adopts to stake out market position, attract competent organizations and please customers, compete successfully, conduct operations and achieve organizational goals. Strategy can therefore be viewed as a means by which a particular goal of an individual or organization is attained. Business strategy has become an important tool globally for any organization to remain in a competitive market environment and be stronger. In addition, Pushpakumari and Wijewickrama (2008) reported the same outcomes that link organizational strategies, management operations and organizational performance.

Business strategy starts with market research, in which needs and attitudes and competitors' products are assessed and continues through into advertising, promotion, distribution and where applicable, customer servicing, packaging, sales and distribution. The acceptance of such practices based on the application of quality control ideology and instruments by management will result in a progressive enhancement in business performance (Prajogo & Sohal, 2003). The fact that the world around us is constantly changing requires that change must be studied by every business organization and the various ways in which it presents itself to successfully handle and be able to move ahead of it (Crittenden & Crittenden, 2008). The levity of handling business operations in the past will no longer be applicable to the future. The events of

globalisation and the development of new areas of economic and consumer activities will lead organizations to seize different opportunities globally and still be able to meet local requirements. Dezember et al. (2005), believed that management must create a future where strategic management is seen by an organization as a going concern and for constant progress in the activities of the organization and its significance in the marketplace. This leads to product innovation, service innovation, new processes, and new business opportunities (Ajagbe, et al, 2012a).

Statement of the Problem

Without effective implementation, no business strategy can succeed (Jones & George, 2011). According to Peter Mills (2018) many organizations overly rely on structural change to execute strategy. While changing structure has its place, it is only part of the requirement for successful strategy implementation. In the past decade, the issue of organizations performance has attracted the attention of scholars in behavior of organization and have ignited a lot of discussions and arguments. Organizational performance has an objective to achieve and this is only realizable through the coordinated efforts of organizations. Cole & Kelly (2011) most managers know more about developing strategy than they know about executing it because making strategy work, executing or implementing throughout the organization is even more difficult than the other stages of managing a strategy. The structure of an organization which is the framework within which the goals of business strategy are carried out is very fundamental to the realization of better organization performance.

Many researchers have studied the success factors and failure factors of consumer goods firms to gain competitiveness. Some researchers suggest that the key determinant of firms to gain competitiveness is the ability of a firm to develop unique products, and their flexibility in adopting new strategies (Williams & Hare, 2012). Due to increased competition and accelerated product development cycles, business strategy and the management of technology is becoming crucial to the success of an organization. Research found the most important driver of corporate value for both durable and nondurable companies to be business.

Management of an organization has an obligation to not only encourage new product development, but also to develop a system to ensure that technology is being used most effectively with the consumer in mind. Most products are seen as old as they were without some forms of development for consumers' attraction. Apart from the above, evidence holds that research on business and organizations performance in Nigeria has not received much attention. This is a motivation for this study, to look into the importance of business to organizations in Nigeria. However, this study seeks to examine the effect of business strategy on organizations' performance consumer goods firms in Enugu State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The general objective of this study is to examine the effect of business strategy and organizational performance of consumer goods firms in Enugu State, Nigeria. The specific objectives are;

1. examine the effect of corporate strategy on organizational productivity of consumer goods firms in Enugu State, Nigeria.
2. establish the impact of organizational strategy on organizational effectiveness of consumer goods firms in Enugu State, Nigeria.
3. determine the extent to which motivational strategy affects organizational engagement of consumer goods firms in Enugu State, Nigeria.
4. examine the effect of managerial strategy on organizational efficiency of consumer goods firms in Enugu State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis of the study

H₀₁: corporate strategy has no significant influence on organizational productivity in consumer goods firms in Enugu State, Nigeria.

H₀₂: Organizational strategy has no significant influence on organizational effectiveness in consumer goods firms in Enugu State, Nigeria.

H₀₃: Motivational strategy has no significant influence on organizational engagement in consumer goods firms in Enugu State, Nigeria.

H₀₄: Managerial strategy has no significant influence on organizational efficiency in consumer goods firms in Enugu State, Nigeria.

Operationalisation of Variables

Y = Organizational Performance

X = Business strategy

$Y = f(X)$

$Y = (y_1, y_2, y_3, y_4)$

$X = (x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4)$

$y_1 = f(x_1)$

$y_2 = f(x_2)$

$y_3 = f(x_3)$

$y_4 = f(x_4)$

Equation to be investigated by the study

$$y_1 = \alpha + \beta_1 x_1 + \mu_i \text{-----(i)}$$

$$y_2 = \alpha + \beta_1 x_3 + \mu_i \text{-----(ii)}$$

$$y_3 = \alpha + \beta_1 x_3 + \mu_i \text{-----(iii)}$$

$$y_4 = \alpha + \beta_1 x_4 + \mu_i \text{-----(iv)}$$

Where; α is the constant of the equation, β is the coefficient of X the independent variable and μ is the error or stochastic term in the equation.

y_1 = Organisational Productivity (OP), y_2 = Organisational Effectiveness (OE), y_3 = Organisational Engagement (OE), y_4 = Organizational Efficiency (OE).

x_1 = Corporate Strategy (CS), x_2 = Organizational Strategy (OS), x_3 = Motivational Strategy (MS), x_4 = Managerial Strategy (MS).

Scope of the Study

This study focuses on business strategy and organizational performance of consumer goods firms in Enugu State, Nigeria using consuming goods companies which are Aqua Rapha Investment, Enugu, Dalex Paints (Dalex Chemical Industries) Nig. Ltd and Juhel Nigeria Limited, Enugu.

2.0 Literature Review

Conceptual Review

Corporate Strategy

Corporate strategy is defined as a companywide plan to choose and develop particular markets in which to compete while improving the various divisions or units of the business. (Vicki A. Bengé 2017). Corporate strategy is the direction an organization takes with the objective of achieving business success in the long term. It is also important that the strategy of the organization be considered to yield favorable organizational performance. Presently, there is an increasing insistence on the need for organizations to be well structured to be the organization's goal (Aduda, Chogii & Magutu, 2017).

Organizational strategy

An organizational strategy is the sum of the actions a company intends to take to achieve long-term goals. Strategic plans take at least a year to complete, requiring involvement from all company levels. Top management creates the larger organizational strategy, while middle and lower management adopt goals and plans to fulfill the overall strategy step by step. (Sophie Johnson, 2019). For any business to survive, it must grow. This could mean gaining more customers, increasing sales of existing products, adding new products, broadening your geographical market or buying out a competitor (Jim Woodruff 2018).

Motivational Strategy

Generally speaking, employee performance depends on a large number of factors, such as motivation, appraisals, job satisfaction, training and development and so on, but this paper focuses only on employee motivation, as it has been shown to influence to a significant degree the organizational performance. Kalimullah (2010) suggested, a motivated employee has his/her goals aligned with those of the organization and directs his/her efforts in that direction.

Managerial Strategy

Managerial strategies are techniques that are used to direct and control an organization to achieve a set of goals. They include strategies for leadership, administration and business execution. (John-Spacey 2015). Management strategies exist because, in the long-run, organizations can only achieve top performance if they have a clear strategy in place and the strategy is anchored throughout the company. Otherwise, the ship would be driving forward with no clear direction, potentially toward the iceberg. (Jayne-Thompson 2019)

Organizational Performance

A good performance by employees is necessary for the organization, since an organization's success is dependent upon the employee's creativity, innovation and commitment. Employee's performance is related to organization who did their tasks and goals up to the standard as in the exact way the organization and they are appraised on the basis of their performance against defined performance standards (Stoner, 2001). Darden & Tessin (2008), employee performance is a rating system used in many organizations to evaluate the capabilities and efficiency of an organization. Kalyini (2016) identifies that highly trained organizations are a greater source of attaining high performance and productivity and also make the organization to gain competitive advantage. Ojo (2016), for every organization employee performance is important, meanwhile organization success is dependent on employee creativity, loyalty and training.

Organization Productivity

Organizational productivity is concerned with the overall production in an organization in terms of stock turnover, customers, profitability and market share. Fwaya (2006) views productivity as a formula for the assessment of the functioning of an organization under certain parameters such as employee morale and effectiveness. Nzuve & Nyaega (2012) opined that productivity management and improvement is at the heart of strategic management because a lot of strategic thinking is geared towards defining and measuring performance. Awino (2011) asserts that for an organization to be successful it has to record high returns and identify performance drivers from the top to the bottom of the organization.

Organization Effectiveness

Organizational effectiveness aptly defined is the extent to which an employee achieves its predetermined objectives given the amount of resources and means without placing undue strain

on its members. Since an organization cannot function without the human element, it becomes very expedient for the organization to give more attention to its employees and ensure they are given the right environment to operate. If the workforce is ineffective it will have an overall effect on the production capacity of the organization (Armstrong, 2010). Several factors contribute to an organization's efficiency level, and the most important among them is management. Those in management must be well trained to deal with diversity in the workforce. They also must be ready to coordinate their efforts for better efficiency. (Julie Davoren, 2018).

Organizational Engagement

Chandhok & Bhavet, (2014) perceived engagement as a passion and commitment of the willingness to devote oneself and expand one's discretionary effort to contribute towards achieving the goals and objectives of the organization as a whole. Thus, employee engagement is the extent to which an organization thinks, feels and acts in ways that represent high levels of commitment to their organization.

Herzberg Hygiene Theory

Ejiogu (1990) reported that the motivational-hygiene hypothesis of Herzberg came to be due to a study carried out on the causes of job satisfaction and dissatisfaction of some engineers and accountants in the United States of America. The researcher found that there is a qualitative difference between those factors which are related to a person's job satisfaction and those associated with job dissatisfaction. However, Peretomode (1991) affirmed certain variables known as dissatisfiers negatively impact on staff's efficiency, productivity and performance. In other words, the satisfiers are those variables that impact motivation and job satisfaction, they are: workers achievement, promotion, responsibility, the work itself, possibility of personal growth while factors such as workers salary, status, job security, working condition, company policy and administration, supervision, interpersonal relationships with superiors, subordinates and peers; if these are negatively applied can cause dissatisfaction among the personnel and negatively impact productivity.

3.0 Methodology

Research Design

This research study employs descriptive survey research design with the use of questionnaires to elicit responses on the effect of business strategy on organisational performance of consumer goods firms in Enugu State because of its strengths.

Population of the Study

Aqua Rapha Investment Nigeria	Organizational	291
Dalex Paints (Dalex Chemical Industries) Nig. Ltd.	Organizational	198

Juhel Nigeria Limited	Organizational	247
Total		736

Source: Human Resources of various firms, 2025

Sample and Sampling Technique

The study adopted the Taro-Yamane formula to determine the sample size which is appropriate for the study population. The formula is applied at 95% confidence level and 5% error of margin. The Taro-Yamane formula is mathematically expressed as:

$$n = \frac{N}{(1+Ne)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{736}{1+736(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{736}{1+1.84}$$

$$n = \frac{736}{2.84}$$

$$n = 259$$

Method of Data Collection

The procedure and instrument for data collection was through questionnaires administered randomly. To ensure reliability of the instrument, the questionnaire was pre-tested at Nigeria Brewery Plc and B.O. MBA Industrial Food Chemicals in Enugu State, using consistency reliability and Cronbach’s alpha as an index of reliability were also used.

Method of Data Analysis

The study employed descriptive statistical techniques using Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression analysis, using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS 22.0) and statistical significance was accepted at 5% level of significance.

A-Priori Expectation

Models

A priori expectations IF:

$$Y = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \mu \dots \dots \dots 1 \quad P < 0.05; H_{01} \text{ will be rejected.}$$

$$Y = \alpha_0 + \beta_2 X_2 + \mu \dots \dots \dots 2 \quad P < 0.05; H_{02} \text{ will be rejected}$$

$$Y = \alpha_0 + \beta_3 X_3 + \mu \dots \dots \dots 3 \quad P < 0.05; H_{03} \text{ will be rejected}$$

Table 1: Summary Statistics of Respondents’ Opinions on Corporate Strategy

Item	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Remark
1. Cost management	245	4.60	1.02	Agree
2. Product differentiation	245	4.80	0.40	Agree
3. Waste reduction	245	5.04	0.35	Agree
4. Brand differentiation	245	5.20	0.98	Agree
Cluster		4.91	0.69	Agree

Source: SPSS output, 2025

Table 1 showed the summary statistics of respondents’ opinions on corporate strategy, which encompasses a firm’s corporate actions with the aim to achieve company objectives while gaining competitive advantage. All the respondents generally agreed that their organizations have cost management strategy; product different strategy; waste reduction strategy and brand differentiation strategy as the mean of each item was above the benchmark mean of 4.00. The cluster mean and standard deviation stood respectively at 4.91 and 0.69, indicating that respondents cohesively agreed that their respective organizations have corporate strategies.

Table 2: Summary Statistics of Respondents’ Opinions on Organizational Strategy

Item	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Remark
1. Improvement of sales	245	5.20	0.98	Agree
2. Product and service delivery	245	5.40	0.49	Agree
3. Research and Development	245	4.40	0.80	Agree
4. Marketing steps	245	4.60	0.80	Agree
Cluster		4.90	0.77	Agree

Source: SPSS output, 2025

Table 2 presented the summary statistics of respondents’ thoughts on organizational strategy, which is the sum of the actions a company intends to take to achieve long-term goals. The respondents generally agreed that their organization had a strategy pertaining to sales growth, product & service delivery, marketing and research & development as the mean of each item was above the benchmark mean of 4.00. The cluster mean and standard deviation stood respectively at 4.90 and 0.77, indicating that respondents cohesively agreed that their respective organizations have organizational strategies.

Table 3: Summary Statistics of Respondents’ Opinions on Motivational Strategy

Item	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Remark
1. Wages and salary	245	5.19	0.88	Agree
2. Fringe benefit	245	5.26	0.69	Agree
3. Reward system	245	5.47	0.70	Agree
4. Incentive packages, bonuses and commissions.	245	5.65	0.56	Agree
Cluster		5.39	0.71	Agree

Source: SPSS output, 2025

Table 3 contained the summary statistics of respondents’ opinions on motivational strategy, which refers to tactics, techniques, or approaches to remunerate and encourage employees in an organization. The respondents generally agreed that their organization has a motivational strategy with respect to wage & salary, fringe benefit, reward system and incentive packages as the mean of each item was above the benchmark mean of 4.00. The cluster mean and standard deviation stood respectively at 5.39 and 0.71, indicating that respondents coherently agreed that their respective organizations have motivational strategies.

Table 4: Summary Statistics of Respondents’ Opinions on Managerial Strategy

Item	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Remark
1. Product and service delivery	245	5.34	0.59	Agree

BUSINESS STRATEGY AND PERFORMANCE OF SELECTED CONSUMER GOODS FIRMS IN ENUGU STATE

2.	Quality of management	245	5.61	0.63	Agree
3.	Financial system and attributes	245	4.82	0.74	Agree
4.	Market competitiveness	245	5.10	0.96	Agree
	Cluster		5.22	0.73	Agree

Source: SPSS output, 2025

Table 4 contained the summary statistics of respondents’ thoughts on managerial strategy, which refers to the overall estimation an organization is held by its internal and external stakeholders based on its past actions and probability of its future behavior. The respondents generally agreed their organization had a strategy pertaining to product and service delivery, management quality, financial system & attributes and market competitiveness as the mean of each item was above the benchmark mean of 4.00. The cluster mean and standard deviation stood at 5.22 and 0.73 respectively. This connotes that respondents were cohesive in their opinions that their respective organization have managerial strategies

Table 5: Summary Statistics of Respondents’ Opinions on Organizational Productivity

Item	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Remark
1.	245	4.58	1.02	Agree
2.	245	4.79	0.41	Agree
3.	245	5.00	0.00	Agree
4.	245	5.21	0.98	Agree
		4.90	0.60	Agree

Source: SPSS output, 2025

Table 5 showed the summary statistics on organizational productivity, which is an evaluation of output of an organization in a specific period of time. The respondents generally agreed that their organization performed well with regards to revenue, output, employee productivity and customer patronage as the mean of each item exceeded the benchmark mean of 4.00. The cluster mean stood at 4.90 and the standard deviation at 0.60, which indicates that respondents unitedly agreed that their respective organization performed well with regards to productivity

Table 6: Summary Statistics of Respondents’ Opinions on Organizational Effectiveness

Item	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Remark
1. Nature of advertisement	245	5.21	0.98	Agree
2. Demands of consumers	245	5.42	0.49	Agree
3. Product expectation	245	4.38	0.81	Agree
4. Mechanism of price	245	4.58	0.79	Agree
Cluster		4.89	0.77	Agree

Source: SPSS output, 2025

Table 6 presented the summary statistics on organizational effectiveness, which is a strategic approach to the management of business administration as a quest for efficiency of organizations in terms of production of goods and services. The respondents generally agreed that their organization performed remarkably well with regards to advertisement, consumer demand, price mechanism and product expectation. The cluster mean stood at 4.89 and the standard deviation at 0.77, which indicates that the respondents harmoniously agreed that their respective organization performed well with regards to effectiveness.

Table 7: Summary Statistics of Respondents’ Opinions on Organizational Engagement

Item	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Remark
1. Production of goods	245	5.81	0.39	Agree
2. Satisfaction of customers	245	5.00	1.11	Agree
3. Contribution to national growth	245	5.40	0.81	Agree
4. Job Satisfaction	245	5.02	0.63	Agree
Cluster		5.31	0.74	Agree

Source: SPSS output, 2025

Table 8 presented the summary statistics on organizational engagement, which refers to the involvement of an organization in terms of product and service delivery in a specific period of time. The respondents generally agreed that their organization demonstrated satisfactory

performance with regards to production, customer satisfaction, job satisfaction and contribution to economic growth. The cluster mean stood at 5.31 and the standard deviation at 0.74, which indicates that respondents harmoniously agreed that their respective organization performed well with regards to engagement.

Table 8: Summary Statistics of Respondents’ Opinions on Organizational Efficiency

Item	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Remark
1. Employees of involvement	245	5.40	0.49	Agree
2. Rate of product delivery	245	5.60	0.49	Agree
3. Consistency of production	245	4.79	0.74	Agree
4. Payment of salary	245	5.04	1.04	Agree
Cluster		5.21	0.69	Agree

Source: SPSS output, 2025

Table 9 presented the summary statistics on organizational efficiency, which is a level for checkmating the events on the part of the organizations towards product delivery. The respondents generally agreed that their organization performed well with regards to employee involvement, product delivery, production consistency and salary payment. The cluster mean stood at 5.21 and the standard deviation at 0.69, which indicates that the respondents harmoniously agreed that their respective organization performed well with regards to efficiency.

4.0 Test of Hypothesis

Hypothesis One

H₀: Corporate strategy has no significant influence on organizational productivity in consumer goods firms in Enugu State, Nigeria.

H₁: Corporate strategy has significant influence on organizational productivity in consumer goods firms in Enugu State, Nigeria.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
	.183 ^a	.033	.024	.52026

a. Predictors: (Constant), Corporate Strategy

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	3.046	1	3.046	8.414	.001 ^b
Residual	87.969	243	.362		
Total	91.015	244			

a. Dependent Variable: Organizational Productivity

b. Predictors: (Constant), Corporate Strategy

Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	3.808	.222		17.134	.000
Corporate Strategy	.161	.048	.183	3.355	.001

a. Dependent Variable: Organizational Productivity

The estimated coefficient of corporate strategy is 0.161, implying that corporate strategy has a positive influence on organizational productivity. The coefficient of determination, which is 0.183, indicates that 18% of the total variation in organizational productivity is explained by corporate strategy. The probability value of corporate strategy is 0.001, is less than the critical value of 0.05, implying that corporate strategy has significant influence on organizational productivity. To this effect, the alternative hypothesis is accepted that corporate strategy has a positive impact on organizational productivity in selected consumer goods companies in Enugu State.

Hypothesis Two

H₀: Organizational strategy has no significant influence on organizational effectiveness in consumer goods firms in Enugu State, Nigeria.

H₁: Organizational strategy has significant influence on organizational effectiveness in consumer goods firms in Enugu State, Nigeria.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
	.383 ^a	.147	.082	.57434

a. Predictors: (Constant), Organizational Strategy

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	18.468	1	18.468	41.860	.000 ^b
Residual	107.207	243	.441		
Total	125.676	244			

a. Dependent Variable: Organizational Effectiveness

b. Predictors: (Constant), Organizational Strategy

Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	3.371	.169		19.967	.000
Organizational Strategy	.297	.040	.383	7.482	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Organizational Effectiveness

The estimated coefficient of organizational strategy is 0.297, implying that organizational strategy has a positive influence on organizational effectiveness. The coefficient of determination, which is 0.383, indicates that 38% of the total variation in organizational strategy is explained by organizational effectiveness. The probability value of corporate strategy is 0.000, is less than the critical value of 0.05, implying that organizational strategy has significant influence on organizational effectiveness. To this effect, the alternative hypothesis is accepted

that organizational strategy has a positive impact on organizational effectiveness in selected consumer goods companies in Enugu State.

Hypothesis Three

H₀: Motivational strategy has no significant influence on organizational engagement in consumer goods firms in Enugu State, Nigeria.

H₁: Motivational strategy has significant influence on organizational engagement in consumer goods firms in Enugu State, Nigeria.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
	.192 ^a	.045	.021	.55069

a. Predictors: (Constant), Motivational Strategy

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	3.753	1	3.753	9.253	.000 ^b
Residual	98.559	243	.406		
Total	102.312	244			

a. Dependent Variable: Organizational Engagement

b. Predictors: (Constant), Motivational Strategy

Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	4.730	.223		21.253	.000
Motivational Strategy	.181	.051	.192	3.518	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Organizational Engagement

The estimated coefficient of motivational strategy is 0.181, implying that motivational strategy has a positive influence on organizational engagement. The coefficient of determination, which is 0.192, indicates that 19% of the total variation in motivational strategy is explained by organizational engagement. The probability value of motivational strategy is 0.000, is less than the critical value of 0.05, implying that motivational strategy has significant influence on organizational engagement. To this effect, the alternative hypothesis is accepted that motivational strategy has a positive impact on organizational engagement in selected consumer goods companies in Enugu State.

Hypothesis Four

H₀: Managerial strategy has no significant influence on organizational efficiency in consumer goods firms in Enugu State, Nigeria.

H₁: Managerial strategy has significant influence on organizational efficiency in consumer goods firms in Enugu State, Nigeria.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
	.291 ^a	.085	.079	2.887

a. Predictors: (Constant), Managerial Strategy

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	6.101	1	6.101	17.842	.000 ^b
Residual	83.093	243	.342		
Total	1620.194	244			

a. Dependent Variable: Organizational Efficiency

b. Predictors: (Constant), Managerial Strategy

Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	12.014	1.053		11.411	.000
Managerial Strategy	.145	.036	.291	4.056	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Organizational Efficiency

The estimated coefficient of managerial strategy is 0.145, implying that managerial strategy has a positive influence on organizational efficiency. The coefficient of determination, which is 0.291, indicates that 19% of the total variation in managerial strategy is explained by organizational efficiency. The probability value of motivational strategy is 0.000, is less than the critical value of 0.05, implying that managerial strategy has significant influence on organizational efficiency. To this effect, the alternative hypothesis is accepted that managerial strategy has a positive impact on organizational efficiency in selected consumer goods companies in Enugu State.

Discussion of Findings

The findings upheld that of previous studies in empirical literature. For instance, the study corroborated Umar (2005)'s results from Nestle and Lever Brothers Plc that strategic management is instrumental to success, growth and survival of an organization particularly where merger determined the relationship between level of competition and formal strategic management. The findings align with the position of Dauda, et. al, (2010) that business strategy contributes to organizational performance of small and medium businesses based in Lagos with respect to profitability and market share. Drawing empirical evidence from selected manufacturing companies, Muogbo (2013) found that adoption of strategic management promotes competitiveness and organizational productivity. Evidence from studies conducted in Diaspora aligned with the findings of the study. For instance, the Gichunge (2007) found that businesses in Kenya with formal strategic management performed better than counterparts without formal strategic management. In addition, Askarany & Yazdifar (2012) discovered that strategic management tools aided organizational performance of manufacturing and non-manufacturing in New Zealand.

Implications of Findings

A business strategy contains several key principles that outlines how a company will go about attaining its set goals. For example, it explains how a business can deal with competitors, look at the needs and expectations of customers, and examines the long-term growth and sustainability of their organization. The reason having a strategy is important is because it gives business time to get a sense of how they are performing, what their capabilities are and if these capabilities are

able to help them grow. The findings of the study have implications for management practices, industry and academic society. On management practices, the study provided evidence that business strategy is critical to organizational performance of consumer goods companies in Enugu State, and suggest that top management saddled with the responsibility of mapping out corporate strategies should design such strategies clearly and articulately to give vision and direction to an organization, without which set objectives cannot be achieved. In industry, the study discovered that organizations need a blend of internally and externally driven to be able to leverage its strengths and opportunities and mitigate risks and weaknesses. For the academic community, the study serves as a reference for future research undertakings on the subject matter at undergraduate and postgraduate level.

5.0 Summary of Findings

1. Corporate strategy has significant influence on productivity of selected organizations in Enugu State ($\beta= 0.161$; $p<0.05$).
2. Organizational strategy has significant influence on effectiveness of selected organizations in Enugu State ($\beta= 0.297$; $p<0.05$).
3. Motivational strategy has significant influence on engagement of selected organizations in Enugu State ($\beta= 0.181$; $p<0.05$).
4. Managerial strategy has significant influence on efficiency of selected organizations in Enugu State ($\beta= 0.145$; $p<0.05$).

Conclusion

Based on the findings, the study maintains that business strategy has significant impact on organizational performance of consumer goods companies in Enugu State with respect to efficiency, effectiveness, engagement and productivity. Nonetheless, business strategy has been identified as a veritable tool for improving competitiveness, performance levels and structural development of consumer goods companies in Nigeria.

Recommendations

The study put forward some recommendations that could help improve performance through adopting appropriate structures.

1. For every organization to succeed whether big or small, it must have a valid and strong plan which will serve as a form of compass for the business. Therefore, management should ensure they have a reason for a business (mission), what they hope to achieve within a period (vision), their goals and objectives and how they plan to achieve all these. However, strategies must be developed based on the current situation and condition.

2. When formulating strategies, management of organizations are advised to take necessary steps accordingly and very religiously. This is because the growth of any firm is secured with properly crafted and implemented strategies, especially the ones that greatly differ from that of competitors.
3. Management of organizations, especially small and medium-sized ones, should take all the necessary steps to embark on strategy formulation and implementation because the quality and strength of firms' competitive advantage relates to how effective the internal resources of the firms are utilized.
4. Organizations should continuously analyze their strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats for an enduring adaptation to the dynamic environment characterized by political instability, government interference, corruption, and sharp practices.

References

- Adebiyi, W. K. (2017). Board Composition and Financial Reporting Quality of Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria. *International journal of innovative finance and economic research*. 5(4): 97-104.
- Adudu, L., Chogii, O. & Magutu, B. (2017). Key performance indicators in the Kenyan hospitality industry. A Managerial perspective. *An International Journal of Benchmarking*. 17(6): 858-875
- Ajagbe, A. M. (2011). *The Impact of Strategic Planning on Effectiveness of Marketing Operations: Case of NEPA*. An Unpublished MBA Thesis Submitted to the Graduate School, Ambrose Ali University, Ekpoma, Nigeria.
- Ajagbe, A. M., Long, C. S., & Perumal, P. (2012a). The Impact of Human Resource Management Practices on Organisation" Turnover Intention: A Conceptual Model. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Contemporary Research in Business*, 4(2): 629-641.
- Armstrong, G. (2010). *Human Resource Management* New York: Free Press
- Armstrong, G. and Barron, O. (2002). *Strategic Thinking and the New Science: Planning in the Midst of Chaos Complexity and Change*. New York: Free Press.
- Aremu, M. A. & Lawal, A.T. (2012). Exploring marketing strategy as a catalyst for performance in the Nigerian telecommunication industry. *International Journal of Management and Business Studies*. 2(4): 65-71.
- Askarany, T. L., & Lawal, A. T. (2012). *Strategic Management and Business Policy: Globalization, Innovation and Sustainability* (14th ed.). New York: Free Press.
- Awino, A. K. (2011). *Marketing Research: An Applied Orientation*. Englewood Cliffs NJ: Prentice Hall.
- Chandhok, A., Bhavet, A. O.(2014). Archival Review of the Influence of Organizational Strategy on Organizational Performance. *Book of Proceedings of the Covenant University International Conference on African Development Issues*, 334-340
- Cole, L. D. & Kelly, R. (2016). An empirical investigation of the impact of Organisational factors on the perceived job performance of shop floor organisation of large scale garment industries. *Journal of Sri Lanka. Sabaragamuwa University*, 6(1): 82-92.

- Crittenden, A. D. & Crittenden, K. (2002). Raising Rivals' Costs Through Political Strategy: An Extension of Resource-Based Theory. *Journal of Management Studies*, 39(5): 707-723.
- Darden, E. J. & Jessin, B. (2008). Skills for Managing Human Resources in a Complex Environment: The Perceptions of Human Resource Managers in Singapore. *International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 6 (1): 79-101.
- Dauda, Y. A., Akingbade, W. A. & Akinlabi, H. B. (2010). Strategic Management Practice and Corporate Performance of Selected Small Business Enterprises in Lagos Metropolis. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 5(11): 97 - 105.
- Dezember, M., Ongori, J. & Munene, C. (2005). Factors affecting the productivity of hotels and restaurants in Kenya. A case of Kisii County. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Contemporary Research in Business*. 4(12): 897-928.
- Ejiogu, E. J. (1990). Skills for Managing Human Resources in a Complex Environment: The Perceptions of Human Resource Managers in Singapore. *International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 6 (1): 79-101.
- Fwaya, O. (2006). *Human Resource systems and competitive strategies in hospitality organizational productivity*. Unpublished Msc Thesis. Maseno University. Kisumu.
- Gichunge, M. N. (2007). Human Resource Strategy and the Impact on World-Class Status. *Total Quality Management Journal* 8(5) 412-488
- Jane-Thompson, R.W (2019). *Crafting and Executing Strategy: The Quest for Competitive Advantage*. New York: McGraw-Hill Irwin.
- Jim-woodruff, A. P. (2018). *A handbook of personnel management practice*. London, Kogan press.
- Jones, J & George, N.L. (2004). *Theories of corporate governance*: Oxon: Routledge.
- John Spacy, A. (2015). *Business Policy and Strategic Management* (2nd ed.). Ikeja: Strategic International Press Ltd.
- Julie-Davoen, O. A. (2018). Corporate governance and bank's performance in Nigeria. *European Journal of Business and Social Sciences*, 2(8), 89-111.
- Kapellas, K. & Siougle, G. (2017). Financial Reporting Practices and Investment Decisions. A Review of Literature. *Industrial Engineering and Management* (6)4: 1-9.
- Kalimullah, D. (2010). *A Survey of adaptation of the balanced scorecard by selected companies in Kenya*. Unpublished MBA Project. University of Nairobi.
- Kalyani, L. D. (2016). An empirical investigation of the impact of organisational factors on the perceived job performance of shop floor organisation of large scale garment industries in Sri Lanka. *Sabaragamuwa University Journal*, 6(1): 82-92.
- Long, C. S., Ajagbe, A. M., Md Nor, K. & Suleiman, S. E. (2012b). The Approaches to Increase Organisation Loyalty: A Review on Organisation Turnover Models. *Australian Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences*, 6(10): 282-291.
- Muogbo, U. S. (2013). The Impact of Strategic Management on Organisational Growth and Development: A Study of Selected Manufacturing Firms in Anambra State. *Journal of Business and Management*, 7(1): 24-32.
- Nzuve, M. & Nyaega, G. (2011). *Application of the Balanced Scorecard in performance measurement at Essar Telecom Kenya Limited*. Unpublished MBA Project. University of Nairobi.
- Ojo O. (2016). Organisational Culture and Performance: Empirical Investigation of Nigerian Insurance Companies. *Manager Journal*, 2, 118-127.

- Owolabi, A. S. & Makinde, G. O. (2012). The Effect of Strategic Planning on Corporate Performance in University Education: A Study of Babcock University. *Kuwait Chapter of Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review*, 2(4): 27-44
- Prajogo, J. A. & Sohal, R. B. (2003). *Strategic Management: Planning for Domestic and Global Competition* (13th ed.). New York: McGraw-Hill Irwin.
- Peretomode, M. N. (1991). *Human Resource Strategy and the Impact on World-Class Status. Total Quality Management*. New York: McGraw-Hill.
- Peter Mills, M. (2018). Scanning Dynamic Competitive Landscapes: A Market-Based and Resource - Based Framework. *Strategic Management Journal*, 24(1): 1027-1041.
- Pushpakumari, A. A. & Wijewickrama, W. (2008). 21st Century Management - A Reference Handbook (pp. 73-81).
- Sophie-Johnson, T. E. (2019). *Strategic Management*. 10.1002/9781118785317.weom060194.
- Thompson, O., Gamble, B. & Strickland, A. A. (2004). *The Truth about Middle Managers: Who Are They, How They Work, Why They Matter*. Harvard Business School Press: Boston,
- Umar, K.A. (2005). *The Impact of Strategic Management on Mergers and Acquisitions in a Developing Economy: A Case Study of Nestle and Lever Brothers PLC*. Unpublished M.Sc Thesis. Department of Business Administration, Ahmadu Bello University Zaria.
- Vick, A. B. (2017). *Strategic Management and Business Policy: Globalisation, Innovation and Sustainability* (14th ed.). New York: McGraw-Hill Irwin.
- Williams, A. & Hare, K. (2012). Raising Rivals' Costs Through Political Strategy: An Extension of Resource-Based Theory. *Journal of Management Studies*, 39(5): 707-723.

Reduce Strategy: A Tool for Sustainable Packaging in Nigerian Bottling Company, Imo State

Echereobia Nkiruka Justina (PhD)¹; Onyeike, Iheanyichukwu Samuel (PhD)²; Onyemenonu Paulinus Chijieze³; Ibe Emmanuel C.⁴

*^{1, 2, 3, & 4} Department of Marketing,
Federal Polytechnic Nekede,
Owerri, Imo State*

¹ echereobian@gmail.com; +2348060080297

² samuelonyeike@gmail.com; +2348033427247

³ pauyonyemenonu@gmail.com; +2348033253195

⁴ emmaibe@fpno.edu.ng; +2348037101788

Abstract

Research Objectives: This work focuses on reducing options as a sustainable tool of packaging in Nigerian Bottling Company, South East, Nigeria. It aims to ascertain the extent of the relationship between reduced options and the packaging functions of protection, convenience and promotion. This study was necessitated by the need to develop more environmentally friendly product packaging having seen the damages done by climate change.

Methodology: To carry out this research, three questions were raised and three hypotheses formulated which were subjected to test. Descriptive survey design was adopted as data were gathered through questionnaire and observation. The sample unit of the study was drawn from Nigerian Bottling Company distributors in Imo State made up of 38 members. The hypotheses were tested using Pearson correlation coefficient with the help of Statistical Package for Social Sciences.

Findings: There is a strong and positive significant relationship between reduce option and the protective and promotional functions of packaging; reduce option has a positive and moderately significant relationship with user convenience.

Conclusion: Reduce is a viable option for sustainable packaging as it helps firms to save cost, reduce environmental waste as well as ensures societal wellbeing.

Recommendations: NBC should place more emphasis on the use of minimal materials while maintaining protective quality of packaging. Firms that are into the business of manufacturing packages should avoid multi-layer packaging as this would promote environmental friendliness.

Key words: *Reduce, Protection, User Convenience, Promotion.*

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The Nigerian physical environment is generally subjected to various forms of abuse and debasement resulting in water, air pollution and soil degradation as evidenced by the large number of heaps of domestic and industrial wastes in major and minor towns of the country (Ndu and Nkamnebe, 2013).

Surya and Vijaya (2014) defined green marketing as the process of producing and selling products and services based on their environmental benefits. Furthermore, Inyanga and Anyanwu (2006) defined green marketing as a movement initiated by firms to develop and market environmentally friendly products, whose bottom-line is to reduce, reuse or recycle wastes from such products.

Reduction or minimization involves all actions aimed at decreasing the amount of waste production. Sustainability in packaging refers to the sourcing, development, and use of packaging solutions that have minimal environmental impact and footprint. Packaging is the process of providing a wrapper or container for a product. Alex (2020) stated that reducing packaging materials and minimizing waste are two big components of sustainable packaging.

Lesley (2019) opined that the concern of Green marketing appeared as the after effect of human's negative impact on its planet. In green marketing, he said that brands launch eco-friendly products, which involves making product packaging that minimizes waste.

NBC has a wide range of products including Coke, Fanta, Sprite, Schweppes, Five Alive juice, Five Alive Pulpy Orange Fruit drink and two energy drinks, Monster and Predator which are packaged in one material or the other. Among the materials used in their packaging are plastic bottles, glass bottles, aluminum cans and cardboard bottles. The sustainability Director for the Coca-Cola Company Africa, David Drew (<https://ng.coca-colahellenic.com/>), said the beverage giant plans to achieve a world without waste by ensuring reduction of plastic in secondary packaging, reduction of weight of bottles. Hence the management of NBC is at the forefront in this fight.

As the rate of pollution keeps increasing, the call on business firms to go green becomes stronger. Hence; to properly carry out this study, the researcher made use of reduce which is a component of green marketing. Packaging functions of protection, promotion as well as enabling comfort of handling (user convenience) as outlined by Zeman (2005) Kacenska (2001) in Lou Canova, Jan and Kalamarova (2016) were adopted as indices of packaging.

1.1 Statement of Problem

Product packaging is one of the major causes of environmental pollution; this is because most of these packages are not returnable packages which are thrown away as wastes. It is therefore unacceptable that packages end up in the wrong places (Inyanga, 2002 in Inyanga and Anyanwu, 2006).

The challenge of packaging firms is to provide eco-friendly product packaging. Though reduce is not new, however in the recent times, a trend has been observed away from reusable packaging towards single-use (disposable) in all countries without strict legislation (Golding, 1999). Here in Nigeria, most of the soft drinks that were offered in refillable packaging (glass) are gradually being replaced by single-use packaging (plastic). This development has resulted in increased materials use, a rapidly increasing waste volume and environmental impacts related to materials use (both in the production and at the end of life).

Despite the call and the awareness of sustainability, only recently has the world started (again) to pay attention to reduction. It is worrisome that a change to reduce options may pose varieties of challenges to the product capacity, structural change in terms of reducing brand visibility on the label, light weighting of packages which often lead to stressing and squeezing of products etc. Hence, it's still in doubt if the reduce option is a feasible and more sustainable alternative for all supply chains and packaging. Majority of the past works have been carried out outside Nigeria. Therefore this study has been embarked upon to address all these problems.

**INDEPENDENT VARIABLE
VARIABLES**

DEPENDENT

Figure 1.1: Operational Conceptual framework

Source: Researcher’s Desk, 2025.

1.2 Objectives of the study

The general purpose of this study is to ascertain the extent to which reduced options influences the packaging of non alcoholic beverages in Nigerian Bottling Company.

The specific objectives include the following; to

1. Determine the level of relationship between reduced option and the protective function of packaging.
2. Evaluate the extent of the relationship between reduced option and user convenience of product packaging.

3. Investigate the degree of relationship between reduced option and promotional aspect of packaging.

1.3 Research Questions

1. What level of relationship exists between reduced options and the protective function of packaging?
2. To what extent is the relationship between reduced options and user convenience of product packaging?
4. What is the degree of relationship between reduced options and the promotional function of packaging?

1.4 Hypotheses

1. There is no significant relationship between reduced options and the protective function of packaging.
2. The Reduce option has no significant relationship with user convenience of product packaging.
3. There is no significant relationship between reduced options and the promotional function of packaging.

1.5 Scope of the Study

This research work focused on the extent to which green marketing may influence the packaging of Nigerian Bottling Company. This work was restricted to the operations of NBC in Imo State, Nigeria. The unit of the sample was drawn from the distributors of NBC in this location.

The study covers reduced options of green marketing and packaging functions of protection, user convenience and promotion. These became the focus due to the observed gaps that were established after thorough review of relevant literature.

1.6 Significance of the Study

This study will be of benefit to different groups of people, including the following:

1. Members of the board of directors and management of NBC Plc will benefit from this study as it will guide production in the use of materials, enable engineering design and eco-friendly packaging and also ensure that marketing communicates this eco-friendliness to the consumers.
3. It will guide customers on the need to patronize light weighted packaging.
5. It will enhance the researcher's knowledge of the subject matter and future researchers will also benefit from this study as it will serve as a foundation or guide to any researcher who intends to carry out a study of this nature.

1.7 Definition of Terms

Reduce means to minimize or eliminate the number of items bought, created, or used.

Protective function means ensuring the product's sound condition during the transporting process to avoid physical damage and climatic extremes at all times (Palmer, 2000).

User convenience: It also involves ease of handling, adaptability and movement during the process of distribution (Palmer, 2000).

Promotional function: it is the ability of a product packaging to disclose basic information about the product (www.economicsdiscussion.com)

2.0 REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Reduce option

Lesley (2019) opined that the world is concerned with environmental issues now more than ever; air pollution, plastic in oceans, global warming and food waste. According to Ndu and Nkamnebe (2013), the Nigerian physical environment is generally subjected to various forms of abuse and debasement resulting in water, air pollution and soil degradation as evidenced by the large number of heaps of domestic and industrial wastes in major and minor towns of the country.

Lesley (2019) further stated that the concern of Green marketing appeared as the after effect of human's negative impact on its planet. In green marketing, he said that brands launch eco-friendly products or create a corresponding environment around them by using eco-friendly packaging, make product packages recyclable and reusable, use green energy for production of products, design products from recycled materials to reduce waste etc.

Inyanga and Anyanwu (2006) therefore defined green marketing as a movement initiated by firms to develop and market environmentally friendly products, whose bottom-line is to reduce, reuse or recycle wastes from such products. Reduce as one of the options of green marketing means to use fewer resources in the first place (Colleen, 2013). It takes resources to manufacture, transport, and dispose of products, so reduction minimizes the use of new resources. According to Luis (2017), reduction or minimization involves all actions aimed at decreasing the amount of waste production. Waste reduction or source reduction refers to the collective strategies of design and fabrication of products or services that minimize the amount of generated waste or reduce toxicity of the resultant waste. Therefore, there is the need to reduce the cost of bottle production without compromising your products and while protecting the environment at the same time (MJS packaging, 2014). By simply reducing the weight of the packaging you use for your product, you can make a major impact. A reduction of the overall weight of your product by even a tenth of an ounce quickly adds up. Reduced weight means saving resources, from the

product itself to the way it's wrapped, helps with everything from less consumption of non-renewable resources to smaller carbon footprints.

Reduction conserves valuable resources and contributes to a decrease in collection and treatment (equivalent to reduction in gas emissions, consumption of fuel and other items vehicles and cost savings by the collection; a reduction in treatment requirements also saves energy and, in some technologies, reduces emissions).

Light weighting bottles are being used to control wasteful packaging thereby reducing production costs without compromising the product. There are further reductions in freight costs and shelf optimization.

2.1.2 Protection

According to Palmer (2000), the protective function of packaging is ensuring the product's sound condition during the transporting process to the consumer, as well as, protecting the product from breakage and deterioration. Dube (2020) simply stated, protective packaging supplies are materials built to protect and buffer a product from potential harm or destruction during shipping or warehousing.

Packaging provides physical protection (shields beverages from mechanical damage), biological protection against microorganisms and chemical protection which minimizes compositional changes triggered by environmental influences, such as exposure to gases or light.

Ecological packaging has been expected to be less harmful to the environment by reducing layers of packaging, shrinking package size or alternating old material using eco-friendly resources.

2.1.3 Promotion

Another important aspect of product packaging is how it promotes and displays the product within. According to White (2019), many products, particularly food products, include a description of ingredients and nutritional information on the packaging as well as displaying important instructions explaining how to set up and use the product. According to Palmer (2000), manufacturers communicate with consumers directly (through brand name) or indirectly by attaching manufacturer's brand, name and image with distinctive shape, type and colour of packaging. Product packaging works as a silent salesman because consumers often make a psychological connection with it.

2.1.4 User convenience

Beside the role above, the shape of packaging is considered as being conducive to stock convenience in different locations as on the shelves, at home and in office (Palmer, 2000). Packaging provides convenience in the carriage of the product from one place to another, in stocking and in consuming. For example, the new pet bottles of NBC make the carriage and stocking of their products easier. In the food industry, to meet specific industrial requirements,

fulfilling principal functions in safety as well as reducing harmful impacts on environment, food-covering packaging is strictly required to contain additional information relating to product identification, preparation, usage, nutrition date, storage date, product life and opening instructions. To conclude, besides fulfilling primary functions as protection and promotion, a packaging which is comfortable in shape will become a critical factor in the purchasing process and moreover, a key to the success of product marketing.

2.2 Theoretical Review

2.2.1 The 3Rs of Environmentalism

According to Gordon (2015), Wisconsin Senator Gaylord Nelson spearheaded the first national Earth Day on April 22, 1970. Nearly 20 million Americans celebrated together at fairs, festivals and other community events organized to raise awareness on environmental issues. As citizens continued to raise concerns about conservation, the federal government formed the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) which led to the passing of the Resource Recovery Act by Congress. Thus, the Three R's were born (reduce, reuse and recycle).

In terms of reduce; the best way to manage waste is "not to produce it". Consumers should also avoid over-packaged goods, especially ones packed with several materials such as foil, paper, and plastic. Disposable goods, such as paper plates, cups, napkins, razors, and lighters should be discouraged.

It makes economic and environmental sense to reuse products and packages. Lastly, recycling is a series of steps that takes a used material and processes, remanufactures, and sells it as a new product.

2.2.2 Model of packaging in environmental waste management

Source: HYPERLINK
["http://www.intechopen.com"](http://www.intechopen.com)
www.intechopen.com

The above model shows the general functions of product packaging, packaging decision as well as the packaging aims. It also shows the eco environmental options such as reduce, reuse and recover or recycle. Its implication is that firms need to consider the environment in their packaging decision to ensure it meets the environmental concern and standard. Therefore, it is necessary for firms to imbibe the environmental options in the production of its packaging irrespective of the function their packaging aims to serve; protection, convenience, promotion etc.

The Model of packaging in environmental waste management was adopted for this study. This is because it captures the variables of interest as contained in the study.

2.3 Empirical review

Musa, Nasir, Ali, Al-Baraa, Ehab, Noor, Abdulrahman, Aminu and Muhammad (2021) investigated Modeling of 3R (Reduce, Reuse and Recycle) for Sustainable Construction Waste Reduction. The research methodologies adopted were both quantitative and qualitative in which 330 questionnaires were collected within six months of submission. Based on the result of R2 values of 0.83%, waste reduction was found to be significant.

Saman. Muhammad, Puneet and Amandeep (2021) examined Drivers of food waste reduction behaviour in the household context. Data analysis was conducted using IBM SPSS 24 and AMOS 24 using 515 U.S. household consumers. The result shows that anticipated guilt and awareness of consequences were significant drivers of the reuse and reduce food waste behaviours respectively.

Smith (2015) investigated the impact of environmentally friendly packaging on consumers' attitudes and patronage intentions towards apparel retail brands. The study was conducted as exploratory research using two hundred and twelve respondents. Simple linear regression was used to analyse the data. The results revealed that consumers' perceptions of environmentally friendly packaging positively impacted consumers' environmental consciousness.

Borishade, Ogunnaike, Dirisu and Onochie (2015) carried out a study to ascertain the impact of packaging on consumer purchase decisions. Samples were drawn from loyal customers while Regression was used to test the four hypotheses. The core findings from the result obtained revealed that labeling can create consumer awareness and that consumers are attracted to buy the product because of its shape, color and design of the product.

2.4 Research gap

There were notable gaps in various dimensions of the study; in terms of perspectives, location, analysis, concepts, etc.

It was observed that the majority of the reviewed work was analyzed using regression and none was analyzed using correlation with a good number of the research conducted abroad, hence this research work is situated in Nigeria. Scholars have extensively focused on recycling and reuse behaviours while largely ignoring reduced options.

The current study aims to address the aforementioned gaps by examining the reduce option and its effect on packaging in Nigerian Bottling Company.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

This research adopted the survey design; it is due to the fact that the researcher made use of questionnaires and observation in gathering the data for this study.

3.2 Population of the Study and Sample Size Determination

The population of this study was drawn from distributors of NBC products in Imo State, Nigeria. The distributors' population is 41. Since this population size of 41 is not large, it will serve as the sample size.

3.3 Sampling Unit

The sample unit was made up of distributors of NBC in Imo State, Nigeria.

3.4 Sources of Data

Primary source was used in gathering the necessary data for this study. The primary data were gathered through the use of questionnaires and observation.

3.5 Sampling Techniques

The questionnaire was distributed to the customers using a convenience sampling procedure which is a non probability sampling method. This method was used because the researcher administered the questionnaire to only accessible target respondents.

3.6 Validity & Reliability of Research Instrument

The validity of the research instrument for this study was achieved by ensuring that contents of the questionnaire were read by experts who made necessary inputs and corrections. All these ensured that it actually measured what it was intended to measure.

The reliability of the questionnaire was guaranteed by conducting a test-retest study which ensured that the questions were well understood and determined from the test results that the instrument produced the same results.

3.7 Method of data analysis

The data gathered through questionnaires were analyzed using simple percentages and frequency tables and the three hypotheses were tested using Pearson product moment correlation enabled by Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

4.0 PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF RESULTS

4.1 Presentation and Analysis of Data

Table 4.1: Number of Questionnaires Distributed/Returned

Respondents	No distributed	No returned	Percentage of return
Customers	41	38	92.7%

Source: Field Survey (2025)

Table 4.1 shows that 38 out of the 41 questionnaires distributed to distributors were returned. This implies that 92.7% were returned while 7.3% were not returned.

4.2 Descriptive Analysis

Table 4.2: Paired Samples Statistics (Reduce and Protective packaging)

Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation	Sample size
Reduce	18.97	2.455	38
Protective Function	20.66	2.704	38
Valid N (listwise)			38

Source: SPSS 21.0 Output

The variable Reduce has a mean score of 18.97 and a standard deviation score of 2.455 while Protective Function averaged 20.66 and varied with a standard deviation score of 2.704. The variable protective function has the higher mean and standard deviation scores.

Table 4.3: Paired Samples Statistics (Reduce and User Convenience packaging)

Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation	Sample size
Reduce	18.97	2.455	38
User Convenience	19.63	2.624	38
Valid N (listwise)			38

Source: SPSS 21.0 Output

The variable Reduce has a mean score of 18.97 and a standard deviation score of 2.455 while the User Convenience function of packaging as a variable has a mean score and standard deviation score of 19.63 and 2.624 respectively. The variable user convenience function has the higher mean and standard deviation scores.

Table 4.4 Paired Samples Statistics (Reduce and Promotional function of packaging)

Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation	Sample size
Reduce	18.97	2.455	38
Promotional Function	20.87	2.723	38
Valid N (listwise)			38

Source: SPSS 21.0 Output

The variable Reduce has a mean score of 18.97 and a standard deviation score of 2.455 while the mean and standard deviation scores of the variable Promotional Function are 20.87 and 2.723 respectively. Hence, the variable promotional function has the higher mean and standard deviation scores.

4.3 Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1

H_0 : There is no significant relationship between reduced options and the protective function of packaging.

H_1 : There is a significant relationship between reduced options and the protective function of packaging.

Table 4.5: Result of Correlation Analysis Between Reduce and Protective Function of Packaging

		Reduce	Protective Function
Reduce	Pearson Correlation	1	.709
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.015
	N	38	38
Protective Function	Pearson Correlation	.709	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.015	
	N	38	38

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS Output

The Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis revealed that the correlation between reduce and protective function of packaging is positive and strong. This is because the coefficient of correlation (r) between both variables is 0.709; which is both positive and close to one (1). Again, since the p-value of t-statistic is less than the agreed 5% level of significance ($0.015 < 0.05$), the null hypothesis (H_0) was rejected, while the alternative hypothesis (H_1) was accepted. Hence it can be said that there is a strong and positive significant relationship between reduce and the protective function of packaging.

Hypothesis 2

H_0 : Reduce has no significant relationship with user convenience of product packaging.

H_1 : Reduce has a significant relationship with user convenience of product packaging.

Table 4.6: Result of Correlation Analysis Between Reduce and User Convenience

		Reduce	User Convenience
Reduce	Pearson Correlation	1	.722*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.028
	N	38	38
User Convenience	Pearson Correlation	.622*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.028	
	N	38	38

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS Output

Table 4.6 is correlation analysis revealed that there is a positive and moderately strong correlation between reduce and user convenience. This is because the correlation coefficient here is 0.622, which is a positive number and is closer to 0.5 than 1. Also, the value of t-statistic is 0.028, which falls below the level of significance, 5 percent (0.05). As such, it follows that the null hypothesis was rejected and the alternative accepted and it was therefore concluded that reduce has a positive and moderately significant relationship with user convenience function of product packaging.

Hypothesis 3

H₀: There is no significant relationship between reduce and the promotional function of packaging.

H₁: There is a significant relationship between reduce and the promotional function of packaging.

Table 4.7: Result of Correlation Analysis Between Reduce and Promotional Function

		Reduce	Promotional Function
Reduce	Pearson Correlation	1	.863
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.003
	N	38	38
Promotional Function	Pearson Correlation	.863	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.003	
	N	38	38

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS Output

The result shows that there is a strong and positive correlation between reduce and promotional function of packaging. This is because the coefficient of correlation (r) is 0.863 which is positive and close to one (1). Again, since the p-value of t-statistic is less than the agreed 5% level of significance (0.003 < 0.05), the null hypothesis (H₀) was rejected, while the alternative hypothesis (H₁) was accepted. Hence it was concluded that there is a strong and positive significant relationship between reduce and the promotional function of packaging.

The above finding is in agreement with Musa, Nasir, Ali, Al-Baraa, Ehab, Noor, Abdulrahman, Aminu & Muhammad (2021) where reduction was found to be significant when ranking reduce, reuse and recycle.

5.0 SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary

Findings from the study revealed that;

- There is a strong and positive significant relationship between reduced options and the protective function of packaging.
- The Reduce option has a moderately strong and positive significant relationship with user convenience of product packaging.
- There is a strong and positive significant relationship between reduced options and the promotional function of packaging.

5.2 Conclusion

It is obvious that protective and promotional functions of packaging seem to be highly valued more than the user convenience function.

It has been established that reduce is a viable option for sustainable packaging as it helps firms to save cost, reduce environmental waste as well as ensures societal wellbeing as advocated by societal marketing concept. The Reduce option is a necessity as it helps a firm to spend less on packaging materials. It also cuts the cost of shipping which is often tied closely to the volume or weight of products. It goes on to reduce the negative impact packaging has on the environment.

Based on the foregoing, it was evidenced that reduce is a sustainable option for the packaging of Nigerian Bottling Company in Imo State, Nigeria.

5.3 Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study and the conclusions drawn, it is recommended that NBC should place more emphasis on the use of minimal materials while maintaining protective quality of packaging.

Firms that are into the business of manufacturing packaging should invest more in materials with lower weight in order to ensure user friendliness.

Avoidance of multi-layer and secondary packaging which will promote a firm as environmentally friendly.

References

- Abila, B & Kantola, J (2019). The perceived role of financial incentives in promoting waste recycling-Empirical evidence from Finland. *Recycling*, 4(1), 4.
www.mdpi.com/https://doi.org/10.3390/recycling4010004
- Alex, T (2020). 7 ways packaging is changing to reduce plastic waste. *World Economic Forum*.
<https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2020/12/sustainable-packaging-reduce-plastic-waste/>

- Bartlett, J, Kotrlik, J & Higgins, C. (2001). Organizational Research: determining appropriate sample size in survey research. *Information technology, learning and performance journal*, 19(1), 43-50.
- Borishade, T., Ogunnaike, O., Dirisu, J & Onochie, P. (2015). Empirical study of packaging and its effect on consumer purchase decisions in a food and beverages firm. *European Journal of Business and Social Sciences*, 3 (11). 44 – 53.
- Claire, K. (2019). How to reduce packaging waste. *Institute of Food technologist*. www.ift.org
- Colleen, B. (2013). An Introduction to the Three R's of Sustainability. *Wildlife Habitat Council*. <https://www.wildlifehc.org/an-introduction-to-the-three-rs-of-sustainability/>
- Dube, N (2020). What is protective packaging? *Industrial Packaging*. <https://www.industrialpackaging.com>
- Environmental Protection Agency (2013). "Non-Hazardous Waste Management Hierarchy." *United States Environmental Protection Agency*. <http://www.epa.gov/solidwaste/nonhaz/municipal/hierarchy.htm>
- Eurostat (2021). Eurostat data on total waste generation. *Interreg Europe*. <https://www.interregeurope.eu/smartwaste/news/news-article/11581/eurostat-data-on-total-waste-generation/>
- Golding, A. (1999). Reuse of Primary Packaging – *Final Report*. Germany.
- Gordon, R. (2015). The History of the Three R's. *Recycle Nation*. <https://recyclenation.com/2015/05/history-of-three-rs>
- <https://ng.coca-colahellenic.com/>
- <https://www.bulkbagreclamation.com/what-is-green-packaging>
- <https://www.thisdaylive.com>
- Inyanga, J. & Anyanwu, A (2006). *Marketing and society*. Avan Global Publishers.
- Lesley, V. (2019). What is green marketing? 5 sustainable examples to know. *Learn G2*. www.learn.g2.com
- Loukanova, E., Jan, P & Kalamarova, M. (2016). The perception of respondents of packaging innovations in slovakia. *Semantic Scholar*. www.pdf.semantic scholar.org
- Luis, F (2017). Waste management in developing countries and the circular economy. *Waste management and research: The Journal for a sustainable circular economy*, 5 (1).
- MJS Packaging (2014). The newest trends in flexible packaging. *MJS Packaging*. www.mjspackaging.com
- Musa, M., Nasir,S., Ali, E., Al-Baraa, A., Ehab, F., Noor, A., Abdulrahman, H., Aminu, D. & Muhammad, B. (2021). Modeling of 3R. *Journal of sustainability*. 13 (19). 1066
- Ndu, O. & Nkamnebe, A. (2013). Reverse logistics management and environmental sustainability Drive in Nigeria. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 8 (16). 54. doi:10.5539/ijbm.v8n16p54
- Palmer, A. (2000). *Principles of Marketing*. Oxford University Press, Oxford
- Ramos, M., Arantzazu, V., Mellinas, A. & Garrigós. M. (2015). New Trends in Beverage Packaging Systems. *Beverages* 1 (4). 248 - 272. <https://doi.org/10.3390/beverages1040248>
- Rick, L (2019). What is reusable packaging? *The Balance Small Business*. www.thebalancesmb.com

- Roh P, Bernd M, Qiuliang H and Raoul V. (2020). Sustainable waste management for zero waste cities in China. *Clean Energy Journal*, 4 (3). 169-201. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ce/zkaa013> 06October2020 <https://www.academic.oup.com/ce/article/4/3/169/5918339>
- Saman. A., Muhammad, D., Puneet, K., Muhammad, J., Shahid, H & Amandeep, D. (2021). Drivers of food waste reduction behavior in the household context. *Journal of food quality and preference*. 94. 104300. Doi: 10.1016/j.foodqual.2021.104300
- Smith, M. (2015). The impact of environmentally friendly packaging on consumers' attitudes and patronage intentions toward apparel retail brands. *ScholarWorks*. www.scholarworks.uark.edu
- Surya, R and Vijaya, P (2014). Introduction to green marketing. *International journal of Economics and management studies*, vol 1 no 2.
- White, J (2019). Top 5 food packaging trends to watch for in 2020 *Safeopedia*. www.safeopedia.com

Unravelling Fiscal Policy Effects on Unemployment: A Nigerian Perspective through ARDL Approach

Agbadua, Oyakhiromhe Bamidel¹; Ale, Solomon Akintayo²; Chukwuto, Nnamdi Ogochukwu²; Ojeogwu, Chike Ignatius³; Okoh, Johnson Ifeanyi⁴

¹ *Department of Banking & Finance, Federal Polytechnic, Auchi, Nigeria.*

² *Bursary Department, National Open University of Nigeria, Abuja, Nigeria.*

³ *Department of Banking and Finance, Delta State Polytechnic, Ogwuashi Uku, Delta State, Nigeria.*

⁴ *Department of Financial Studies, National Open University of Nigeria, Abuja, Nigeria.*

Abstract

Research Purpose: With Nigeria facing persistent unemployment challenges, understanding the impact of fiscal policy is crucial for informed policy formulation. This study investigates the long-run effects of various fiscal policy instruments on unemployment in Nigeria.

Methodology: The study utilises annual time series data from 1980 to 2021 sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria. An Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) approach is employed to analyse the relationship between unemployment (dependent variable) and government consumption expenditure, gross fixed capital formation, exchange rate, and interest rate (explanatory variables). Stationarity is tested using the Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) test, while Johansen co-integration tests determine short- and long-run relationships.

Findings: Long-run analysis reveals a positive relationship between government consumption expenditure and exchange rate with unemployment. Conversely, interest rate demonstrates a negative long-run association with unemployment.

Conclusion: Fiscal policy significantly influences unemployment in Nigeria. While certain instruments positively impact unemployment, others can contribute to its reduction.

Recommendations: The study recommends increased government capital expenditure on infrastructure to stimulate national income and employment. Tax policies should be conducive to investment and economic activity. Combating corruption is crucial to prevent the diversion of public funds, ensuring their effective utilisation for economic growth and job creation. Finally, fiscal policies should be implemented alongside complementary monetary policies for optimal economic performance.

Key words: *Fiscal policy, Unemployment rate, Nigeria.*

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Unemployment has become a topic of global concern, spurred by shifts in labour practices during the industrial revolution that emphasised skill as essential. In Nigeria, the aftermath of the civil war exacerbated already severe unemployment, prompting urgent policy responses. Yet, governments worldwide grapple with this issue. Adawo *et al.* (2012) averred that Nigeria's unemployment data may be manipulated for political reasons, underscoring the gravity of the situation. With over 200 million people, the country struggles as less than 40% have full-time employment.

The Nigerian economy faces a myriad of challenges, leading to declining living standards and increased impoverishment. Fiscal policy interventions were intended to reverse this trend, but economic and social instability hinder long-term progress, as noted by Akanni (2013) and Adefeso & Mobolaji (2010), with significant welfare costs.

Since 1970, governments have experimented with various strategies to tackle unemployment, yet the problem persists, fueling social and economic issues like crime, corruption, poverty, and prostitution. Recent reports indicate Nigeria's unemployment rate has reached alarming levels, threatening social cohesion. Consequently, the government, in collaboration with international bodies such as the International Labour Organization (ILO), prioritises addressing unemployment.

The overarching aim of this study is to explore the impact of fiscal policy on unemployment in Nigeria, with specific objectives including:

- i. Assessing the short-term effects of Nigeria's fiscal policy on unemployment.
- ii. Evaluating the long-term impact of Nigeria's fiscal policy on unemployment rates.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

Fiscal Policy: Alex and Peter (2008) claim that fiscal policy frequently uses taxation and spending by the government as a macroeconomic strategy policy to influence the level of economic activity. Fiscal policy, in the words of Fadare (2010), is the deliberate action of the government that is used to influence or change macroeconomic indicators in the direction that is desired through spending patterns, taxing and borrowing. The objectives include stable economic expansion, high levels of employment, and low inflation. The objective of fiscal policy regularly shifts in response to the state of the economy and the goals of the government at large. Given this, reducing government expenditure and rising taxes can help to contain an inflationary economy. Government expenditure cuts and/or tax increases will result in decreased disposable income and aggregate demand, which will lower prices and a surplus supply while also lowering aggregate demand and easing inflationary pressure. On the other hand, boosting government spending and reducing taxes can be used to

stabilise a downturn in the economy. The domino effect will be the exact opposite of the circumstance we just looked at.

Prior to the advent of Keynesian economics, any situation of disequilibrium was made up for by market forces. Fiscal policy, which makes use of public funds, is based on interventionist theories that believe that market forces alone cannot correct for deviations from equilibrium. The inability of solely market economies to achieve long-term equilibrium and simultaneously adjust towards equilibrium during periods of disinformation, especially when it came to the Great Depression in the middle of the 1930s, was a devastating blow to the conventional model. Since that time, only market economies afflicted by periodic changes (which in turn are inherent in market economies) have been addressed using means of government fiscal and monetary policy. As a result, fiscal policy, according to Medee and Nembee (2011), comprises employing government expenditure, taxes, and borrowing to impact the structure of economic activity as well as the extent and rate of growth in output, employment, and total demand. It equally entails the government controlling the economy by modifying its income and purchasing power in order to achieve particular preferred macroeconomic objectives, including economic development and maintenance.

According to the Central Bank of Nigeria (2011), fiscal policy is the use of government spending, taxes, and proceeds collection to control the economy. Dornbusch and Fischer (1990) claim that the vast majority of definitions make it obvious that taxes and expenditures by the government are the two primary mechanisms of fiscal policy, although they are not the only ones. Additional fiscal policy alternatives could include public debt and public work. The authors continued by stating that the aim of fiscal policy is to affect the degree and growth of consumer demand as a whole, production, and employment. Fiscal policy has an effect on macroeconomic conditions since it affects tax rates, interest rates, and government spending. Policymakers must use particular tools to regulate or alter macroeconomic factors that benefit the economy as a whole in order to fulfill the goals of fiscal policy.

Unemployment: As compared to Adawo, Essien, and Ekpo (2012), unemployment is the condition in which people actively look for work even when they are competent, able, and prepared to do so. According to Stone (2008), in order to be considered unemployed, a person must actively seek employment (i.e., fill out an application, go to an interview, register with employment services, get in touch with businesses directly, visit school placement centres, or call either public or private employment organisations). As said by Abel, Smith and Bernanke, (2003), the twin monsters of macroeconomics—inflation and unemployment—are some of the most difficult and divisive problems that policymakers must resolve. This is so because of the widespread public anxiety caused by elevated unemployment and inflation rates induce due to their immediate and evident consequences. As unemployment rates and pricing pressures rise, economic growth and development are inhibited. The three primary types of unemployment that have been discussed in the literature are

frictional, structural, and cyclical. Employees who out of their own choice quit their occupations in search of better prospects or who are changing careers, according to Stone (2008), experience frictional unemployment because it might require days or even weeks for them to start working for their new employer. Essentially, it is claimed that someone is frictionally unemployed when they experience a brief period of unemployment as a result of changing jobs. Structured unemployment, as captured by Abel, Smith and Bernanke (2003), is brought on by shifts in consumer demand patterns or technical improvements. Before regaining employment, workers may require substantial retraining, and this is typically a protracted process. For instance, using automation in a plant can make manpower unnecessary. Downturns in the business cycle are what lead to cyclical unemployment, claims Ekpo (2017). The study asserts that this sort of unemployment can be managed by monetary and fiscal policy actions by the government. A stagnant economy might result from unemployment (unless it is voluntary), which is unfavourable because it lowers aggregate demand. The rise in the value of the gross domestic product (GDP), which can eventually lead to a recession, can be slowed by rising unemployment rates and inflation. According to Ekpo (2017), macroeconomic issues including unemployment as well as inflation triggered major changes in GDP that led to the current economic decline that occurred in Nigeria between 2014 and 2016. The ongoing economic downturn in Venezuela and other countries across the world is another proof of the crippling effects of high unemployment.

According to Adawo, Essien, and Ekpo (2012), the primary causes of unemployment in Nigeria are a shortage of electricity, a meagre road system, a weak communication system, security issues, and the authority's casual approach to job creation. The authors assert that employment was outlawed in Nigeria as well. The economy has suffered as a result, largely as a result of the fact that most people are employed by the government. Additionally contributing to the unemployment problem are unsuccessful and ineffective economic strategies. As stated by Nwosa (2015), current government trade regulations and the country's restrictive/unfavourable economic conditions have deterred investment. Because of this, many companies have shut down, investors are losing faith, and staff members have been fired off as a result. It is distressing to see the ugly effects of unemployment. Insecurity, poverty, underdevelopment, brain trench, absence of self-worth, and other emotional effects are a few of them, along with increased criminal activity. Ekpo (2017) contends that it is easier to envisage the impacts of unemployment than to really experience them, both for the individual and the economy. Numerous authors have put out a wide range of economic solutions to the unemployment problem that, if zealously implemented, may at least lessen the threat. The government should collaborate with the private sector to diversify the economy, lawful activities in the unorganised sector has to be investigated, encouraged, and given backing in their efforts, and the educational system ought to be strengthened in order to produce graduates who are suitable for employment in the workplace, according to Adawo, Essien, & Ekpo (2012).

Taxation: One of the main budgetary measures the government may use to lower unemployment is taxation. High taxes on consumers limit their purchasing power, which lowers consumption. As a result of lower consumer spending, businesses have lower income, which makes it more difficult for them to hire new employees or, in some cases, even compels them to terminate existing ones in an effort to reduce expenses. Tax reductions are regularly used by the government as a measure to encourage economic progression and reduce unemployment. Tax reductions increase spending among consumers, which can provide additional funding for business growth and employee hiring. Spending on programming could be another weapon the government uses to address unemployment. By supporting new public works projects like the building of facilities like roads or train lines, for example, the government can lower unemployment while increasing disposable income and spending. If the initiatives help the economy grow generally, there will be more jobs available once they are completed (Egbulonu & Amadi, 2016).

Keynesian Theory of Unemployment

The traditionalists' thesis of voluntary unemployment was criticised by Keynesians. Keynes suggested that the cyclical oscillations of market-based economies result in involuntary unemployment in his 1936 book. Like Marx, Keynes thought that unemployment will always exist in a completely market-based economy. During the economic downturn of the mid-1930s, market forces completely failed to correct the enormous departures from equilibrium. Unbelievably high unemployment rates were present. The state of the world economy was chaotic. The threat was too large for traditional economics to manage, it turned out. Keynes (1936) asserted that "unemployment happens whenever the economy's aggregate demand is inadequate to provide employment to everyone who needs it."

Wagner's Theory of Fiscal Policy

The economist Adolph Wagner from Germany, who lived from 1835 to 1917, established a theory on public spending after researching other countries as well as his own. Wagner (1890) stated that "for any nation, government expenditure rises continuously as revenue expands." As a result, it is anticipated that the expansion of a manufacturing-based economy will be followed by an increase in the proportion of public expenditure in the GDP. The idea is that government expenditures should generally have a positive effect on the economy, which will encourage additional spending and consequent economic growth. Wagner (1890) stated that "as progressive nations industrialise, the share of the government sector in the national GDP grows continually." As stated by Singh (2008), increased government participation and expenses are essential given the state's rising social, governmental duties, defensive, and welfare functions.

Njoku and Ihuba (2011), for instance, noted the unemployment and progress in Nigeria between 1985 and 2009. The study uncovered the intriguing discovery that between 1991 and 2006, the GDP

expanded by 55.5 percent while the overall population increased by 36.4 percent. This should have caused the unemployment rate to decrease, but instead, it increased by 74.8 percent. Nigeria's high rate of unemployment was the subject of a 2012 study by Adawo, Essien, and Ekpo. According to the evaluation, the workforce in Nigeria increased over a 33-year period at an average pace of 0.3%, indicating that unemployment was a problem for the nation's economy. Inadequate infrastructure, a lack of economic diversification, security issues, and a poor educational system that takes a long time to generate marketable graduates are all reasons for Nigeria's high unemployment rate, according to the report.

Iyeli and Azubuike (2013) conducted an experiment to investigate the results of fiscal policy factors on the economy of Nigeria between 1970 and 2011. The co-integration approach and error correction mechanism was used to examine the real gross domestic product (the dependent variable) in connection to the federal government's expenditures, federal revenues, the rate of inflation, and capital inflow (the independent variables). The study discovered a long-term equilibrium connection between fiscal policy elements and Nigerian economic growth. Samira and Khalil (2015) evaluated the effect of government civil spending on the rate of unemployment in Iran from 1997 to 2013 using the universal ADF unit root test, Johansen cointegration test, (VAR) method, and VEM. After examining the long-term relationship, it was discovered that there is a negative and significant correlation between total government expenditure and the unemployment rate. Adefeso and Mobalaji talked about Nigeria's fiscal-monetary policy and economic growth in a 2010 essay. Their major goal was to reevaluate and review the comparative impact of fiscal and monetary policies on the growth of the economy in Nigeria using annual data from 1970 to 2007. The error correction mechanism (ECM) and co-integration technique were used to carefully analyze the data and provide policy conclusions. According to their research, monetary policy has a much bigger impact than fiscal policy. They recommended increasing the importance and reliance on monetary policy in order to achieve the goal of economic stability in Nigeria.

According to Muritala and Taiwo (2011), who examined the relationship between these two forms of spending and GDP using the ordinary least squares estimation method, both recurrent and capital expenditures by governments have substantial beneficial effects on GDP, which, then steadies the economy. In an associated research project, Yahya, Haruna, and Miriam (2013) used multiple regression analysis to examine the impact of recurring and capital expenses on Nigeria's economic development using data from 1987 to 2010 and found that both effects were insignificant in terms of statistical significance, despite the fact that the influence of recurring expenditure was positive, and the impact of capital spending was adverse. Similar conclusions were found by Ogbonna and Appah (2012). Amassoma and Nwosa examined the association between output increase in Nigeria and unemployment rates from 1986 to 2010 in a study published in 2013. To analyze the relationships among the variables, the co-integration methodology and error correction model methodology were

both utilised. The results of the study show that the government must keep taking immediate action against the increasing rate of unemployment since it poses a serious obstacle to social growth and leads to ineffective utilisation of a trained workforce. This again upheld the findings of Appah (2010) and Aregbbyen (2007). Nwosa (2014) also investigated how government expenditures from 1981 to 2011 affected Nigeria's unemployment and poverty statistics. Employing the Ordinary Least Square (OLS) assessment method, he noted that government spending had a significant, beneficial effect on the rate of unemployment but a negative, slight influence on the poverty rate. Reviewing the empirical research shows that the inferences made from the data are debatable. Examining the impact of various fiscal policy initiatives on unemployment in Nigeria is the aim of this study.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

The study adopted the ex-post facto research design as the data utilised are historical in nature .The study employed a descriptive approach to research to ensure that the methodology is well-developed to gather reliable and correct data for the research task. Secondary data were acquired from the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) and Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Statistical Bulletin for that time of 1981 to 2022 in order to examine how Nigeria's fiscal policy affects unemployment. Total government spending, currency exchange rates, and interest rates are some of the main fiscal policy factors that influence the employment rate. Two of the analytical methods employed in the study to analyse the data were the error correction model (ECM) and co-integration.

Model Specification

The fiscal policy factors that must be considered include gross fixed capital creation for domestic investment, the government expenditure on consumption, the foreign exchange rate, the rate of interest, and the interest rate. The dependent variable is the rate of unemployment. The following equations represent the connection between the variables.

$$UNEMP =F(GCON, EXC ,INR, GFCF) \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

where

- UNEMP = unemployment rate
- GCON = the government consumption expenditure
- EXC = Exchange rate
- INR = Interest rate
- GFCF = Gross fixed capital formation

The econometric form of the model above is stated as:

UNRAVELLING FISCAL POLICY EFFECTS ON UNEMPLOYMENT IN NIGERIA THROUGH ARDL APPROACH

$$UNEMP_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 GCON_t + \beta_2 EXC_t + \beta_3 INR_t + \beta_4 GFCE_t + \mu_t \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

μ_t = stochastic error term

β_0 = constant intercept

$\beta_1 - \beta_4$ = coefficient of the associated variables

In order to lower the exponentially increasing values of certain of the study's variables, these variables are further turned into logarithms as follows:

$$UNEMP_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 LOG(GCON)_t + \beta_2 EXC_t + \beta_3 INR_t + \beta_4 LOG(GFCE)_t + \mu_t$$

Method of result evaluation

In this study, stationarity is evaluated using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test. This allows the Auto Regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) bound test approach to be used under the premise that the variable quantities under investigation are either integrated of order zero or order one. As a result, an order of integration was established using ADF test approaches. The null hypothesis that guided the test is stated as follows: $H_0: \beta=0$ (β has a unit root); $H_1: \beta<0$ (for alternative hypothesis). The ARDL model is written as follow:

$$\Delta UNEMP_t = \beta_0 + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_{1i} \Delta UNEMP_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \beta_{2i} \Delta LOG(GCON)_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \beta_{3i} \Delta EXC_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \beta_{4i} \Delta INR_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \beta_{5i} \Delta LOG(GFCE)_{t-i} + \delta_1 UNEMP_{t-1} + \delta_2 LOG(GCON)_{t-1} + \delta_3 EXC_{t-1} + \delta_4 INR_{t-1} + \delta_5 LOG(GFCE)_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t \dots\dots\dots(3)$$

where:

Δ = Difference operator

ε_t = Stochastic term

An Ordinary Least Square (OLS) estimation is first carried out as part of the ARDL bound test to ascertain whether there is a long-term correlation between the variables under consideration. The test is founded on an F-Statistic for the joint statistical importance of the lagged variables. The null hypothesis of no cointegration stated as: ($H_0 : \beta_1 = \beta_2 = \beta_3 = \beta_4 = 0$), for the equations are evaluated.

As a result, the fundamental premise is as follows: H_0 is rejected, concluding that the variables under investigation are cointegrated if the F-statistic is greater than the higher critical bound; otherwise, it is not accepted. The decision becomes inclusive if, however, the F-statistic, the lower critical bound, and the higher critical bound. If the null hypothesis of zero cointegration is not accepted, an

estimation of a vector error correction model (VECM) is then performed. The VECM model is therefore specified as follows:

$$\Delta UNEMP_t = \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_{1i} UNEMP_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_{2i} \Delta LOG(GCON)_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_{3i} \Delta EXC_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_{4i} \Delta INR_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_{5i} \Delta LOG(GFCF)_{t-1} + \lambda ECM_{t-1} + \mu_t \dots\dots\dots(4)$$

where:

ECM = The error correction term

λ = the error coefficient

4.0 DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Data Analysis

The empirical data is to show the significance of the connection between unemployment (UNEMP) and the fiscal policy instruments of government consumption expenditures (GCON), exchange rate (EXC), interest rate (INR), and gross fixed capital formation (GFCF).

Descriptive Statistics

Using the Jarque-Bera (JB) test statistic, the variables (control variables) were examined to determine whether the normal probability distribution applied to them. The JB test for normality, an exponential or large-sample test, calculates kurtosis and skewness measurements. In order to do this, the sample standard deviation, mean, kurtosis and skewness, Jacque-Bera statistics, and p-values are all looked at. The variables used in this investigation's descriptive statistics are displayed in the table below:

Table 1: The descriptive statistics

	UNEMP	GCON	EXC	INR	GFCF
Mean	4.338548	3.953910	459.4395	-0.019857	37.31496
Median	3.964000	2.114938	493.8285	2.683386	33.97212
Maximum	6.237000	9.448340	732.3977	18.18000	89.38105
Minimum	3.424000	0.911235	211.2796	-65.85715	14.90391
Std. Dev.	0.916070	2.882889	142.0967	14.11808	20.05444
Skewness	1.160551	0.631167	-0.169133	-2.633464	1.108071

UNRAVELLING FISCAL POLICY EFFECTS ON UNEMPLOYMENT IN NIGERIA THROUGH ARDL APPROACH

Kurtosis	2.764174	1.911888	2.067432	12.73620	3.732239
Jarque-Bera	9.525473	4.860584	1.722187	214.4348	9.533058
Probability	0.008542	0.088011	0.422700	0.000000	0.008510
Sum	182.2190	166.0642	19296.46	-0.833997	1567.229
Sum Sq. Dev.	34.40658	340.7531	827850.7	8172.131	16489.40
Observations	42	42	42	42	42

Source: Author's own computation from the E-views result, 2022

According to descriptive statistics from the outcome table above, from 1980 to 2021, four of the variables under consideration show an average positive mean value, while a single variable has a negative average value with 42 observations. According to the standard deviation, the EXC and UNEMP both had values of (142.0967), with the EXC having the lowest value. The skewness statistics in the table show that three of the variables have positive skewness, while two have negative skewness. According to the test's probability, four of the variables were found to be normally distributed because their scores in the Jarque-Bera test fell under the 5% level of significance.

Correlation

The correlation test is employed to assess how closely the variables that are independent and dependent variables are related. This is done by using the correlation matrix. To determine the level of the link connecting the independent factors and the dependent variable, we analyze the variables in the correlation test. Employing a correlation matrix, the model's depiction of the connections between the variables in investigation was evaluated. The answers of this evaluation are shown below:

Table 2: The Correlation matrix

	UNEMP	GCON	EXC	INR	GFCF
UNEMP	1.000000	-0.320324	0.302737	0.222535	-0.412387
GCON	-0.320324	1.000000	-0.758996	-0.318975	0.654954
EXC	0.302737	-0.758996	1.000000	0.366771	-0.709160
INR	0.222535	-0.318975	0.366771	1.000000	-0.476640
GFCF	-0.412387	0.654954	-0.709160	-0.476640	1.000000

Source: Author's own computation from the EViews result

The results of the correlation inquiry show that the UNEMP and two additional variables, the currency exchange rate (EXC) alongside the interest rate (INR), have positive relationships. Government consumption (GCON) and gross fixed capital formation (GFCF) both exhibit negative

signals ranging from -32% to -41%, despite the linkages being 30% and 22%, respectively. Therefore, we infer that the variables under consideration do not show multicollinearity.

4.2.3. Unit Root /Stationarity Test

Economic variables often follow a non-stationary stochastic process. The linear combination of non-stationary series is, in general, a non-stationary series that is directly related to economic theory. Using Dickey Fuller's broad Economic theory presupposes that every combination of economic variables would stagnate, hence the test is used in this study to investigate at stationary variables. Unit root testing was used to evaluate the data's time series characteristics. Engle and Granger (1987) claimed that even if the individual time series data were non-stationary, their linear combinations might be stationary if the variables were integrated in the same order. This is how the premise is defined: If the absolute value of the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test exceeds the critical threshold at the 1%, 5%, or 10% level of significance at order zero, one, or two, the variable under consideration is stationary; otherwise, it is not. The results of the ADF which stands for Augmented Dickey-Fuller are as follows:

Table 3: The Unit root test

Variable	Level difference	Probability	Order of integration	First difference	probability	Order of integration
UNEMP	-1.05414 5	0.7230		-5.975363	0.0000	I(1)
GCON	-1.80523 7	0.3730		-8.584326	0.0000	I(1)
EXC	-1.82597 9	0.3632		-5.791878	0.0000	I(1)
INR	-4.73404 2	0.0004				
GFCF	-3.07889 4	0.0359	I(0)			

Source: Author's own computation from the E-views result

The results of the stationarity tests indicate that two more variables are stationary at the level difference, while three further variables are integrated of degree one at a 5% level of significance. Cointegration can have multiple degrees of order, hence a bound cointegration test is carried out.

4.2.4 Bound auto regressive distributed lag (ARDL) testing approach

When using the ARDL bounds test technique, the variables should be I(0) or I(1); otherwise, the variable may be viewed as spurious. When doing the ARDL test, we use the Augmented Dicky Fuller (ADF) test to determine the various levels of the variables. To be able to evaluate the a closer connection over a long period where the highest lag length p is 2 in the ECM, we compute an F-statistics test approach. As a result, the following is how the results of the limits F-test are presented:

The ARDL Bound test results

ARDL Bounds Test

Date: 06/06/23 Time: 13:28

Sample: 5 42

Included observations: 38

Null Hypothesis: No long-run relationships exist

Test Statistic	Value	k
F-statistic	8.008543	4

Critical Value Bounds

Significance	I0 Bound	I1 Bound
--------------	----------	----------

10%	2.45	3.52
5%	2.86	4.01
2.5%	3.25	4.49
1%	3.74	5.06

Source: Author’s own computation from the E-views result

The Bound test result from the aforementioned table demonstrates that it is possible to create the ARDL model and determine the short-run dynamic-estimated coefficients and the long-run slope-estimated coefficients for the Nigerian balance of payments. According to the Akaike information criterion (AIC), the ARDL (1, 4) is chosen:

4.2.5 The short run error correction coefficients

Although there is an equilibrium link between the variables in the regression model over the long run, the short time is what actually influences the long term. Error Correction Mechanism (ECM) is utilised in order to fix or get rid of the disagreement that develops in the short term. The basic idea of the ECM is that if two variables cointegrate, then there must be an error-correcting mechanism to rectify short-term instability. ECM measures the speed at which a variable adjusts when it departs from its common stochastic trend. ECM makes corrections for short-run deviations from the long-run equilibrium. This demonstrates how variations in independent variables are a result of changes in explanatory factors and the drop back error component in cointegrated regression. The ECM outcome is so displayed below:

The short run error correction coefficients results

Dependent Variable: UNEMP

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(UNEMP(-1))	0.775294	0.176407	4.394909	0.0003

UNRAVELLING FISCAL POLICY EFFECTS ON UNEMPLOYMENT IN NIGERIA THROUGH ARDL APPROACH

D(UNEMP(-2))	0.659990	0.150442	4.386999	0.0003
DLOG(GCON)	0.701143	0.418071	1.677092	0.1083
D(EXC)	-0.001246	0.001406	-0.886263	0.3855
D(EXC(-1))	-0.004342	0.002451	-1.772029	0.0909
D(INR(-3))	-0.013941	0.006348	-2.196049	0.0395
DLOG(GFCF(-1))	3.023010	1.076893	2.807159	0.0106
ecm(-1)	-1.090922	0.188162	-5.797766	0.0000

Source: Author's computation from the E-views result

The results table high up can be used to compute the equilibrium error-correction coefficient, or ECM (1), which is -1.090922. The coefficient is of statistical significance and has the expected negative sign at 5% significant levels. This shows a long-term causal link between independent causes and dependent variables. Additionally, it shows that every one of the variables are cointegrated or have a long-term link. This means that the dependent variable's real values have been modified by 1.09 percent to match the values of the long-term equilibrium. A further estimate of the pace of readjustment toward long-term balance is 1.09% each year. Its t-ratio is -5.797766 and the probability of the null hypothesis being true for zero is [0.0000], which is significant even when $\alpha = 0.05$. Thus, it can also be concluded that the adjustments are quite meaningful in the short-run ARDL relationship.

4.2.6 The long run relationships exchanger rate and balance of payment in Nigeria

Long Run Coefficients results

Long Run Coefficients

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
LOG(GCON)	0.642707	0.327419	1.962950	0.0630
EXC	0.003049	0.001594	1.912536	0.0695
INR	-0.003455	0.022022	-0.156902	0.8768
LOG(GFCF)	-1.399028	0.481667	-2.904557	0.0085

C 7.017360 1.183891 5.927371 0.0000

Based on the long-term elasticity of the independent factors causing the drop in unemployment in Nigeria, the coefficient of LOG(GCON) and EXC exhibit good signs and are statistically significant. It illustrates how the currency rate and government consumption over the long run have a positive effect on the rate of unemployment. The coefficient of GFCF has a sign that is negative and is statistically significant, in contrast to the coefficients of INR, which have a negative sign but are statistically insignificant. This indicates that domestic investment throughout the research period helped the Nigerian economy's unemployment rate to drop.

4.2.7 Diagnostic test

For the purpose of determining the model's adequacy of fit, diagnostic tests are run. During the model's diagnostic tests, serial correlation, functional form, non-normality, and heteroscedasticity will all be examined.

Serial correlation tests

Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test:

F-statistic	1.282923	Prob. F (2,19)	0.3002
Obs*R-squared	4.521137	Prob. Chi-Square (2)	0.1043

Source: Author's computation from the E-Views result

The serial correlation test findings show that the null hypothesis regarding serial correlation is false, and the associated probability values of the F-statistics are not statistically significant at the 5% level. As an outcome, we draw our conclusion that the variables being examined do not exhibit serial correlation.

Figure 2 The normality test

Source: Author’s computation from the E-views result

The null hypothesis can be accepted in light of the results since the probability, 0.117817, is higher than 0.05 at the 5% threshold of significance. This cannot serve as the basis for habitually allocating the residuals.

4.2.8 The Heteroskedasticity Test

Heteroskedasticity Test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey

F-statistic	1.186991	Prob. F(16,21)	0.3509
Obs*R-squared	18.04594	Prob. Chi-Square(16)	0.3212
Scaled explained SS	8.081572	Prob. Chi-Square(16)	0.9464

Source: Author’s computation from the EViews result, 2023

Given that the likelihood of Chi-Square (16) is 0.3212, which is higher than 0.05 at the 5% level of significance, the results show that the null hypothesis is rejected. This demonstrates that there is no

heteroscedasticity in the model. Because of this, error terms from repeated sampling have homoscedasticity or a constant variance.

4.3 Restatement of Hypotheses

4.3.1 Hypothesis one

H₀: Fiscal policy does not have any considerable short-term impact on Nigeria's unemployment rate.

H₁: Fiscal policy has considerable short-term impact on Nigeria's unemployment rate.

Decision

Using Table 4.2.6 above as a guide, the decision criterion is to not reject the null hypothesis if the likelihood of the t-statistics is > 0.05 level of significance. If not, you should reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative one. We accept the null hypothesis and come to the conclusion that government consumption spending has a positive but insignificant influence on unemployment in Nigeria because Table 4.2.6 shows a positive coefficient of 0.642707 and a probability value of 0.0630 > 0.05 threshold of significance for the t-statistics.

4.3.1 Hypothesis two

H₀: Fiscal policy does not have any significant long run effect on unemployment in Nigeria.

H₁: Fiscal policy has a significant long run effect on unemployment in Nigeria.

Decision

According to Table 4.2.6 above, the null hypothesis should not be rejected if the probability of the t-statistics is > 0.05 level of significance. If not, then prove the alternative hypothesis and reject the null hypothesis. We accept the null hypothesis and conclude that the government exchange rate has no appreciable effect on unemployment in Nigeria because Table 4.2.6 shows that it has a coefficient that is positive of 0.003049 and a probability value of 1.912536 > 0.05 threshold of significance.

Decision

According to table 4.2.6 above, the null hypothesis should not be rejected if the probability of the t-statistics is > 0.05 level of significance. If not, then prove the alternative hypothesis and reject the null hypothesis. According to Table 4.2.6's negative coefficient of -0.003455 and the probability value of the t-statistics, which is -0.156902 > 0.05 threshold of significance, the interest rate in Nigeria has a negative and significant effect on unemployment. As a result, we disprove the null hypothesis.

5.0 SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary of Findings

This study assessed the effects of Nigeria's fiscal policy on unemployment. In order to ascertain the tangential connection between fiscal policy and unemployment in Nigeria, the study examined the pattern of fiscal policy instruments in Nigeria. Secondary data were acquired from multiple sources, including the CBN's statistical bulletin, for the period of 1982 to 2022. The unit root test, autoregressive distributed lag, correlation analysis, and other analytical techniques were also applied in the study.

The study's analysis revealed the following as a result:

- (i) Government consumer spending has a positive but negligible influence on unemployment in Nigeria.
- (ii) Interest rates have a favourable and negligible outcome on unemployment in Nigeria.
- (iii) Interest rates have a negative and substantial impact on unemployment in Nigeria.

Conclusion

The inability to find work prevents the poor from earning an income, which is a vital source of support. The government's capacity to restore stability to the economy and create jobs is essential to reducing poverty. The current research examined the manner in which Nigeria's fiscal policy affects employment in order to investigate this. Descriptive statistics, the Augmented Dickey-Fuller test for the unit root test, Johansen cointegration, the error correction model, the diagnostic test, and the heteroskedasticity test were all put to use in the study. The result shows that Nigeria's unemployment rate has not been significantly decreased by the government's fiscal policy measures.

Recommendations

Nigeria's unemployment condition is unbearable. The government's efforts to implement fiscal policy do not always provide the desired outcomes. Institutional shortcomings and a lack of political will are the main causes. Therefore, the analysis suggests that:

- The government should reconsider its expenditures in the country, especially on infrastructure development, in order to grow the rate of efficiency in the country and slow the economic progression needed in order to increase the employment of labour.
- By cutting corporation tax rates, the government should encourage both domestic and international investment.

- To promote gross fixed capital creation, the public and private sectors should work together. This needs to be carefully investigated since it has the capacity to scavenge idle labour force and increase productivity.
- Widening the country's economic base and putting into action a sensible mix of monetary and fiscal policies.
- Massive expansion and investment outside the oil industry of the country's economy are needed in order to raise the employment rate, particularly in the manufacturing sector and agricultural subsector.

References

- Adawo, A.M, Ekpo N.U & Essien, E.B. (2012). Is Nigeria's unemployment problem unresolvable? *Current Research Journal of Social Sciences*, 4(6), 389-395.
- Adefeso H. A., & Mobalaji H. I. (2010). The fiscal-monetary policy and economic growth in Nigeria: Further empirical evidence Pakistan. *Journal of Social Sciences*, 7(2), 137-142
- Aganga, O. (2010). Rising unemployment rate is unacceptable – Goodluck Jonathan. *Business Facts and Figures Magazine* September 2010, p. 15.
- Akanni, K.A, & Osinowo, O. H. (2013). Effect of fiscal instability on economic growth in Nigeria, *Advances in Economics and Business* 1(2), 124-133.
- Amassoma, D., & Nwosa, P. I. (2013). The impact of unemployment rate on productivity growth in Nigeria. *International journal of economics and management science*, 2(8), 1-13.
- Bassani, A & Duval (2006). Employment patterns in OECD Countries: Reassessing the role of policies and institutions. OECD Economic Department Working Papers 486, OECD Publishing.
- Burnside C, Fisher J & Eichenbaum M (2014). Fiscal shocks and their consequences. *Journal of economic theory*, 115, 89-117
- Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin (2020) Edition
- Cottarelli, C (2012). Fiscal policy and employment in advanced and emerging economies". International monetary fund, fiscal affair department.
- Dickey, D.A. & Fuller, W.A. (1979). Distribution of the estimators for autoregressive time series with a unit root, *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, 74.
- Egbulonu, K. G.& Amadi K. W. (2016). Impact of fiscal policy on inflation in Nigerian economy. *International Journal of Innovative Development & Policy Studies* 4(3),53-60.

- Ekpo, A. (1994). Public expenditure and economic growth in Nigeria 1960 to 1992. Final report. AERC, Nairobi.
- Holden. S & Sparrman V (2016). Do government purchases affect unemployment? <http://folk.uio.no/sholden/wp/fiscal-U.pdf>
- Mehmood, R., & S. Sadiq (2010), The relationship between government expenditure and poverty: A Co-integration analysis, *Romanian Journal of Fiscal Policy*, 1(1), 29-37.
- Medee & Nenbee (2011) Econometric analysis of the impact of fiscal policy variables on Nigeria's economic growth (1970–2009). *International Journal of Economic Development Research and Investment* 3(1).
- Monacelli, T & Perotti R. (2010). Fiscal policy, the real exchange rate, and traded goods. *Economic Journal*, 120, 437-461.
- Nurudeen, A. & Usman, A. (2010). Government expenditure and economic growth in Nigeria, 1970-2008: A Disaggregated Analysis. *Business and Economic Journal*, 26(4), 11-13.
- Nwosa P. I (2014). Government expenditure, unemployment and poverty rates in Nigeria” *JORIND* 12 (1).
- Olayinka I.K (2009). Economic liberalization and job creation in Nigeria, *Central Bank of Nigeria Economic and Financial Review* 47(1).
- Owolabi, A.U. (2011). Econometric evaluation of government spending, system of government and economic growth in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development* 2, (4).
- Ozurumba ,B. A (2012). Fiscal deficits and inflation in Nigeria: The causality approach *International Journal of Scientific & Technology Research* (8)
- Reem H. (2009). What is fiscal policy? *Bond International Monetary Fund*. (on-line- www.imf.org)
- Samira & Khalil. (2015). The effect of government expenditure on unemployment rate for Iran”. *International Journal of review in life science* 5(7), 109-116.